

Supplementary Material for the Publication Detecting Information Flow Security Vulnerabilities by Analysis Coupling

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1 Introduction

This report mainly provides supplementary information regarding the case study-based evaluation of our coupling approach in the article *Detecting Information Flow Security Vulnerabilities by Analysis Coupling* [35].

The coupling approach connects a model-based architectural analysis using information flow-related security characteristics of data, hereafter called *architectural analysis*, with a model-based static source code analysis detecting information flow violations in the implementation using information flow specifications, hereafter called *source code analysis*. This coupling approach comprises (1) a coupling process with process steps that have to be performed to achieve the coupling, (2) reference metamodels to which the input and output metamodels of the analyses have to conform to so that they are usable in our coupling approach and (3) necessary Integration Conditions (ICs) that have to hold so that a coupling is established. The reference metamodels and ICs allow our coupling approach to abstract from specific analyses.

We design our evaluation with the Goal-Question-Metric (GQM) approach [5] to evaluate these contributions. We are formulating the two evaluation goals **G1**: *Coverage of Reference Metamodels and Integration Conditions* and **G2**: *Accuracy regarding Architectural Vulnerabilities Arising from Non-Compliant Information Flows in the Implementation*.

With **G1** we investigate (a) whether the metaclasses of the reference metamodels are covered by the input and output metamodels of the analysis and (b) whether all ICs are covered by the transformations in successful couplings. With **G2** we investigate the accuracy of the architectural analysis in the coupling regarding architectural vulnerabilities that are expected to arise or not arise when non-compliance between the architectural analysis input model and the implementation is found.

The evaluation of **G1** is guided by three questions about whether the reference metamodels are covered by the input and output metamodels of the analyses (**Q1.1**, whether the ICs are covered on the metamodel level in successful couplings (**Q1.2**) and whether the ICs are covered on the model level in successful couplings (**Q1.3**). The evaluation of **G2** is guided by the questions about how accurate the coupling analysis is in detecting architectural vulnerabilities arising from non-compliant information flows in the implementation (**Q2**).

We use the metric *Coverage* for answering **Q1.1** to **Q1.3**. We use the metrics *Precision* and *Recall* for answering **Q2**.

We structure the remainder of this report as follows: Chapter 2 provides the foundations necessary for this report. Chapter 3 then presents details about the cases in the evaluation

of our coupling approach. Chapter 4 provides supplementary information regarding the reference metamodels and ICs, such as formalizations, refinement of the ICs, and their description on the metamodel and model level. The model-level description of the ICs is necessary as we describe most ICs only on the metamodel level due to space limitations in our article [35]. For the same reason, we combine ICs where appropriate to provide a more concise representation, making their refinement in this report beneficial. In addition, we use the formalizations to guide evaluation of **Q1.1**, **Q1.2** and **Q1.3**. Chapter 5 provides supplementary information for the evaluation of the coverage (**Q1.1**, **Q1.2** and **Q1.3**) like a formalization of the specialization of the *Coverage* metric [35]), additional artifacts, the performances determined for the coverage of the reference metamodels or the automatization of determining whether a IC holds. Chapter 6 then presents supplementary information about the evaluation of accuracs (**Q2**), such as the injected flows or examples on the calculate of true positives, false positives and false negatives.

2 Foundations

In this section, we provide the foundations for this report. This section comprises definitions of models, metamodels, and transformations in Section 2.1. Section 2.2 provides foundations about model-based security analysis.

2.1 Models, Metamodels and Transformations

A model, in this context, is an abstraction of a virtual or real entity for a given purpose with a subset of its attributes [42]. The structure of a *model* is defined by a *metamodel*, comprising allowed elements and relations between these elements [43, 1]. Metamodels are structured by *metaclasses*, and directed relations between the *metaclasses* are called *reference* [43, 1]. For the description of metamodels and models, we use the set-theoretic approach and formal terminology applied by Burger et al. [10] and Klare et al. [25]. Here, a metamodel X specifies the metaclasses $x_n \in X; n \geq 0$ and references $\langle x_i, x_j \rangle; i, j = 0 \dots n$ between these metaclasses. We denote $\langle x_i, x_j \rangle^T$ as a transitive reference from x_i to x_j if an element x_k exists with $\langle x_i, x_k \rangle$ and $\langle x_k, x_j \rangle$. An instance of a metamodel, hereafter called a model \underline{X} , contains instances of the metamodel elements $\underline{x} \in \underline{X}$ and references between $\langle \underline{x}_i, \underline{x}_j \rangle; i, j = 0 \dots n$ them. We generally denote a set of metaclasses with uppercase letters, e.g., \overline{X} . We also denote a set of instances of metaclasses with underlined uppercase letters, e.g., \underline{X} . For the description of metamodels and models, we use the Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF) [44], a popular framework for model-driven development. For more about EMF, please refer to the EMF book [44].

Model transformations translate one or more input models into one or more output models [8]. For simplification in this paper, we assume one-to-one transformations [8], i.e., the transformation receives one input model and provides one output model. The translation between elements of the input and output models in a transformation is described by *transformation rules* [43]. The transformation rules are described based on *correspondences* between the elements of the input and output metamodels defining a relation between them [38]. When a transformation rule is applied, correspondences between the input and output model elements can be captured in a *correspondence model* $CR_{X,Y}$, which is based on a *correspondence metamodel* [19]. For simplicity, we assume the correspondence metamodel only to capture correspondences between two metamodels A and B . Thus, we denote a correspondence metamodel by $CR_{A,B}$ and one of its instances with $\overline{CR_{A,B}}$. In the remainder of this paper, $a \leftrightarrow b$ denotes a correspondence between metaclass $\overline{a} \in A$ in metamodel

A and metaclass $b \in B$ in metamodel B . We denote $\leftrightarrow_{a,b} \in CR_{A,B}$ with $\leftrightarrow_{a,b} \subseteq A \times B$ as a metaclass capturing this correspondence, i.e.,

$$\forall \leftrightarrow_{a,b} \in CR_{A,B}: \exists a \in A, b \in B: \langle \leftrightarrow_{a,b}, a \rangle \wedge \langle \leftrightarrow_{a,b}, b \rangle$$

This operator can also be applied on the instance level, i.e., that $\underline{a} \leftrightarrow \underline{b}$ to denote a correspondence between an instance \underline{a} of the metaclass a and an instance \underline{b} of the metaclass b . In this line $\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{a,b} \in \underline{CR}_{A,B}$ with $\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{a,b} \subseteq \underline{A} \times \underline{B}$ denotes an instance of the metaclass $\leftrightarrow_{a,b}$ corresponding the instances \underline{a} of the metaclass a and \underline{b} of the metaclass b , i.e.,

$$\forall \underline{\leftrightarrow}_{a,b} \in \underline{CR}_{A,B}: \exists \underline{a} \in \underline{A}, \underline{b} \in \underline{B}: \langle \underline{\leftrightarrow}_{a,b}, \underline{a} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{\leftrightarrow}_{a,b}, \underline{b} \rangle$$

We define a function $fst_{cr}(\leftrightarrow_{a,b})$ and $snd_{cr}(\leftrightarrow_{a,b})$, where we interpret $\leftrightarrow_{a,b}$ as a tuple $\leftrightarrow_{a,b} := (a, b)$, thus:

$$\begin{aligned} fst(\leftrightarrow_{a,b}) &= a \\ snd(\leftrightarrow_{a,b}) &= b \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Model-Based Security Analysis

In our coupling, we focus on *model-based analyses*. In the evaluation of our coupling approach, we use the Access Analysis [28], an extended version of the Data Flow Analysis (DFA) of Seifermann et al. [41], the *Java Object-sensitive ANALysis (JOANA)* [15] and an extended version of CodeQL [11]. In the remainder of this section, we introduce the terminology we use for model-based security analyses. The architectural description in the Access Analysis and DFA is performed with the *Palladio Component Model*, which we also introduce in this section. Then, we introduce the essential parts of the Access Analysis, DFA, JOANA and CodeQL.

2.2.1 Model-Based Security Analysis

A *model-based analysis* evaluates *input models* with a certain *analysis technique* to provide an answer to a given *question* in *output models* [46]. Various *analysis techniques* are possible, such as label propagation or formal verification. The *question* to be answered by security analysis is commonly the query of whether a specific vulnerability in the system exists. The syntax of the input models and output models of *model-based analyses*, i.e., the available model elements and relations between them, can be described by metamodels or grammars. The output of a *model-based analysis* is an abstraction of the input models [45]. The output can have different formats, such as numeric values, boolean values, or more complex representations, such as examples of vulnerabilities in the form of counter-examples [46].

Specification-based analyses use specifications that define expected security characteristics [39] for system elements, e.g., on the architecture or implementation level. A security

characteristic comprises a type and a value range to describe security-relevant properties in a representation of the system or its elements, such as an architectural model [39].

The *question* whether a vulnerability exists in a system in model-based security analyses is based on the specifications and a given *security policy*. The security policy defines a state or execution as unacceptable [37].

A prominent specification-based source code analysis type is information flow analysis, such as [15, 11, 32, 3, 13]. We also use the term information flow analysis for data flow analyses, as both analyses investigate the data flow while the former also considers the control flow [4]. Specifications are used in these analyses to determine whether an unallowed information flow exists between parts of the analyzed program.

2.2.2 The Palladio Component Model

The Palladio Component Model (PCM) [36] describes component-based architectures with different views on the system, each provided in a dedicated model. We only discuss the parts of the PCM necessary in this report. For further details, please refer to the Palladio book [36]. The *Repository* model defines *RepositoryComponents*, such as *BasicComponents* or *CompositeComponents*, and *Interfaces* that contain services in the form of *OperationSignatures*. The *OperationSignatures* are structured similarly to *Method* signatures in the Java programming language, i.e., they have a name, define a *Return* type, and input *Parameters*. A *RepositoryComponent* component either *Requires* or *Provides* services in a *Interface*, which is represented by a *OperationRequiredRole* or *OperationProvidesdRole* role between the *Interface* and the *RepositoryComponent*. The *Repository* allows to define own *DataTypes*, like the *CompositeDataType*. *CompositeDataType* is defined by assembling different other *DataTypes*. *CompositeComponents* are assembled by connecting other *RepositoryComponents*. *BasicComponents* provide and require some functionality. When a *BasicComponent* provides a *OperationSignature*, it defines the Service Effect Specification describing the component's behavior when executing the service.

The *System* model assigns *BasicComponents* and *CompositeComponents* to *AssemblyContexts*. These *AssemblyContext* are then used to create the final system by connecting the *AssemblyContexts*.

The *Deployment* model uses *Resource Container* to describe available computing resources in the system. *Linking Resources* describe connections between the *Resource Container* for communication.

The *Allocation* model then allocates *AssemblyContexts*, i.e., the components, to the *Resource Containers*.

The *UsageModel* defines the interaction of a *User* with the *System*, e.g., the *Data* the user provides as input.

2.2.3 Access Analysis

The purpose of the Access Analysis [28] is to detect in a system design whether an *Adversary* in the system can reach a *Location* where *Data* is exposed through the *Interfaces* of *Components* that they are not allowed to access. We only describe the most relevant content of the Access Analysis for this report. Please refer to the report about the Access Analysis [28] for all information. For this purpose, the Access Analysis uses the PCM to describe the architecture of the system. The Access Analysis uses the *Confidentiality* model to describe, among others, *DataSets* that define some arbitrary group of data [28]. In addition, the *Confidentiality* model defines *Locations* in the system and *TamperProtection* mechanisms to avoid access to a *Location* or a *Resource Container*. The *Adversary* comprises *DataSet* defining the data they are allowed to see. In addition, an *Adversary* is assigned a location they can access and *TamperProtection* mechanisms they are able or willing to circumvent. The Access Analysis uses profile mechanisms, similar to UML-Profiles (e.g., see Pardillo et al. [33]), to annotate elements of the PCM with the information of the *Confidentiality* model. The *Information Flow* stereotype, for instance, is used to assign *DataSets* to the *Call*, *Return Value* or the data contained in the *Parameters* of a *OperationSignature*. The *Location-AndTamperprotection* stereotype assigns *Locations* and *TamperProtection* mechanisms to *Resources*. The Access Analysis calculates vulnerabilities based on a collection of prolog rules. A vulnerability is reported if an *Adversary* reaches a *Location*, e.g., by circumventing *TamperProtection* mechanisms, where the *OperationSignatures* are assigned *DataSets*, e.g., in their *Parameters*, where an *Adversary* does not have any of the *DataSets* assigned.

2.2.4 Architectural Dataflow Analysis

The DFA of Seifermann et al. [41] evaluates whether there are unallowed dataflows in the architecture of the system. A current implementation of the DFA is provided by Boltz et al. [7]. For this purpose, the DFA uses the PCM as Architecture Description Language (ADL). The DFA enables the definition of *DataDictionary*, comprising *Enums* of *Literals* defining labels for *Security Characteristic*. These labels are then assigned to *Security Characteristic* through an *EnumCharacteristic*. The DFA provides annotations *Security Characteristics* to specify characteristics of data supplied by the *User* or characteristics of *Resource Containers*. The annotation *ResourceAssignee* in the framework of Boltz et al. [7] allows specifying the values of a *EnumCharacteristic* for *Resource Containers*, e.g., whether it is located in the *EU* or not. The *UserAssignee* allows specifying the characteristics of the data provided by the *User*. The DFA then requires to specify in the Service Effect Specification how the data is propagated to the system and how the characteristics of the data are changed in this process.

In the current state of the DFA, the constraints to define when a vulnerability in the system is reported regarding the assigned security characteristics to *Data* and *Resource Containers* must be provided in a dedicated implementation. This implementation is generally specific to the *EnumCharacteristics* a user wants to analyze.

2.2.5 Java Object Sensitive Analysis

The Java Object Sensitive Analysis (*JOANA*) [15] is an information flow analysis investigating the information flows in the implementation. *JOANA* investigates the information flows in one compiled program based on call-return semantics. It analyzes direct and indirect information flows [4] in the system. For this purpose, it uses a specification of *Sources* of data and *Sinks* of data. These *Sources* and *Sinks* can be attached to program parts such as *Parameters* of *Methods* or *Fields* of *Classes*. For each *Source* and *Sink*, a *Level* are characterizing the respective data. A *Level* is represented by a *String*. A *Lattice* defines allowed flows between pairs of *Levels*. For performing the analysis, *JOANA* creates a system dependence graph and determines all flows in the system. For each detected flow from a *Source* to a *Sink*, *JOANA* determines whether it is allowed based on the assigned *Levels* and the *Lattice*. If the relation between the assigned *Levels* is not allowed, *JOANA* reports an illegal flow. For running the analysis *JOANA* uses the location of the compiled source code as input and an *EntryPoint*. The *EntryPoint* determines the starting point from which the system dependence graph is created. In addition, the *EntryPoint* defines the allowed *Levels*, the *Lattice* and which *Sources* and *Sinks* are used in the analysis.

2.2.6 CodeQL

CodeQL [11] is a framework to discover vulnerabilities in the source code. In this report, we only focus on the data flow capabilities of CodeQL. For more details about CodeQL, please visit the website [11]. It allows for the specification of queries about the code in a declarative language, resembling database query languages. For this purpose, CodeQL transforms source code, e.g., from the Java language, into a database-like representation. It provides, among others, the built-in capability to analyze data flows in the system. This data flow analysis is possible for a single code base with call-return semantics. The primary goal of the data flow analysis is to determine whether dataflows between defined sources and sinks exist. For this purpose, CodeQL requires a Dataflow or Tainttracking Configuration to generate a *Path Graph*. In this graph, the data flows are investigated. CodeQL reports a data flow if a flow between a *Source* and *Sink* is detected.

3 Cases in the Case Study

The cases in the case study comprise the coupling of an architectural analysis, a source code analysis and the application of this coupling to one case study system.

As case study systems, we used JPMail and the Travelplanner. Both comprise security specifications in literature with different semantics of the security characteristics of data. However, these systems have a message-oriented design, while *JOANA* and CodeQL(Extended) can only perform whole-program analysis of Java programs with call-return semantics. Therefore, we created whole-program Java source code with call return semantics. We describe the systems and the creation of this Java source code in Section 3.1

In our case study, the architectural analyses are the Access Analysis [28] and the Extended Dataflow Analysis (DFA-Ext), an extended version of the DFA [41]. The source code analyses are *JOANA* [15] and CodeQL Extended (CodeQL-Ext), an extended version of CodeQL [11]. We use the EMF for metamodeling and modeling. Therefore, we require all analyses to provide metamodels created with EMF. Neither *JOANA* nor CodeQL provide metamodels in EMF. Therefore, we had to provide for them EMF metamodels. We must also extend the DFA and CodeQL with additional metamodel elements and functionality to be applicable in the case study. We provide information about the newly created metamodels and the extended functionality in section 3.6.

We define how the specifications in the case study systems are realized in the Access Analysis and Extended Dataflow Analysis (EDFA) in Section 3.7.

All implementations, metamodels and models created for the case study can be found in our replication package [34].

3.1 Case Study Systems

We evaluate the increase of accuracy we achieve by application of our coupling approach [35]. In this case study-based evaluation, we use the four systems *TravelPlanner* [23], *JPMail* [47], *EclipseSecureStorage* [48] and *CoCoMe* [21, 18]. For the evaluation, we require the architectural model, the architectural specification, and a Java implementation that uses call-return semantics. In addition, we require information flows in the systems that result in values of security characteristics of data that are not consistent with the architectural specification and which influence the architectural analysis result in the coupling. There is no data set comprising all this information and artifacts to be used to evaluate our coupling approach. We, therefore, have to provide them ourselves. We, therefore, describe the architectural

model, the architectural specification, and the java implementation of our case study systems in Sections 3.2 to 3.5. All models and the reimplementations can be found in our replication package [34].

3.2 The JPMail System

The JPMail System has already been applied in evaluating approaches for analyzing data flow security by Tuma et al. [47] and Seifermann et al. [41]. These approaches have been evaluated on abstractions of the source code. The original JPMail is designed message oriented. However, the source code analyses in the case study of our evaluation [35] can only analyze information flows in Java programs with call-return semantics. Therefore, we reimplemented a simplified JPMail that contains Java method calls and returns. We implemented this using existing models and descriptions of JPMail provided by Seifermann et al. [41]. In Section 3.2.1, we present the architecture of JPMail provided by Seifermann et al. [41]. In Section 3.2.2, we define the architectural specification of JPMail for the Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext in the case study [35]. Finally, we describe our implementation of JPMail in Section 3.2.3.

3.2.1 Architectural Model of JPMail

For JPMail, we used the PCM model provided by Seifermann et al. [40] and the description of Tuma et al. [47]. In this report, we provide the structural system elements involved in the information flows relevant to evaluating the coupling approach [35]. The complete architectural model can be found in the replication package [34]. The architectural model of JPMail contains two *CompositeDataTypes* *EMailHeader* and *EMailBody* to represent the header and body of an email. A *MailSendingFacade* component provides the *MailSending* interface to the user. This interface contains the *OperationSignature* *sendMail* with the *Parameters* *header* and *body* of the types *EMailHeader* and *EMailBody*. In the system, *sendMail* declassifies the header for further use and encrypts the body. *sendMail* then calls the *OperationSignature* *dispatchMail* service in the *OperationInterface* *EMailDispatchment* provided by the *Component* *SMTP* and transmits the declassified header and the encrypted body through the *Parameters* *header* and *body*. From this call, *SMTP* calls the *OperationSignature* *dispatchMail* of the *Component* *POP3* and, again, transmits the declassified header and the encrypted body through the *Parameters* *header* and *body*. In the behavior of *dispatchMail* of *POP3*, this procedure is repeated by a call to the *OperationSignature* *dispatchMail* of the *Component* *MailReceivingFacade*. In this call, the *Parameter* *body* is decrypted, a *CompositeDataType* *email* created and then stored in the *Component* *EMailStorage* with the service *addEmail*.

We allocate the *MailSendingFacade* to the *ResourceContainer* *Alice*, the *MailReceivingFacade* on the *ResourceContainer* *Bob* and the *SMTP* and *POP3* on the *ResourceContainer* *Internet*.

3.2.2 Security Specification for JPMail

We use specifications for the expected behavior of JPMail as presented by Tuma et al. [47]. Tuma et al. [47] define the confidentiality levels of data *high* and *low* (security characteristic of data) and *AttackZones* (security characteristic), which are a non-empty set of hardware nodes where an attacker can potentially use techniques to obtain data. The components *SMTP* and *POP3* are expected to be allocated in an *AttackZone* (see Tuma et al. [47] or Seifermann et al. [40]). The *MailSendingFacade* first receives the confidential *header* and *body* of the email, i.e., both have the confidentiality *Level high*. Due to the expected *AttackZones*, the *MailSendingFacade* encrypts the *body* and declassifies the *header* in *sendMail*, i.e., lowers the confidentiality levels of the data from *high* to *low*, before sending it to *SMTP* through the *dispatchMail* service. Similarly, the *MailReceivingFacade* only decrypts the email body when the *receiveMail* service is called by a user, i.e., increasing the confidentiality *Level* of the body from *low* to *high*.

3.2.3 Reimplementing JPMail

We performed the implementation of JPMail by using the existing PCM models provided by Seifermann [40]. We used the generator PCM2Java of Kramer et al. [2], which generates Java classes, methods skeletons, and fields from a PCM repository model. This approach, however, does not translate the behavior descriptions of each provided service captured in the *SEFFs*. We implement the behavior of each *Method* in a *Class* corresponding to the *SEFF* in the corresponding providing *Component*. Each *ExternalCallAction* in a *SEFF* will be realized as a call to the corresponding *Method* of the *Interface* provided by the *Component*. The call passes the *Parameters* of the *OperationSignature* from the *SEFF* to the *Method* as described by the *VariableUsages*. For convenience, we represent *SetVariableActions* providing a new variable and *InternalCallActions* as private *Methods*. For instance, the *SetVariableAction decrypt* in the *receiveMail* of the *MailReceivingFacade* is first represented by a *Method decrypt* that uses the body of the email and a private key for decryption. This method is then called, and the result is assigned to a local variable with the name as provided in the *SetVariableAction*. We create a *Class Main*, which instantiates all classes. For this, we inspect the *System* model of PCM and create for each *AssemblyContext* an object of the corresponding *Class*. We either try to obtain a sequence to inject all objects in the constructors, or we create an object and call a setter afterward, e.g., when there are circular dependencies between two components. The complete implementation can be found in the replication package [34].

3.3 The TravelPlanner System

The TravelPlanner System [24] has already been applied in evaluating the DFA [41], the Access Analysis [28] and IFlow [24]. These evaluations either use PCM models or Unified Modeling Language (UML) models as architectural representation. The evaluation of IFlow [24] also uses source code which is provided on the TravelPlanner website [31] The

original TravelPlanner, however, is designed to be message-oriented. As for JPMail, the source code analyses in the evaluation of our coupling approach [35] can only analyze information flows established in a call-return semantic. In addition, the provided TravelPlanner implementation [31] contains IFlow [24] specific artifacts which are missing in the data set. Therefore, we reimplemented a simplified TravelPlanner that contains Java method calls and returns to the best of our knowledge. We performed this implementation by using existing models and descriptions of the TravelPlanner provided by Seifermann et al. [41], Kramer et al. [28], and the descriptions provided on the TravelPlanner website [31] and IFlow publications [23, 24]. We also extend the TravelPlanner system with architectural elements and implementations to support our evaluation of the coupling approach [35]. In Section 3.3.1, we present the realized architecture of the TravelPlanner. In Section 3.3.2, we define the architectural specification of the TravelPlanner for the Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext in our case study [35]. We extend this specification with new roles for our evaluation. Finally, we describe our implementation of TravelPlanner in Section 3.3.3.

3.3.1 Architectural Model of the TravelPlanner

For the TravelPlanner, we modified the PCM model for the Access Analysis [28], provided in the data set of Kramer et al. [22] to provide the architectural elements and specifications we require for the evaluation of our coupling approach [35]. In this report, we provide the structural system elements involved in the information flows relevant to evaluating the coupling approach [35]. Our extended TravelPlanner model comprises *BasicComponents* for the main services and applications provided by the original TravelPlanner description [31]: *TravelPlanner*, *TravelAgency*, *Airline* and *CreditCardCenter*. We also introduce the *BasicComponents* *UserInterface*, *AirlineLogger*, *LoggingDB* and *FlightStorage*. We change some of the original *OperationSignatures* of the *BasicComponents* or define new ones. The introduction of these modifications regarding the original TravelPlanner [31] has the purpose of introducing our information flows that result in values of security characteristic of data that are inconsistent with the ones specified in the architectural model to evaluate the increase in accuracy of the coupling approach [35]. These information flows are discussed later in Chapter 6. We will specifically introduce these modifications in relation to the original TravelPlanner in the following.

The *UserInterface* represents the interaction with the user and provides the *OperationSignatures* *getFlightOffers*, *confirmRelease* and *bookSelected*. The *AirlineLogger* is expected to enable logging functionality for the *Airline* in case of unexpected behaviors. This component provides the *OperationSignature* *log* with the *Parameter* *entry*. In *log*, the content should be sanitized so that no confidential information should be stored in the *LoggingDB* by passing the data with the call to its *OperationSignature* *storeLog* via the *Parameter* *entry*. After the logging is performed by the *Airline*, all flights for the airline are fetched by calling the *OperationSignature* *retrieveFlights* of the *FlightStorage*, returning the *CollectionDataType* *Flights*. The retrieved flights are then filtered by the *Airline* and successively returned to the *UserInterface*.

The *UserInterface* calls the *OperationSignature* *getFlightOffers* of the *TravelPlanner* to request a set of flights provided by the *Airline* fitting to the data provided by the *CompositeDataType* *RequestData*. The *TravelPlanner* passes this call to the *TravelAgency* through the same *OperationSignature* *getFlightOffers*. In contrast to the original *TravelPlanner*, we change the parameters of the provided *OperationSignature* *getFlightOffers* of *Airline*, which is used in the communication with the *TravelAgency*. In this operation signature, we add a *Parameter* *discount* of the *CompositeDataType* *DiscountDetails* in addition to the former *requestData* to represent possible discounts agreed upon between the *TravelAgency* and the *Airline*. We introduce new calls to other components in the behavior of *getFlightOffers* in the *Airline*: We introduce a call of the *OperationSignature* of the *AirlineLogger*

A user can then use the *UserInterface* to book a flight by calling the *OperationSignature* *bookSelected*. The *UserInterface* then calls the *OperationSignature* *bookSelected* from the *TravelPlanner*. The behavior up to the *Airline* is analog to the one described in the original *TravelPlanner* [31]. The *TravelPlanner* requests the *CreditCardCenter* to release the credit card details, captured by the *CompositeDataType* *CreditCardDetails*, for the airline. This release has to be confirmed by the user by calling the *OperationSignature* *confirmRelease* provided by the *UserInterface*. The *TravelPlanner* then receives the credit card details and calls the *OperationSignature* *bookFlightOffers* provided by *Airline*. In contrast to the original *TravelPlanner*, we add the *Parameter* *passengerDetails* of the *CompositeDataType* *PassengerDetails* to the existing *Parameters* *offerId*, representing the selected flight offer, and the *ccd_decl* representing the released credit card details. In the behavior of the *bookFlightOffer*, we also add two calls to *log* of the *AirlineLogger* and the provided *OperationSignature* *addToFlight* of *FlightStorage*. The call to *log* of the *AirlineLogger* is analog to the same call of in *getFlightOffers* of *Airline*. This time, *log* receives the *ccd_decl* to store the information, which is expected to declassify the information. It passes on this information to *storeLog* of *LoggingDB*, which stores the logged information. The *Airline* then processes the booking and adds the *PassengerDetails* to the flight by calling *addToFlight* of *FlightStorage*. In the behavior of *addToFlight*, *PassengerDetails* is added to the booked flight. The remainder of the behavior of *bookFlightOffer* is analog to the description of the original *TravelPlanner* [31]

These components are distributed over the *ResourceContainers* *AgencyServer*, *AirlineServer*, *MobilePhone*, *SupportCenter* and *FlightStorageServer*. *UserInterface*, *TravelPlanner* and *CreditCardCenter* are allocated to the *MobilePhone* of the user. *TravelAgency* is allocated to the server of the travel agency *AgencyServer*. *Airline* is allocated to the server of the airline *AirlineServer*. *FlightStorage* is allocated to the server *FlightStorageServer*, which can be used by different airlines to store their flights securely. *AirlineLogger* and *LoggingDB* are allocated to the *SupportCenter* to enable a support team to use the logs to perform maintenance tasks.

3.3.2 Architectural Specification for TravelPlanner

In the specification of the *TravelPlanner* case study, we use values of security characteristic of data representing roles as in the original *TravelPlanner* [31] and extend them with additional roles for our scenario. In addition to the roles *Airline*, *User* and *TravelAgency*

from the original specification [31], we also add the role *Support*, representing a support team that can use the logs to perform maintenance tasks.

We also use the *Security Policy* of this description, which uses a *disjunctive* representation of combined roles, i.e., a dataflow may exist between the information of roles *a* to roles *b*, if *a* comprises all roles of *b*. To assign these roles to data in the TravelPlanner, we use the original description [31]. For the existing elements of the TravelPlanner, we assign every *Parameter* in a *OperationSignature* the roles defined in the original TravelPlanner description [31]. The declassified credit card details *ccd_decl* in *bookFlight*, for instance, are assigned the roles *User* and *Airline* to state that either users or the airline system may obtain information about this data. We now discuss changes in these assignments or the roles for data in our version of the TravelPlanner that are used for extension.

In *getFlightOffers* of *Airline*, we assign the roles *TravelAgency* and *Airline* to the *discount* as the discount information should only be accessible by employees of the travel agency and the airline. The *entry* of the *log* in the *AirlineLogger* contains data that are accessible by *Airline* and *Support*. The *entry* of the *storeLog* in the *AirlineLogger* contains data that are accessible by *Support*. In performing the booking process, we define for *bookFlightOffer* of *Airline* that the provided *passengerDetails* contain information allowed to be accessed by *Airline* and *User*. For *addToFlight* in *FlightStorage*, we expect the information in *passengerDetails* and *flightId* to be accessible by the role *Airline*.

3.3.3 Reimplementing TravelPlanner

We reimplemented TravelPlanner using the existing PCM models provided by Kramer et al. [22]. We used the generator PCM2Java of Kramer et al. [2], which generates Java classes, methods skeletons, and fields from a PCM repository model. This approach, however, does not translate the behavior descriptions of each provided service captured in the *SEFFs*. We implement the behavior of each *Method* in a *Class* corresponding to the *Sequence Diagram* provided in the original TravelPlanner description [31]. As the original TravelPlanner is designed to be message-oriented, we translated each message as a call to the corresponding *Method* method, which is also provided in the architectural model as *OperationSignature* provided by a *Component*. The call passes the *Parameters* accordingly to the parameters of the messages. We represent the messages and calls *RetFlightOffersTP* and *GetSingleSelection* in the original TravelPlanner description [31] as returned *FlightOffers* for the sequential calls *getFlightOffers* from the *UserInterface*. The newly introduced method *log* (*AirlineLogger*) directly calls the *storeLog* (*LoggingDB* without further actions. *storeLog* (*LoggingDB* mocks storing the information in a database and performs no further actions. Both methods do not provide any return value.

Similar to the usage of the logging functionality, we introduce calls to *retrieveFlights* and *addToFlight* in the *Methods* *getFlightOffers* and *bookFlightOffer* respectively. *retrieveFlights* returns a filtered list of *Flights* that contain the respective *airlineId* without further side effects. *addToFlight* adds the passed *passengerDetails* to the flight with the passed *flightId* without further side effects.

We insert the two *Fields* *ccd* to *CreditCardCenter* and *passengerDetails* to *TravelPlanner*. *ccd* is specified in the original *TravelPlanner* description [31] to contain user details. We introduce *passengerDetails* to provide an information flow to evaluate the increase of accuracy of our coupling approach [35], as discussed later in Chapter 6.

We found a bug in the *JOANA* tooling, which does not compute an information flow if a *Method* does directly pass a *Field* to a call of another *Method* without further behavior. We expect this behavior of *JOANA* to be a bug as *CodeQL* computes an information flow for such calls. This is why we introduce an artificial check if *passengerDetails* is null in *bookSelected* of the *TravelPlanner* to enable *JOANA* to calculate the proper information flow as shown in listing 3.1. The effect of the bug is shown especially as we do not see the created *details* but pass the *this.passengerDetails*.

```
1 public boolean bookSelected(FlightOffer flightOffer) {
2
3     CreditCardDetails ccd_decl = declassification.releaseCCD(flightOffer.
4         airlineId);
5     PassengerDetails details = null;
6     if(this.passengerdetails != null) {
7         details = this.passengerDetails;
8     } else {
9         details = new PassengerDetails("John", "Doe", 20);
10    }
11
12    return airlinebooking.bookFlightOffer(flightOffer.id, ccd_decl, this.
13        passengerDetails);
14 }
```

Listing 3.1: Workaround for JOANA detecting information for directly passed fields

3.4 Eclipse Secure Storage

The Eclipse Secure Storage system has been applied to evaluate SecDFD from Tuma et al. [48], which determines the compliance between dataflow diagrams and the implementation. Tuma et al. [48] provide the dataflow diagrams, the implementation and the ground truth in a GitHub Repository [16]. The security specification is based on the notion of *confidentiality level* with the values *high* and *low*. We will discuss the full specification of Eclipse Secure Storage in Section 3.4.2

The Eclipse secure Storage is designed to be a single application that contradicts the component-based principle where components are allocated on different resources used in our analyses in the case study (the extended DFA and the Access Analysis). This is why we perform an evolution step to where we deploy the relevant elements to different resources, which we will describe in Section 3.4.1. After creating the corresponding architectural design, we applied the architectural analyses of our evaluation. These DFA-Ext showed that a vulnerability exists based on the original behavior of the implementation. As we require

for the evaluation of accuracy system designs that are free of vulnerabilities, we adapted the behavior of the system accordingly. We will discuss this issue further in Section 3.4.3. Also, Eclipse Secure Storage is heavily dependent on external library functionality that could not be used with *JOANA*. However, this functionality does not influence our analyzed cases, which is why we removed them. We describe this in the discussion regarding reimplementation in Section 3.4.4.

3.4.1 Architectural Model of Eclipse Secure Storage

Tuma et al. [48] provide the data flow diagram regarding parts of the Eclipse Secure Storage, while we require a component diagram. Thus, we used the description of Tuma et al. [48] and the implementation they provide [16] to extract a component-based architecture in our evolution step. We extracted the two components *PasswordManagement* and *SecurePreferences*. The *PasswordManagement* component is responsible for executing the procedure to set up the master password recovery and also to execute the recovery itself. The *SecurePreferences* component is responsible for storing and providing the (encrypted) master password and the questions the user has to answer for the recovery.

The implementation of *SecurePreferences* does not implement any *Interface*. However, this is necessary in component-based systems. Thus, we created the *Interface ISecurePreferences-Main* that contains all methods of the *SecurePreferences* class. This interface is provided by the *Component SecurePreferences* and required by the *Component PasswordManagement*. This *Interface* contains, amongst others, the *OperationSignatures put*, *node*, and *internalPut*, which are relevant for our case study. *internalPut* has the parameters *key* and *value*, both of the type *String* and does not have a return type. This *OperationSignature* puts the provided *key* and *value* in an internal storage (i.e., Key-Value Map in the implementation). *node* has the parameter *pathName* of type *String*. This service is meant to obtain the *node* at the provided path. In the original implementation, this service returns a *SecurePreferences* object. In order to maintain as much of the original implementation as possible, we use a dummy *CompositeDataType SecurePreferences* in the PCM. *put* has the parameters *key* and *value* of type *String*, *encrypt* of type boolean. In addition, the original implementation provides the parameter *container* of the type *SecurePreferenceContainer*, which passes an object of the class *SecurePreferenceContainer*. Again, we use a dummy *CompositeDataType* named *SecurePreferenceContainer* for mocking this to maintain as much of the original implementation as possible. For both mocked classes in component-based systems, either an internal routing would be necessary to invoke the correct component or another type of identification to identify the correct *SecurePreferences* or *SecurepreferencesContainer*. This method stores the provided *value* either in clear text (*encrypt = false*) or encrypts it before (*encrypt = true*) for the provided *key*.

The *PasswordManagement* in the original implementation does not have an interface. Thus, we created an *Interface IPasswordManagement* with, amongst others, the *OperationSignature setupRecovery* which is provided by *PasswordManagement*. We used the implementation to define the parameters of *setupRecovery*: *challengeResponse*, *moduleID* and *container*. In the

implementation, *challengeResponse* uses a two-dimensional String array `String[][] challengeResponse` for which we created an *CollectionDataType* with the name *String_ArrayArray*. This identifier simplified handling of the transformation but could also have been realized by combining different *CollectionDataTypes*. *moduleID* is of the type *String*. In the implementation, *container* is used to execute the correct *SecurePreferences* object. We use the approach to mock this as in the *Interface ISecurePreferencesMain*. In normal component-based architectures, *SecurePreferences* would be realized by encapsulating it behind its services.

In the *setupRecovery* service, the correct *SecurePreference* object corresponding to the *moduleID* is obtained. Then, a *String internalPassword* is calculated (“mashed”) from the provided answers. With this *internalPassword*, the master password is encrypted and stored with the *internalPut* service of *SecurePreferences*. Afterwards, the questions are stored using the *put* service of *SecurePreferences* requesting their encryption.

The component *PasswordManagement* is deployed on the *ResourceContainer UserPC* and the *SecurePreference* is deployed on the *ResourceContainer DataBase*. Both resources are connected with the *LinkingResource Network*.

3.4.2 Security Specification for Eclipse Secure Storage

We use the specifications for the expected behavior of JPMail as presented by Tuma et al. [48]. Tuma et al. [48] define the confidentiality levels of data with the values *high* and *low* similar to JPMail described in Section 3.2.2. Tuma et al. [48] specify the parameter *challengeResponse* in the service *setupRecovery* to be classified as *high*, while all parameters of the services *internalPut*, *put* and *node* provided by the *Component SecurePreferences* are specified as *low* as all confidential information (i.e., *the master password*) should be encrypted with the answers from the user.

As Tuma et al. [48] did not use component-based systems, they did not have to define the locations of the resources. However, this information is necessary for the DFA-Ext and the Access Analyses. Consequently, we adapted the approach of Tuma et al. for JPMail (see Section 3.2.2) to assign the *ResourceContainer UserPC* to a trust zone and the *Resource Container DataBase* to an attack zone.

3.4.3 Addressing Security Vulnerabilities in Evolved Design

When performing our evolution step, using the *put* service for storing questions in the *setupRecovery* service of *PasswordManagement* resulted in an architectural vulnerability, as adversaries could observe the *high* questions in the parameter *value* in this communication. For our evaluation of accuracy, however, we require an implementation that is free of vulnerabilities. Consequently, we adapted the design so that the questions are encryption with the same method the master password has been encrypted. Therefore, the questions

```

tatic private String mashPassword(String[] answers) {
    \\ code for mashing the password ...
    try {
        \\ code for creating an internal password
    } catch (NoSuchAlgorithmException e) {
        (-) String msg = NLS.bind(SecAuthMessages.noDigest, DIGEST_ALGORITHM);
        (+) String msg = SecAuthMessages.noDigest;

        AuthPlugin.getDefault().logMessage(msg);
        internalPassword = mix.toString();
    }
    return internalPassword;
}

```

Listing 3.2: Example of modified code in Eclipse Secure Storage to remove Eclipse plugin dependencies. Red text and (-) indicates removed code and blue text and (+) indicates new code. Most data types and error-handling omitted to improve readability.

are also encrypted and are then stored with the *internalPut* service. This results in the architectural analyses not reporting any vulnerabilities.

3.4.4 Reimplementing Eclipse Secure Storage

We use the majority of the existing implementation of the Eclipse Secure Storage as used by Tuma et al. [48, 16]. However, Eclipse Secure Storage uses the Eclipse Plugin infrastructure to connect to Eclipse. In addition, it uses libraries provided by the Eclipse platform or Eclipse plugins, e.g., the class `org.eclipse.osgi.util.NLS` for message formatting or the class `org.eclipse.core.internal.runtime.RuntimeLog` for logging. However, *JOANA* cannot handle these functionalities as they are only known when using the Eclipse platform. Consequently, we removed all parts of the implementation that involved dependencies on Eclipse plugins or the Eclipse platform. In principal, this involved searching for functionalities provided in sub-packages of `org.eclipse.osgi`, `org.osgi` or `org.eclipse.core`. For the removal of dependencies regarding logging, for instance, we removed the call to the class `NLS`, and provided an alternative message without it, as shown in Listing 3.2. Alternatively, we removed functionality logging functionality such as in the `AuthPlugin.java` to using `FrameworkLog`. Another example is removing the definition of `AuthPlugin.java` by removing that the class `AutPlugin` implements the `BundleActivator` interface. We provide the result in the replication package [34].

3.5 CoCoME

CoCoMe has already been applied in evaluating approaches involved in information flow by Tuma et al. [48], Gerking et al. [14], or Greiner [17]. In addition, Greiner and Herda [18]

describe *CoCoMe with Security* where they describe adversaries and security characteristics of data. The security characteristics of data represent the roles an adversary requires to be allowed to obtain the data in the system. These roles are described as *disjunctive lattice* (see our article [35]). However, *CoCoMe with security* only describes the system structure, i.e., components, their interfaces, how the components are connected, and the annotation of the security characteristics of data. For these descriptions, they provide a PCM model and security specification in form of an Access Analysis model. However, they omit information like locations, behavior descriptions or deployment. Still, we require this omitted information for the DFA-Ext or the Access Analysis. This is why we used the information from the original *CoCoMe* [18] and the description of *CoCoMe with Security* to extend the existing model of *CoCoMe with Security*. After performing the extension, we applied the Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext to the model. Both analyses found vulnerabilities. However, as described in our article [35], we require for our evaluation of accuracy an architectural model that is free of vulnerabilities. We further extended the architectural model and implementation. We describe the parts of the resulting architectural model of the extended *CoCoMe with Security* in Section 3.5.1 that are relevant for the evaluation. We then present the specification in Section 3.5.2. As JPMail and the TravelPlanner, *CoCoMe* is mainly designed to be a message-oriented system. Thus we use the same procedure as for JPMail and the TravelPlanner and reimplement our extended *CoCoMe with Security*. This reimplement is further detailed in Section 3.5.3

3.5.1 Architectural Model of the Extended CoCoMe with Security

Our extended *CoCoMe with Security* comprises 14 Components and 19 Interfaces. For the sake of brevity, we now only describe the components and interfaces relevant for our evaluation. All models can be found in our replication package [34]. *CoCoMe with Security* comprises, amongst others, the components *CardReader*, *Printer*, *Bank* and *CashDesk*.

The component *CardReader* provides the *Interface CardReaderOutIF*, which provides the *OperationSignatures readCardNumber* and *readPIN*. *readCardNumber* comprises the *Parameter number* and *readPIN* comprises the *Parameter pin*. Both parameters are integers. In the *CoCoMe with Security* by Greiner and Herda [18], there was also the *Operation Signature readCardNumber* with the *Parameter number(last four digits)*, which should represent a declassified version. For our evaluation, we removed this *Operation Signature* because of two reasons: (1) Using a second function for this declassification by reading the *number* a second time is unrealistic. The more probable case is that the card number is read and then declassified by the system. (2) We also made this decision because we explicitly circumvent this declassification in our case study. The *CardReader* also requires the *Interface CardReaderOutIf* to communicate the *number* and *pin* to the system. The component *Printer* is responsible for printing details like the shop items, the total amount to be paid, or the details about the payment card on a sheet of paper. For this, the component *Printer* provides the *Interface PrinterIf* with, among others, the *OperationSignature printPaymentCard*. *printPaymentCard* comprises the parameter *cardNumber* and prints its content onto the paper. The component *Bank* enables the cash desk system to perform the bank transactions when

paying by card. For this, *Bank* provides the *Interface BankTransactionIF* with the *OperationSignature requestTransaction*. *requestTransaction* comprises the parameters *cardnumber*, *account* and *amount*. While *cardnumber* and *amount* are of type *Integer*, the *account* is of the *CompositeDataType Account*. The *CashDesk* is responsible for performing the shopping procedure. For this, the *CashDesk* provides the *Interfaces ScannerIf, CardReaderIf* and *CashBoxIf* and requires the *PrinterIf*. In our evaluation, *ScannerIf* is not relevant as they only provide data allowed to be known by all adversaries (detailed later in Section 3.5.2). The *CashBoxIf* comprises, amongst others, the *Operation Interface startNewSale* without parameters to start a new sale process. The *CardReaderIf* comprises the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* with the parameters *number* and *id*, both of the type *Integer*. *readCardNumber* is responsible for receiving the card number to be printed on the receipt for the customer. Originally, *CardReaderIf* also comprises the *OperationSignature readPin* with the parameters *pin* of type *Integer* and the *Operation Signature readCardNumber* with the *Parameter number(last four digits)*. We combined both *Operation Signatures readCardNumber* to a single one due to the same reasons for the *Operation Signature readCardNumber* in the *Interface CardReaderOutIf*. These *OperatonSignature* existed because Greiner and Herda [18] specified that the whole shopping process, including the bank transaction, is performed on the *CashDesk*. However, this resulted in the Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext reporting vulnerabilities. This is why we introduced the component *Billing* to handle the information flows between the *CardReader*, the *Bank*, and the *CashDesk* in a confidential manner. This is why the component *Billing* provides the *Interfaces CardReaderOutIf* and *billingInteraction* and requires the *Interfaces BankTransactionIf* and *CardReaderIf*. The *BillingInteraction* interface comprises the *OperationSignature registerSale* with the *Parameters id* and *amount*, which is responsible for registering a performed sale that has to be paid by card. With these components and interfaces, we can now assembly the sub-parts of the system relevant for our evaluation. The *CashDesk*, *CardReader* and *Bank* are connected to *Billing* with their respective required and provided interfaces.

With these sub-parts, a sale can be executed as follows: The sale is started by the service *startNewSale* of *CashDesk*. Then, the items to be sold are read with the *BarCodeScanner* (not described in this section) and the total amount of money is calculated. If the customer selects the option to pay by card, the transaction is registered at the component *Billing* with the service *registerSale*. The customer then provides his *CardNumber* and *Pin* with the respective services at the *CardReader*. This information is then passed to the component *Billing* with the services *readPIN* and *readCardNumber*. From the *Pin* and *CardNumber*, the *Account* is derived. With this information, the *Bank* transaction is performed with the bank with the service *requestTransaction*. If the transaction is successful, the component *Billing* first declassifies the card number (e.g., using the last four digits as proposed by Greiner and Herda [18]) and then calls the service *readCardNumber* of the component *CashDesk* to print the stored amount of money and the declassified number of the card performing the payment on the receipt.

In our extended *CoCoMe for Security*, there are eight *Resource Containers* to which the components are allocated. Again, we only describe the *Resource Containers* and allocations relevant for our evaluation. The *Resource Container CashDeskPC* is used to allocate the *Components BarCodeCanner* (not described here) and *CashDesk*. The *Resource Container*

CardReader is used to allocate the *Component CardReader*. The *Resource Container BankServer* is used to allocate the *Component Bank*. The *Resource Container CashDeskInternals* is used to allocate the *Component Billing*. The *Resource Container OutputDevice* is used to allocate the *Component Printer*.

3.5.2 Security Specification for CoCoME

We use the security specification of *CoCoMe with Security* from Greiner and Herda [18]. In this specifications, there exist several basic values of security characteristics of data representing the roles of the adversaries in the system. The values are: *Customer*, *Cashier*, *ByStander*, *Bank*, *StoreManager* and *OtherStore*. However, we made one adaptation to the specified security characteristics of data for the parameter of the interfaces. We only discuss the specifications relevant for our evaluation and this adaptation for the sake of brevity. Please refer to Greiner and Herda [18] or our replication package [34] for all specifications.

We adapted the *Parameter cardnumber* of the *Operation Signature requestTransaction* in the *Interface BankTransactionIf* to now be specified with the values *Bank* and *Customer* which were priorly specified also to be accessible by the *StoreManager*, *Cashier*, *Customer* and *Bank*. The rationale behind this is that the full details should only be visible by the *Bank* and the *Customer* to avoid misuse by the other parties. The *Parameter pin* and *Parameter number* of the *Operation Signatures readPIN* and *readCardNumber* of the *Interface CardReaderOutIf* are specified to be only accessible by the *Customer* and the *Bank*. The *Parameter number* in the *Operation Signature readCardNumber* in the *Interface CardReaderIf* is specified to be accessible by the *StoreManager*, *Cashier*, *Customer* and *Bank* and *ByStander*. This specification signals that the *number* has to be declassified before providing it in this service, as discussed in the Section 3.5.1. This specification is also performed for *cardNumber* for the same reasons.

We now define which adversary has access to which *Resource Container*: The *Customer* has access to the *Resource Containers OutputDevices* and *CardReader*. The *Bank* has access to the *Resource Container BankServer*. The *Cashier* has access to the *Resource Container CashDeskPC*. The *ByStander* has access to the *Resource Container OutputDevices* as they are given access to all actors in the shopping queue.

3.5.3 Reimplementing CoCoME

We performed the implementation of JPMail by using the existing PCM models provided by Seifermann [40]. We used the generator PCM2Java of Kramer et al. [2], which generates Java classes, method skeletons, and fields from a PCM repository model. This approach, however, does not translate the behavior descriptions of each provided service captured in the *SEFFs*. We implement the behavior of each *Method* in a *Class* corresponding to the *SEFF* in the corresponding providing *Component*. We translated the *SEFF* similar to *JPMail* (see Section 3.2.3) if existent. For our extension, we performed the implementation of the behavior when the card number and pin are available as illustrated in Listing 3.3 and as

```

@Override
public void readCardNumber(int number) {
    Account acc = retrieveAccount(pin, number);
    Acknowledgement acknowledgement = banktransactionif.requestTransaction(number, acc,
        amount);

    if(acknowledgement.getSuccess()) {
        //Omit declassification here to mimic unclear specifications who declassifies
        cardreaderif.readCardNumber(number, id);
    }
}
}

```

Listing 3.3: Example of behavior in reimplementing of CoCoME omitting declassification.

described in Section 3.5.1. We create a *Class Main*, which instantiates all classes in the *Method main*. For this, we inspect the *System* model of PCM and create for each *AssemblyContext* an object of the corresponding *Class*. We either try to obtain a sequence to inject all objects in the constructors or we create an object and call a setter afterward, e.g., when there are circular dependencies between two components. The complete implementation can be found in the replication package [34].

3.6 Extensions of Analyses and their Metamodels

In this section, we present the extensions of the analyses, their input metamodels or output metamodels for evaluating our coupling approach [35]. We could not use the original CodeQL to analyze security characteristic of data-based information flow, which is a prerequisite for our coupling approach. We present the performed extension of CodeQL in Section 3.6.1 to enable security characteristic of data-based information flow analysis and provide metamodels to capture the input and output of the analysis. While *JOANA* does not need to be extended for the analysis, it does not provide EMF metamodels for its input and output. However, these metamodels are necessary for the evaluation in evaluating our coupling approach [35]. This is why we describe the created metamodels in Section 3.6.2. The DFA of Seifermann et al. [41] does not provide the capability to annotate *System Elements* of the PCM with security characteristics of data that can be annotated in *JOANA* or the extended CodeQL, i.e., *Fields in Classes* or *Parameters in Methods of Classes*. However, this capability is necessary for the DFA to be applicable in our coupling approach [35]. We created an extension metamodel for annotating parameters of the PCM with characteristics. Additionally, we created analysis capabilities that consider these annotations. These extensions are described in Section 3.6.3.

In our coverage evaluation of the coupling approach [35], we use correspondence (meta)models defining correspondences between elements of the input and output models of the analyses. As described by Talcott et al. [46], the output of an analysis is the abstraction of the input model. Moreover, an output representing counter-examples [46] uses representations of the

instances of the input model. Therefore, in EMF, the output (meta)models could directly use elements of the input (meta)models. However, this would result in trivial correspondences. In addition, *JOANA* and *CodeQL* currently only provide textual output that uses identifications of the elements of their input models. They identify a class, for instance, by its fully qualified name. We create the metamodels as close to the textual output as possible. A class in our metamodel, for instance, would be created as a separate metaclass containing an attribute to provide its fully qualified name instead of referencing the class in the input (meta)model. To create the input models from the textual output, we also provide parsers, transforming the textual output of the analyses in our output metamodel. We provide these parsers in the replication package [34].

3.6.1 Extending CodeQL

For utilizing *CodeQL* in our case study, we extend it to use security characteristics of data in its data flow analysis. *CodeQL* provides a declarative language for creating queries to analyze source code, comprising predicates to define the final query. For documentation about *CodeQL*, please refer to the website [11].

For our extension, we provide a set of predicates to extend the analysis query and metamodels capturing the input and output of the extended *CodeQL*, hereafter named *CodeQL-Ext*.

3.6.1.1 Extending CodeQL to Perform a Characteristic-based Dataflow Analysis

We extend *CodeQL* for our evaluation to analyze security characteristic of data-based data flow. We achieve this by defining predicates that allow us the following capabilities:

- provision of security characteristics of data to *Parameters* and *Fields*.
- the connection of these annotated elements to the *Sources* and *Sinks* used in *CodeQL*.
- querying the security characteristics of data for the *Parameters* and *Fields*.
- definition of security policies, i.e., lattices with allowed flows regarding the security characteristics of data.
- representation of the results in a format corresponding to our reference metamodel for the output metamodels of analyses.

CodeQL is a declarative language. For non-intrusive extensions, we must define every additional information in so-called predicates, which are functions in *CodeQL* that either provide a return value or simply hold or not. For the annotation of specific *System Elements*, i.e., *Parameters* and *Fields*, we require the definition of security characteristics of data and the annotation itself.

```

1 newtype SecurityLevel =
2     High() or
3     Low() or
4     None()

```

Listing 3.4: Example for a SecurityLevel type in JPMail

To provide the security characteristics of data, we declare a new type in CodeQL with the *newtype* keyword. This new type is called *SecurityLevel* and comprises a set of values. In addition, we provide a value *None* stating that a *System Element* does not have any security characteristics of data assigned. The definition of *SecurityLevel* for the JPMail system is presented in listing 3.4. We also provide the *getLabelAsString* function, which provides a string representation of each value of *SecurityLevel*. Here, the values comprise *High* and *Low*. It would also be possible to represent the values only as strings. However, we decided on the type to have type-safety in the query.

CodeQL builds a dataflow graph to investigate the data flow. This dataflow graph consists of *Nodes* representing system elements containing data and *Edges*, connecting these elements if a flow exists. Therefore, annotating the security characteristics of data to system elements requires providing this information relative to a *Node*. We perform the annotation and query in a single predicate *getLabel*, which takes a node as a parameter and returns a value of the *SecurityLevel* type for a system element. We provide two predicates for specifying a system element annotated in a node: *getParameter* and *getField*. *getParameter* identifies parameters by the name of the class, the name of the method, and the name of the parameters. This is a rather lightweight identification and does not cover every use case, e.g., method overloading, but it suffices for our evaluation. This predicate uses these names and the node as input and returns whether the node contains a parameter in a method, which is contained in a class, all with respective provided names. *getField* is defined similarly by specifying the field by its name and the name of the class where it is defined. With *getParameter* and *getField*, annotations can be performed with the predicate *getLabel* by defining the value of the *SecurityLevel* type, which is returned when the node contains the specified system element. If the node does not fit any specified system element, the value *None* of *SecurityLevel* has to be returned.

```

1 SecurityLevel getLabel(DataFlow::Node node){
2     labelParameter("MailSendingFacade", "sendMail", "header", node) and
3         result = High() or
4     labelParameter("MailSendingFacade", "sendMail", "body", node) and
5         result = High() or
6     labelParameter("SMTP", "dispatchMail", "body", node) and result = Low()
7     or
8     labelParameter("POP3", "dispatchMail", "body", node) and result = Low()
9     or
10    result = None()
11 }

```

Listing 3.5: Abbreviated example for the getLabel predicate for the JPMail specification

An abbreviated example for the JPMail case study is presented in listing 3.5. With this approach, we now must define the sources and sinks relevant to inspection in the data flow analysis. We specify that all annotated system elements are sources and sinks to inspect

every flow between them. This is performed by using a predicate *hasLabel*, which checks whether *getLabel* does not return the value *None* for a dataflow node. Now, in the CodeQL dataflow Query, we define the *isSource* and *isSink* predicate to hold if *SecurityLevel* for the node is not *None*.

```

1 predicate allowedFlows(SecurityLevel source , SecurityLevel sink){
2   source = Low() and sink = High()
3   or getLevelAsString(source) = getLevelAsString(sink)
4   or exists(SecurityLevel l | allowedFlows(source , l) and allowedFlows(l ,
      sink))
5   or none()
6 }

```

Listing 3.6: allowedFlows predicate for defining the lattice in the JPMail specification

We must also specify the security policy for defining a security characteristic of data-based data flow analysis. We use a transitive *lattice* as security policy in our query, which is defined in the predicate *allowedFlows* with the two parameters *source* and *sink* with the type *SecurityLevel*. An example of an *Lattice* with the values *High* and *Low* for the JPMail specification is presented in listing 3.6. In this predicate, every allowed flow between the two values of *SecurityLevel* is defined by connecting them with a *and* statement. Therefore, the predicate holds if the *source* and *sink* values hold for one of the statements (line 2). We extend this definition by adding the condition that a flow to the same element is always allowed (line 3) and that transitivity is also considered. Allowed flows between the same value of *SecurityLevel* are based on the string representation as CodeQL does not allow comparing types defined with *newtype* in our applied version. We consider transitivity by providing a respective transitive function (line 4). If the direct allowed relations, the condition for the same value, and the transitive relations do not hold, the default value of CodeQL *none* is returned.

```

1 from MyTaintFlow :: PathNode source , MyTaintFlow :: PathNode sink
2 where MyTaintFlow :: flowPath(source , sink) and source != sink and not
      isFlowAllowed(source . getNode() , sink . getNode()) and notEqualElements(
      source . getNode() , sink . getNode())
3 select sink . getNode() , source , sink , printResult(source , sink)

```

Listing 3.7: Query of our CodeQL extension

With these predicates, we can formulate the data flow query based on security characteristics of data as presented in listing 3.7. The query is case-independent, i.e., every case-dependent information exists in the predicates defined before. We modify the *where* and the *select* of the query compared to the data flow analysis not considering security characteristics of data. In the *where* part, we want to output only flows in our analysis if

1. a dataflow between the defined source and sink exists,
2. the nodes of the source and the sink are not equal,
3. the flow is not allowed based on the security policy and
4. the system elements of the sources and the sinks are not equal.

We provide a predicate for condition 4. which checks the equality of system elements of two nodes by comparing the packages, the class names, and either the field name or the method name and parameter name as shown in. For checking whether a flow is not allowed based on our security policy, we provide a predicate that takes the source node and the sink node and resolves the values of the *SecurityLevel* for them and if they are allowed based on the *allowedFlows* predicate. With this approach, we get all data flows that are not allowed based on our security policy.

In the *select* statement, we define how these flows should be provided in the output. CodeQL allows the definition to print a readable message to capture the output information. We define this message in the *printResult* predicate. This predicate receives the source node and sink node as input and provides them as tuples of an identification of the *System Element*, i.e., *Parameter* or *Field*, and the string representation of the value of *SecurityLevel*. We provide formatting predicates for the *System Elements* called *printParameter*, *printField*, and a function *getNodeLevelAsString* to get the string representation of the value of security characteristic of data of the dataflow node. We do not describe these functions in detail here, but they can be examined in the replication package [34]. An example of an output for the JPMail case is presented in listing 3.8. This output states an illegal flow from the *Parameter header* in the *sendMail* method of the class *MailSendingFacade* (fully qualified path) with the *SecurityLevel high* to the *Parameter header* in the *dispatchMail* method of the class *POP3* (fully qualified path) with the *SecurityLevel low*.

```

1 edu.kit.kastel.sdq.coupling.casestudy.jpmail.components.MailSendingFacade
   :: sendMail.header : EMailHeader , high )
2 ->
3 (edu.kit.kastel.sdq.coupling.casestudy.jpmail.components.POP3 ::
   dispatchMail.header : EMailHeader , low )

```

Listing 3.8: Example of the CodeQL-Ext for found flow violating the given policy in JPMail

3.6.1.2 Metamodel for CodeQL

For the usage of correspondence models in our evaluation and to facilitate replicability, we define metamodels for the input and output of our extended CodeQL.

Input Metamodel The metamodel of the input is depicted in Figure 3.1. It uses a Java metamodel, which contains, among others, the metaclasses *Classe*, *Field*, *Method*, and their *Parameter*. The CodeQL metamodel contains the metaclasses *TainttrackingRoot*, *Query*, *SecurityLevel*, *SecurityLevelAnnotation*, *Policy*, *AllowedFlows* and *AllowedFlow*. A *SecurityLevel* has a *name* to represent the value. The *SecurityLevelAnnotation* references a *SecurityLevel* to define the annotated value. *SecurityLevelAnnotation* has two subclasses, *FieldAnnotation* and *ParameterAnnotation* which use the *SecurityLevel* of its parent class and either define a *Field* or *Parameter* of the Java metamodel respectively which is annotated. An instance of *AllowedFlow* defines a single allowed flow relation between two *SecurityLevel* values (*from* and *to*). An instance of *AllowedFlows* contains one or more *AllowedFlow* elements. The metamodel itself is created starting from the *TainttrackingRoot*, which contains one or more

Figure 3.1: The input metamodel for CodeQL-Ext

Figure 3.2: The *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel for CodeQL-Ext

instances of *Query*. A *Query* contains an *AllowedFlow*, one or more values of *SecurityLevel* and the *SecurityLevelAnnotations*.

Output Metamodel The metamodel of the output is depicted in Figure 3.2 and is in alignment with the reference metamodel. We identify system elements with a superclass *SystemElement*. The subclasses *Parameter_SCAR* and *Field_SCAR* provide identification capabilities for their respective *System Elements* in the implementation. *Parameter_SCAR* contains the parameter name (*parameterName*), its type (*parameterType*), the method name (*methodName*) and the fully qualified class name (*fullyQualifiedClassName*). *Field_SCAR* contains the field name (*fieldName*), the type (*type*) and the fully qualified class name (*fullyQualifiedClassName*). *RuleId* contains an *id*, to identify the respective *Query* of CodeQL. A *ResultEntryElement* has a generic type of *SystemElement* and references a *SecurityLevel* (*SecurityLevel_SCAR*). The *Result* references two instances of *ResultEntryElement* captured called *source* and *sink*. Additionally, *Result* references a *RuleId*. The root of the model is captured by *SourceCodeAnalysisResult*, referencing one or more *Results*.

Resulting Values Metamodel Based on the previously described output metamodel of the extended CodeQL, we create the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* as depicted in Figure 3.3. This metamodel contains a root element *ResolvedImplementationValues*. This

Figure 3.3: The output metamodel for CodeQL-Ext

element contains one or more *ResolvedImplementationValue* elements. The *ResolvedImplementationValue* element references a *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues*, a *SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues* and a *RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue*. The *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* identifies a parameter by its name (*parameterName*), its type (*parameterType*), the method name (*methodName*) and the fully qualified class name (*fullyQualifiedClassName*). *SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues* enables identification of a *SecurityLevel* in the previously described input metamodel of CodeQL-Ext by its name. The *RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue* element contains a *id* and enables identification of the *Query* in the previously described input metamodel of the CodeQL-Ext.

3.6.2 Defining Eclipse Modeling Framework Metamodels for JOANA

In our evaluation [35], we use *JOANA* as information flow analysis. In contrast to CodeQL, we do not need to modify the analysis, its input or output. However, *JOANA* does not provide a Metamodel of the EMF, which is a prerequisite for the evaluation. We, therefore, create metamodels for the input and output of *JOANA*.

Input Metamodel For creating the *JOANA* input metamodel, we use a Java metamodel containing *Packages*, *Classes*, *Fields*, *Methods*, and *Parameters* to describe the Java source code. For a generalized identification of system elements in the *JOANA* model, we provide a super element *SystemElementIdentifying*. The elements *ParameterIdentifying*, *MethodIdentifying*, and *FieldIdentifying* reference the respective Java model elements. The *Level* element represents the security characteristics of data in *JOANA*. *Level* contains the attribute *name*

to represent the values. Information flow security in *JOANA* is analyzed by inspecting flows between *Sources* and *Sinks*. *Sources* and *Sinks* are attached to *Fields* or *Parameters* which are represented by the *ParameterIdentifying* or *FieldIdentifying* elements. The *Levels* are also annotated by the *Sources* and *Sinks*. We provide an abstract *InformationFlowAnnotation* metaclass to encapsulate this information. The metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* are subclasses of *InformationFlowAnnotation*. This is possible as the *Sources* and *Sinks* only differ by their additional semantic information. For the definition of unallowed flows, *JOANA* uses a *Lattice*. This *Lattice* comprises one or more *MayFlows*, defining that an information flow from data with the specified *Level* in *from* to data with the specified *Level* in *to* is allowed. *JOANA* performs its analysis based on *EntryPoint*s, which has to be selected for each analysis execution. The *EntryPoint* defines from which part the analysis builds a system dependence graph, on which the information flow analysis is internally performed. An *EntryPoint* has a unique *Tag*. In addition, an *EntryPoint* defines the available *Levels*. In addition, the analysis user has to define the used *Sources* and *Sinks* in an *EntryPoint*. In the *JOANA* annotation syntax, this is performed by the *Sources* and *Sinks* referencing the *Tag* of an *EntryPoint*. In alignment with the reference structure for modular metamodels of Heinrich et al. [20], we define the *EntryPoint* in our metamodel to reference the *Sources* and *Sinks*, i.e., the reference direction is inverted. However, we do not lose semantic information due to this inversion, as the information about which annotation is used in a configuration still exists. With this approach, we could, in principle, use a metamodel defining sources and sinks with characteristics and modularity to extend it with the configuration, i.e., the entry point to use it in *JOANA*. The metamodel element *JOANARoot* is used as the root of the model and contains all *EntryPoint*s.

Output Metamodel The output metamodel is recreated from the output provided by *JOANA* as far as possible and with correspondingly named metaclasses. The *EntryPoint_SCAR* contains a *Tag* to represent an *EntryPoint* in the input model. Analog to CodeQL described in Section 3.6.1, we identify the system elements *Parameter* and *Field*. We provide the metaclasses *Parameter_SCAR*, *Field_SCAR*, which are subclasses of the metaclass *SystemElement_SCAR*. The *Parameter_SCAR* identifies a parameter by the fully qualified class name *fullyQualifiedClassName*, the method name *methodName*, the parameter type *parameterType* and the index in the parameter list of the method *parameterIndex*. The *Field_SCAR* identifies the field by the fully qualified class name *fullyQualifiedClassName* and the field name *fieldName*. *Level_SCAR* contains a *name* and represents the *Levels* of *JOANA* independent of the input model.

The metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* references a *SystemElement_SCAR* and a *Level_SCAR*. The metaclass *Flow* references one *Source* and one *Sink*. The syntax of the output of *JOANA* does not entirely fit the reference metamodel for output metamodels. The representation of *EntryPoint* in the syntax of the *JOANA* output contains the illegal information flows while the *ResultEntry* references the *Configuration* in our reference metamodel. We invert this reference in our metamodel to establish conformance to the reference metamodel, i.e., the *Flow* references the *EntryPoint_SCAR*. This inversion neither reduces the expressibility nor changes the semantics, as the meaning is the same: the illegal information flows are

detected while analyzing the *EntryPoint*. Our parser for the output syntax of *JOANA* into a model of the metamodel also demonstrates that no information is lost.

Resolved Implementation Values Model Based on the previously described output metamodel of *JOANA*, we create the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*. This metamodel contains a root metaclass *ResolvedImplementationValues*. *ResolvedImplementationValues* references *ResolvedImplementationValue*. The *ResolvedImplementationValue* references a *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues*, a *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* and a *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues*. The *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* identifies a parameter by the fully qualified class name *fullyQualifiedClassName*, the method name *methodName*, the parameter type *parameterType* and the index in the parameter list of the method *parameterIndex*. *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* identifies a *Level* in the input (meta)model of *JOANA* by a *name*. The *EntryPointIdentification_ResultingValues* element contains a *Tag* and enables identification of the *EntryPoint* in the previously described input (meta)model of *JOANA*.

3.6.3 Extending the Architectural Dataflow Analysis

We extended the DFA of Seifermann [41] to enable its application in our case study. We call the extended DFA the Extended Dataflow Analysis (hereafter denoted with DFA-Ext) in the following. The extension contains a metamodel for annotating *Parameters* of the PCM [36] with *EnumCharacteristics*. For the description of the PCM, please refer to Reussner et al. [36]. We also provide a process for how the DFA-Ext can be applied reasonably in the development process regarding the annotation of *Parameters*. To realize this process, we define queries for the analysis tooling for the DFA of Boltz et al. [7] regarding our evaluation. For details about the current implementation and workings of the analysis tooling, please see Boltz et al. [7].

3.6.3.1 Metamodel for Annotation of Parameters

The metamodel for the annotation of parameters is represented in Figure 3.4. This metamodel is structured equally to the annotation models of the DFA tooling of Boltz et al. [7]. The purpose of this metamodel is to annotate *EnumCharacteristics* to *Parameters* in the PCM. *Parameters* in the PCM are located in *OperationSignatures* of *OperationInterfaces*.

Our metamodel, therefore, consists of the root element of *ParameterAnnotations* containing one or more *ParameterAnnotation*. *ParameterAnnotation* is a subclass of *CharacteristicsAnnotation*. *CharacteristicsAnnotation* references one or more *EnumCharacteristics* for their annotation. For the identification of parameters, we use the *GeneralOperationParameterIdentification* and the *ProvidedOperationParameterIdentification*. *ParameterAnnotation* references one *GeneralOperationParameterIdentification* to identify a parameter. Therefore, *Parameters* are identifiable by their objects when deserializing them but not due to some unique identifier in the metamodel as they are only defined by the parameter name. This unique

Figure 3.4: The metamodel for the DFA-Ext to annotate parameters

identification is only possible in conjunction with the containing *OperationSignature* as they have a unique identifier. The *GeneralOperationParameterIdentification* element, therefore, references an *OperationSignature* and a *Parameter* to ensure identification based on strings and objects. The semantic of an annotation with *GeneralOperationParameterIdentification* is that the annotated characteristics are expected for every component providing the respective *OperationSignature*. However, it may also be relevant that the characteristics are only relevant for specific components. For this purpose, we define the metaclass *ProvidedOperationParameterIdentification*, a subclass of *GeneralOperationParameterIdentification*. *ProvidedOperationParameterIdentification* adds a *OperationProvidedRole* to indicate that only the *Parameter* of the *OperationSignature* provided by the *RepositoryComponent* is annotated. Therefore, the *GeneralOperationParameterIdentification* could also be represented by multiple *ProvidedOperationParameterIdentification*.

3.6.3.2 Application of the Extended DataFlow Analysis in the Development of Systems

The DFA is used to detect whether data from an origin does not flow to other elements in the system with *Characteristics* that are not allowed based on a given policy. This is why the DFA annotates *Users*, *AssemblyContexts* and *Resource Containers* with *Characteristics*. An example of such a policy is that confidential data must not flow to components deployed on resources accessible by an attacker as described for JPMail [47, 41]. In our approach, the annotation of parameters implies that the contained data must have the *Characteristics* defined in the annotation. We have to account for the annotation of *Parameters* in this scenario and place them in relation to the other annotation capabilities.

We, therefore, propose the application of the DFA-Ext in the development of system design and analysis in alignment with the system development process from the PCM [36] as follows: The *Software Architect* defines the system's components and interfaces. These components are then created by the *Component Developer*, which also describes the behavior of each component. With these components and interfaces, the *Software Architect*

assembles the system. The *Security Expert* (see Seifermann [39]) defines the expected *Security Characteristic of Data in Parameters* in the *Interfaces*, either generalized for all occurrences of the *Parameter* in the *OperationSignature* or specialized for its occurrence in a providing *RepositoryComponent*. In addition, the *Security Expert* defines how values of the *Characteristics* are altered in an execution of a service (see Seifermann [39]). The *System Deployer* describes the available resources, and the *Security Expert* defines their characteristics. The *System Deployer* then describes the deployment of the components to the available resources. In this stage, the DFA-Ext can be performed, which checks whether the deployment is allowed based on the *Characteristics* of the resources and the parameters regarding a security policy specified by the *Security Expert*. If the DFA-Ext reports a vulnerability, i.e., a violation of the security policy, the system has to be changed by deploying on other resources or creating another architecture. If no vulnerability is reported, the *Domain Expert* specifies the interaction of the users with the system. When the user behavior is defined, the *Security Expert* defines the *Characteristics* of the input of the user into the system (see Seifermann [39]). After the user behavior and the *Characteristics* of the data provided by the user are defined, the DFA-Ext can be used to analyze the data flows in the system. In this scenario, the analysis verifies whether the characteristics of the data flowing to the parameters are allowed for the expected characteristics of the parameters based on the given policy. In addition, the analysis verifies whether the characteristics of the flowing data are allowed for the characteristics of the resources based on the given security policy.

3.6.3.3 Creating Queries for the Dataflow Analysis

Performing the analysis while considering our extension with *Parameters*, we must supply custom queries realizing the checks described in Section 3.6.3.2. This is possible in the current version of DFA tool of Boltz et al. [7], which is why we can perform the extension to the DFA-Ext. For every *ActionSequence*, we check three conditions:

1. Whether the characteristics of a parameter and those of the resources the components are deployed on are allowed regarding a given policy
2. Whether the characteristics of data flowing into a parameter are allowed regarding a given policy based on the characteristics annotated to the parameter
3. Whether the characteristics of data flowing into a parameter are allowed regarding a given policy based on the characteristics annotated to a resource container a component is deployed on.

The implementation resolves the relevant elements in each condition and verifies them as related to a given policy specifying the allowed conditions. The current version of the DFA as described by Boltz et al. [7] is designed as a framework, i.e., the analysis user can specify arbitrary characteristics and has to define the security policies themselves and integrate them in the tooling. We support the policy definition by providing a *AllowedConditionsProvider*, specifying a query for the previously mentioned checks which evaluates to *true*, i.e., the relation is allowed, or *false*.

3.6.3.4 Creating Characteristics and Security Policies for Case Study Analyses

For the case study to evaluate our coupling approach [35], we must define the characteristics and security policies for the DFA-Ext. We enable comparability to the Access Analysis [28], which is not extended in the case study by replicating the security policy provided by the integrated prolog rules. The Access Analysis determines whether an *Adversary* can access a location to which data is exposed which has assigned certain *DataSets*. The Access Analysis then reports a violation if and only if the *Adversary* is not allowed to see any *DataSet* that is assigned to the data. This relation between the *DataSets* allowed to be seen by the *Adversary* and those assigned to the data can be specified by a disjunctive policy as described for roles by Bell [6]. In disjunctive security policies, access privileges are described with a basic policy alphabet, such as roles in the CANUKUS Example of Bell [6]. In the CANUKUS example, a security policy involving the parties Canada (*CAN*), the United Kingdom (*UK*), and the United States of America (*US*) is described. This security policy uses roles conforming to the powerset of these basic roles. Therefore, the additional roles are *CANUK*, *CANUS*, *UKUS*, and *CANUKUS*. These roles semantically describe that the data is accessible by the parties whose basic roles are confined to the more complex roles. Based on these roles, the CANUKUS example illustrates the information flow policy where a dataflow may exist between information of roles *a* to roles *b*, if *a* comprises all roles of *b*. For the DFA-Ext, we created an *DisjunctiveAllowedConditionsProvider* realizing exactly such an information flow policy. This *AllowedConditionProvider* is used for the *TravelPlanner*. For any condition specified in Section 3.6.3.3 evaluates to true if an element in the check does not have any value of a *security characteristic* assigned. We define the conditions in Section 3.6.3.3 for this *AllowedConditionProvide* as follows:

1. Allocating a parameter on a resource container *allowed* if the values of a security characteristic assigned to the parameter contain any of the assigned values assigned to the resource container.
2. The flow from data to a parameter is *allowed* if the values are equal.
3. The flow from data to a resource is *allowed* if the values of a security characteristic from the flowing data contain any of the assigned values assigned to the resource container.

There are also other types of flow policies in literature, such as that confidential information is not allowed to flow to confidential data, as described by Mantel [30] and Denning [12], but also in the dataflow analysis of Tuma et al. [47]. In addition, for JPMail Tuma et al. [47] define the policy that confidential information is not allowed to flow to attack locations. Use the policy of Tuma et al. [47] to provide the *HighLowAttackerConditionProvider*. In general, we consider the labels *high*, *low*, and *attack* of *Characteristics* in this policy to replicate the policy of Tuma et al. We define the conditions in Section 3.6.3.3 for this *AllowedConditionProvide* as follows:

1. Allocating a parameter on a resource container is *not allowed* if the value and the value *attack* is assigned to the resource container.

2. The flow from data to a parameter is *allowed* if the values are equal.
3. The flow from data to a resource is *not allowed* if the flowing data has the assigned value *high* and the resource container has the assigned value *attack*.

This policy is applied in the evaluation with JPMail.

3.7 Security Specifications for the Architectural Analyses in the Case Study

We now present the specifications for the *Access Analysis* and *EDFA* for the case study systems *JPMail*, *TravelPlanner*, *CoCoMe* and *Eclipse Secure Storage*. Every model can be found in our replication package [34].

3.7.1 Specification for JPMail

The security specification of *JPMail* is realized for the Access Analysis and EDFA as follows.

Access Analysis In the Access Analysis, we represent three *Adversaries*: *Alice* and *Bob* sending and receiving the emails and an *Attacker* which intends to obtain the mail contents illegally. We model the confidentiality *Levels* by two *DataSets* *high* and *low*. We also define different *Locations* such as *AliceHome* or *BobHome* but also an *AttackZone* representing the *AttackZone* of Tuma et al. [47]. The *AttackZone* does not have any *TamperProtection* assigned and is accessible by the *Attacker*. *AliceHome* and *BobHome* is protected by *TamperProtections* so that the *Attacker* cannot access them. The *Parameters* *body* and *header* in the *OperationSignature* *sendMail* in the *OperationInterface* *MailSending* are annotated with the *DataSet* *high* through an *Information Flow* annotation. The *Parameters* *body* and *header* in the *OperationSignature* *dispatchMail* in the *OperationInterface* *EMailDispatchment* are annotated with the *DataSet* *low* through an *Information Flow* annotation, as they are expected to be encrypted or declassified respectively. This specification holds for the *Components* *SMTP*, *POP3* and *MailReceivingFacade* as they all provide the *OperationInterface* *EMailDispatchment*. With this model, the Access Analysis [28] does not report a vulnerability, as the *Attacker* can only access *OperationSignatures* on which *Parameters* with the *DataSet* *low* are allocated, i.e., *SMTP* and *POP3*.

Extended Dataflow Analysis We transfer this specification to the EDFA, similar to the representation by Seifermann [40]. We provide the *Enumerations* *Level* and *Trust*. *Level* provides the *Literals*, i.e., the values, *high* and *low* to represent the confidentiality *Levels* of Tuma et al. [47]. *Trust* provides the *Literals*, i.e., the values, *attack* and *trusted* to represent the *AttackZones* of Tuma et al. [47]. With these enums, we provide a *Characteristic DataClassification* based on the literals of *Level* and a *Characteristic NodeClearance* based on the literals

of *Trust*. *DataClassification* represents the confidentiality level of data and *NodeClearance* defines whether a node, i.e., a *Resource Container* in the PCM, is in an attack zone. In contrast to Seifermann [40], we model *Encryption* implicitly by elevating encrypted data from the *DataClassification* *low* to *high*. With these characteristics, we annotate the *ResourceContainers* *Alice* and *Bob* with the *NodeClearance* value *Trust* by the *ResourceAssignee* annotation. We annotate the *ResourceContainer* *Internet* with the *NodeClearance* *Attack*. We annotate the *Parameters* of the *OperationSignatures* similarly to the Access Analysis model. We perform a *GeneralOperationParameterIdentification* (c.f., Section 3.6.3) for the *Parameters*, i.e., the annotation holds for every *Component* providing the respective *OperationSignature*. We, therefore, annotate the *Parameter* *body* and *header* of the *sendMail* service with the value *high* from the *Characteristic DataClassification* through the *ParameterAnnotation* annotation. We annotate the *Parameter* *body* and *header* of the *dispatchMail* service with the value *low* from the *Characteristic DataClassification* through the *ParameterAnnotation* annotation. This annotation is applied to the *dispatchMail* service provided by *SMTP*, *POP3* and *Mail-ReceivingFacade*. We finally describe in the *SEFF* for the provided *OperationSignature* of the *MailSendingFacade* that the *DataClassification* of the *body* and *header* is changed from *high* to *low*. The *User* calls the *OperationSignature* *sendMail* and provides *body* and *header* with the *DataClassification* *high*. We explicitly used the *Trust* and *Level* characteristics to conform to Tuma et al. [47] and the evaluation of Seifermann et al. [41].

This specification and architectural model does not result in a vulnerability because:

1. only the *Components* *SMTP* and *POP3* are allocated of resources assigned with the value *Attack* of the *Characteristic NodeClearance* while providing only *Parameters* in the *dispatchMail* with the *DataClassification* *low*.
2. The *body* and *header* provided by the user are encrypted or respectively declassified by the *MailSendingFacade* i.e., they have the value *low*. Therefore, only *low* classified data reaches the *SMTP* and *POP3*, which are allocated on the *Attack* classified *Internet*.
3. The *body* and *header* provided by the user are encrypted or respectively declassified by the *MailSendingFacade*, i.e., they have the value *low*. This data flows to the *Parameters* *body* and *header* of *dispatchMail*, which are both annotated with the same value *low*.

3.7.2 Specification for TravelPlanner

The security specification of *TravelPlanner* is realized for the Access Analysis and EDFA as follows.

Access Analysis In the Access Analysis, we provide a correspondingly named *DataSet* for every basic role. Therefore, we provide four *DataSets*: *Airline*, *User*, *TravelAgency* and *Support*.

For the detection of vulnerabilities with the Access Analysis [28], we define four *Adversaries*: *User*, *Airline*, *TravelAgency*, and *AirlineSupport* to represent the participants in the system.

User represents the user and is, therefore, allowed to obtain information from the corresponding *DataSet User*. *Airline* represents airline employees, who are therefore allowed to obtain information from the *DataSet Airline*. *TravelAgency* represents travel agency employees, who therefore obtain information from the *DataSet Airline*. *AirlineSupport* represents support employees, who therefore obtain information from the *DataSet Support*.

We locate the *SmartPhone* in the *Location UserControlled*, *CoffeeShop* and *Street* where no other *Adversary* in the scenario has access to. We locate the *AirlineServer* in the *Location Airline*. The *AgencyServer* is specified to be in the *Location TravelAgency*. The *Resource-Container SupportCenter* is located in the correspondingly named *Location SupportCenter*. Finally, the *FlightStorageServer* is defined to be in the *Location FlightStorageServerFarm*.

The *Adversary User* can enter the *Locations UserControlled*, *CoffeeShop* and *Street*. The *Adversary Airline* can enter the *Location Airline*. The *Adversary TravelAgency* can enter the *Location TravelAgency*. The *Adversary AirlineSupport* can enter the *Location SupportCenter*. No adversary can enter the *Location FlightStorageServerFarm*.

We provide *InformationFlow* stereotypes annotating the *Parameters* of the *OperationSignatures* with the *DataSets* to realize the specification described in Section 3.3.2. If multiple roles are assigned to a parameter, this is represented by annotating multiple *DataSets*. An example of an *Information Flow* annotation is the annotation of the *Parameter* entry in the *OperationSignature* log of the interface *AirlineLogging* with the *DataSets* *Airline* and *Support*. Another example is the annotation of the *Parameter* *ccd_decl* of the *Method* *bookFlightOffer* in the *Interface* *AirlineBooking* with the *DataSets* *Airline* and *User*.

Extended Dataflow Analysis In the EDFA, we create an *Enumeration Roles* and define the *EnumCharacteristicType AssignedRoles* using it. This *Roles* contains *Literals* named corresponding to the roles described in Section 3.3.2: *User*, *Airline*, *TravelAgency*, and *Support*.

We *AssignedRoles* for annotating the *ResourceContainers* with *ResourceAssignees* and *Parameters* with *ParameterAnnotations*. We provide *ParameterAnnotations* as described before. We annotate the *ResourceContainers* to represent the constellations of the Access Analysis [28]. We annotate the *MobilePhone* with the *Literal User*, the *SupportCenter* with the *Literal Support*. The *FlightStorageServer* is not annotated with any *Literal* to replicate the Access Analysis so that no adversary can access the *ResourceContainer*. The *AirlineServer* is annotated with the *Literal Airline* and the *AgencyServer* with the *Literal TravelAgency*.

We provide *ParameterAnnotations* to annotate the roles described in Section 3.3.2 to the parameters, similar to the Access Analysis. An example of an *ParameterAnnotation* is the annotation of the *Parameter* entry in the *OperationSignature* log of the interface *AirlineLogging* with the *Literals* *Airline* and *Support*. Another example is the annotation of the *Parameter* *ccd_decl* of the *Method* *bookFlightOffer* in the *Interface* *AirlineBooking* with the *Literals* *Airline* and *User*.

3.7.3 Specification for Eclipse Secure Storage

The security specification of Eclipse Secure Storage described in Section 3.4 is realized for the EDFA and Access Analysis as follows

Access Analysis In the Access Analysis, we represent two Adversaries: *User* and *Attacker*. Analog to JPMail, we provide two *DataSets*: *high* and *low*. The *User* may know *high* and *low*. The *Attacker* may only know *low*. We provide three *Locations*: *Trusted*, *Attack*, *Network*. The *Resource Container UserPC* is assigned the *Location trusted*, the *Resource Container DataBase* is assigned the *Location attack* and the *Linking Resource Network* is assigned the *Location Network*. The *User* can access the *Location Trusted*, while the *Attacker* can access the *Location DataBase*. None of them can access the *Location Network*.

We created *ParameterAndDataPairs* for every parameter in the *OperationInterfaces* and assigned them by using the *Information Flow* stereotype. The *ParametersAndDataPair* assigned to the *Parameter challengeResponse* in the *OperationSignature setupRecovery* of the *OperationInterface IPasswordManagement* comprises the *DataSet high*. In contrast, all other *ParametersAndDataPairs* assigned to all other *Parameters* in the system comprise the *DataSet low*.

With this model, the Access Analysis does not report a vulnerability because the *Attacker* can only access the *DataBase* which contains the *SecurityPreferences* component. For every *OperationProvidedRole* all *Parameters* in the respective *OperationInterfaces* are annotated with the *DataSet low*.

Extended Dataflow Analysis In the EDFA, we provide the *Enumerations Level* and *Trust*. *Level* provides the *Literals*, i.e., the values, *high* and *low* to represent the confidentiality *Levels* as described by Tuma et al. [48]. For modeling the *Attacker*, *Trust* comprises the *Literals*, i.e., the values, *attack* and *trusted*. With these enums, we provide a *EnumCharacteristicType DataClassification* based on the literals of *Level* and a *Characteristic NodeClearance* based on the literals of *Trust*. *DataClassification* represents the confidentiality level of data and *NodeClearance* defines whether a node, i.e., a *Resource Container* in the PCM, can be accessed by an attacker.

With these characteristics, we create two *ResourceAssignees*: The first *ResourceAssignee* specifies the value *attack* from the *EnumCharacteristicType NodeClearance* to the *Resource-Container DataBase*. The second *ResourceAssignee* specifies the value *trusted* from the *EnumCharacteristicType NodeClearance* to the *ResourceContainer UserPC*. We also specify a *UsageAssignee* specifying the value *high* from the *EnumCharacteristicType DataClassification* for the input of the user for the *Parameter challengeResponse* in the called service *setupRecovery*.

We specified 55 *ParameterAnnotations*. One annotation specifies the value *high* from the *EnumCharacteristicType DataClassification* for the *Parameter challengeResponse* in the *OperationSignature setupRecovery* of the *OperationInterface IPasswordManagement*. All other *ParameterAnnotations* specify the value *low* of the *EnumCharacteristicType DataClassification* for all other *Parameters* in the system.

Without our adapted desing described in Section 3.4.3, the EDFA reported a vulnerbability because the *Questions* are derived from the *challengeResponse* has been assigned the value *high* which contradicts the annotated value *low* of the *Parameter value* of the *OperationSignature put*. After we adapted the design, the EDFA reports no vulnerability because now, the value of the *Questions* are lowered to the value *low* due to the encryption. This value and the value *low* of the *Parameter value* in the *OperationSignature internalPut* are equal.

3.7.4 Specification for CoCoMe

The security specification of *CoCoMe* is realized for the Access Analysis and EDFA in alignment with Greiner and Herda [18] as follows. As only certain parts of *CoCoMe* are relevant for evaluation, we describe only the corresponding specifications. However, we performed the whole specification, which can be found in our replication package [34].

Access Analysis In *CoCoMe* we specify six *DataSets* for every correspondingly named basic role: *Cashier*, *ByStander*, *Customer*, *StoreManager*, *Bank* and *OtherStore*. As also mentioned by Greiner and Herda [17] for every basic role, we design an *Adversary*, i.e., *Customer*, *Cashier*, *Bank*, *ByStander*, *StoreManager* and *OtherStore* which may know the respective *DataSet*.

As mentioned in Section 3.5, only a part of the system is relevant for our evaluation in our corresponding article [35]. Consequently, we will only further describe the parts that are relevant for this evaluation but provide the complete model in our replication package [34]. This includes the *DataSets* and correspondingly named *Adversaries* *Cashier*, *ByStander*, *Customer* and *Bank*.

For modeling the access of *Adversaries* to *Resource Containers*, we describe amongst others the *Locations*, *CashDesk*, *Bank*, *Queue*, *CardReader* and *CashDeskInternal*.

We perform the following assignments of *Resource Containers* to *Locations*:

- *ResourceContainer CashDeskPC* to *Location CashDesk*
- *ResourceContainer CardReader* to *Location CardReader*
- *ResourceContainer BankServer* to *Location Bank*
- *ResourceContainer OutputDevice* to *Location Queue*
- *ResourceContainer CashDeskInternals* to *Location CashDeskInternal*

Please note that the *OutputDevice* is assigned to the *Location Queue* because potentially multiple adversaries can obtain information about it, for instance, by looking at the receipt.

With these locations, we can now define the access to *Locations* by *Adversaries*. The *Adversary ByStander* can access the *Location Queue* as a person who wants to buy items or intentionally wants to observe information from other customers. The *Adversary Customer* can access the *Locations Queue* and *CardReader* to buy items and pay by card. The *Adversary Bank* can access the *Location Bank*. The *Adversary Cashier* can access the *CashDesk* and

Queue to verify the information from the *ResourceContainer OutputDevice*. No one can access the *Location CashDeskInternal* to avoid viewing the confidential data used for the bank transfer.

With the *DataSets*, we create a *ParametersAndDataPair* for every relevant *Parameter* for our evaluation and annotate them accordingly with the *InformationFlow* annotation. Here, we follow the description of Greiner and Herde [18]. However, we perform adjustments already described in Section 3.5 to avoid an initial architectural model for which vulnerabilities are reported.

The *Parameters pin* and *number* in the *OperationSignatures readPIN* and *readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface CardReaderOutIf* are annotated with the *DataSets Customer* and *Bank*. This is especially relevant as the *number* contains the *full* number of the payment card. The *Parameters cardnumber* and the *account* in the *OperationSignature requestTransaction* in the *OperationInterface BankTransactionIf* are annotated with the *DataSets Bank* and *Customer*. The *amount* in this *OperationSignature* is annotated with the *DataSets Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager*. The *Parameters id* and *amount* in the *OperationSignature registerSale* of the *OperationInterface BillingInteraction* are annotated with the *DataSets Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager*. As we omit the declassified version of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface CardReaderIf* (see Section 3.5, we now annotate the *Parameter number* with the *DataSets Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager*. This shows that the *Component CashDesk* only handles the shopping process and provides the shopping-related information, while the *Component Billing* handles the confidential information. Equally, we annotate the *Parameter cardNumber* in the *OperationSignature printPaymentCard* of the *OperationInterface PrinterOutIf* with the *DataSets Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager*.

Extended Dataflow Analysis *CoCoMe* is similar to the *TravelPlanner* by using roles to describe the security characteristic of data. We facilitate this similarity by also using an *Enumeration Roles* and define the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles* using it. This *Roles* contains *Literals* named corresponding to the roles described in Section 3.5.2: *Customer, Cashier, Bank, ByStander, StoreManager* and *OtherStore*.

As the EDFA does not have explicit *Locations*, we perform the specification of *ResourceContainers* similar to the *TravelPlanner*, by annotating the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles* with *ResourceAssignees* to describe which role can access a *ResourceContainer*. Consequently, we provide seven *ResourceAssignees*. The first *ResourceAssignee* specifies the *Literal Cashier* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles* to the *ResourceContainer CashDeskPC*. The second *ResourceAssignee* specifies the *Literal Bank* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles* to the *ResourceContainer BankServer*. The third *ResourceAssignee* specifies the *Literal Customer* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles* to the *ResourceContainer CardReader*. The fourth *ResourceAssignee* specifies the *Literals ByStander* and *Customer* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles* to the *ResourceContainer OutputDevice*. We omit the description of the remaining *ResourceAssignees* as they are not of relevance in our evaluation. Still, they are provided in our replication package [34].

Similarly, we define several *UsageAssignees* to annotate the *UsageScenarios* with the corresponding roles. For example, we annotate the *UsageScenario UserStartPayment* with the *Literal Customer* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*. In the *UsageScenarios*, we also provide *VariableCharacterisations* to specify the roles that are allowed to see the content of the user input. For example, we specify the *pin* or the *number* when calling the services *readPIN* or *readCardNumber* to contain information allowed to be seen by the customer or the bank by specifying the *Literals Customer* and *Bank* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*.

Equally to the *InformationFlow* annotations of the *AccessAnalysis*, we also specify *Parameter-Annotations* for the EDFA. We created 70 *ParameterAnnotations* to represent the specification of Greiner and Herda [18] and our extension. We will, again, only provide the relevant *ParameterAnnotations*, while all of them can be found in the replication package [34].

The *Parameters pin* and *number* in the *OperationSignatures readPIN* and *readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface CardReaderOutIf* are annotated with the *Literals Customer* and *Bank* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*. Again, this is especially relevant as the *number* contains the *full* number of the payment card. The *Parameters cardnumber* and the *account* in the *OperationSignature requestTransaction* in the *OperationInterface BankTransactionIf* are annotated with the *Literals Bank* and *Customer* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*. The *amount* in this *OperationSignature* is annotated with the *Literals Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*. The *Parameters id* and *amount* in the *OperationSignature registerSale* of the *OperationInterface BillingInteraction* are annotated with the *Literals Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*. As already described before, because we omit the declassified version of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface CardReaderIf* (see Section 3.5, we now annotate the *Parameter number* with the *Literals Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*. This again shows that the *Component CashDesk* only handles the shopping process and provides the shopping-related information, while the *Component Billing* handles the confidential information. Equally, we annotate the *Parameter cardNumber* in the *OperationSignature printPaymentCard* of the *OperationInterface PrinterOutIf* with the *Literals Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager* from the *EnumCharacteristicType Roles*.

3.8 Engineering the Implementation Value Resolution for the Evaluation

In our evaluation, we address two different types of security characteristic of data and their resulting lattices:

1. The first type of security characteristic of data represents *Confidentiality Levels* with the values *high* and *low*, forming a strictly ordered lattice.

Figure 3.5: Examples of applied classes of case study information flow lattices for (1) TravelPlanner (reduced set of values) and (2) JPMail.

2. The second type of security characteristic of data represents *Roles* with a *disjunctive lattice* (please see our Paper [35]). The values for these roles are specific for the designed systems.

Examples for the lattices are shown in Figure 3.5.

One part of designing the coupling is to create the *Implementation Value Resolution*. We now discuss the engineering of the *Implementation Value Resolution* for both *ConfidentialityLevels* and *Roles*.

3.8.1 Implementation Value Resolution: Confidentiality Levels

In the *Implementation Value Resolution* for confidentiality levels, we exploit the strict order of the values in the lattice. Therefore, we calculate the value representing the highest confidentiality in the lattice from all information flows flowing to a single sink. In the case of a strictly ordered lattice with the levels *high*, *medium* and *low*, the lattice described would provide that *medium* data may flow to *high* data and *low* data may flow to *high* data. Consequently, every flow violating this lattice results in a vulnerability. Based on this lattice, if we have two flows: one from data specified with *high* and one specified with *medium* to data specified with *low*, the value *high* would result. The rationale behind this is that when the value *medium* violates the security policy, so will the one with the value *high*.

In our evaluation, we only consider two values *high* and *low*. In these scenarios, a vulnerability is reported by the source code analysis as soon as a flow from a source system element specified with the value *high* to a sink system element specified with the value *low* is detected. Consequently, in our evaluation, we select the value *high* for the sink system element, which was previously specified with the value *low*, as soon as a flow from a source system element specified with the value *high* is detected.

3.8.2 Implementation Value Resolution: Roles

For roles in the evaluation of our paper [35], we only consider *disjunctive powerset lattices* as shown in Figure 3.5. In this context, a powerset lattice comprises the superset combinations

of the basic roles. Our example in Figure 3.5 shows a powerset lattice of all basic roles of TravelPlanner.

```
1  protected boolean isResultEntryValidWRTAccessAnalysis(Flow resultEntry)
   {
2  Collection<String> sourceBasicLevels = ResultingValuesModelHandlingUtil
   .splitLevelNameIntoBasicLevels(resultEntry.getSource().
   getSourceLevel().getName(), SUBLEVEL_DELIMITER);
3  Collection<String> sinkBasicLevels = ResultingValuesModelHandlingUtil
   .splitLevelNameIntoBasicLevels(resultEntry.getSink().getSinkLevel().
   getName(), SUBLEVEL_DELIMITER);
4
5  return !(sourceBasicLevels.size() >= sinkBasicLevels.size()
6  && CollectionUtil.containsAny(sourceBasicLevels, sinkBasicLevels));
7  }
```

Listing 3.9: Example condition to decide whether a flow is valid to considered in the Implementation Value Resolution

As shown in Listing Listing 3.9, we only consider information flows (1) where the number of basic values in the sink is larger than that of the source and (2) the source levels do not contain any of the basic values of the sink. If any of these conditions hold (note the negated AND (&)), the reported flow will not be considered.

The reason behind this is the following: Condition (1) exists only to consider information flows with a lower number of basic values. We establish this condition to avoid considering confidentiality levels from the source that are lower than those of the sinks. In a disjunctive lattice, the confidentiality level decreases with more assigned basic values because an adversary only requires *one* basic value to have access to the information. Condition (2) only considers information flows from sources that do not comprise any of the basic levels of the sinks. The sinks are annotated so that an adversary is allowed to access the data if he/she has any of the basic roles assigned. In the CANUKUS example [6], an adversary with the role *CAN* may access all data in a program part that is assigned with any combination of basic values comprising *CAN*. If we were to combine information flows from sources with the values comprising *CAN*, we would not detect any violation, the expected value would always be comprised. Thus, if we then comprise the values from all sources that do not comprise *CAN*, we see whether a new vulnerability would arise in the architectural analysis.

Please note that this heuristic approach may not capture all cases. Thus, in a master's thesis [29], we researched the cases where problems can arise in *conjunctive lattices* due to the application of a heuristic and how we can address these problems with extensions of our black-box coupling approach.

4 Supplementary Information: Reference Metamodels and Integration Conditions

Our evaluation of coverage for reference metamodels and ICs is supported by formalizations. We provide a formalization of the conformance definition between metamodels of analyses and our reference metamodels in Section 4.1. In Section 4.2 we provide a formalization of the reference metamodels. Finally, in Section 4.3 we refine our ICs w.r.t. the definitions provided in our article [35]. Due to space limitations, we could only provide the ICs on the metamodel level and correspondences in a correspondence condition or constraints in a constraint condition where possible. Therefore, we refine the definitions provided in our article [35] by (1) separating ICs where appropriate and (2) provide the conditions on the metamodel and model level. In addition, we provide the formalization of all conditions and their refinements also in Section 4.3.

4.1 Reference Metamodel Conformance

In this section, we formalize the definition of conformance between metaclasses of input and output metamodels of the analysis with the reference metamodels provided in our article [35]. As described in our article [35], we comprehend the reference metamodels as underspecified, i.e., the specific metamodels of the analyses can comprise metaclasses and references not captured in the reference metamodels. Consequently, we define a metamodel to conform to the respective reference metamodel, if for every metaclass in the reference metamodel, a conforming metaclass in the respective metamodel of an analysis exists. In our article [35], we define the conformance of a metaclass in the input or output metamodel of an analysis to a metaclass of our reference metamodel as follows:

A metaclass $m \in M$ in the input or output metamodel of an analysis conforms to a metaclass $r \in R$ in the reference metamodel if a valid transformation can be defined. We define the transformation to be valid if

- The metaclass m fits the semantics of the metaclass of the reference metamodel r .
- For every reference of the metaclass in the reference metamodel r to another metaclass $r' \in R$, the metaclass m must provide a (possibly transitive) reference to another metaclass $m' \in M$ conforming to r' . We define a reference as transitive if metaclass m' is reachable through a sequence of references starting from m .

We describe this conformance definition in the following, where $SM: Syn \rightarrow Sem$ describes a semantic mapping from the syntactic domain Syn to the semantic domain Sem :

$$conf(r, R, m, M) = \begin{cases} true, & SM(r) = SM(m) \wedge \\ & \forall \langle r, r' \rangle \in R: \exists \langle m, m' \rangle \in M: \\ & conf(r', R, m', M) \\ false, & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

Similar conformance definitions can be found in related work. In the following we detail the examples provided in our article [35]. Bucaioni et al. [9] determine the *conformance* between specific components of a specific architecture and an abstract component of a reference architecture. Here, a specific component fully conforms to a mapped abstract component if all mappings of its specific connectors to the abstract connectors of the corresponding abstract component are legal. The mapped abstract and specific components are analog to metaclasses in the metamodels of the analyses and the abstract components to the metaclasses in our reference metamodels. Also, the connectors of the components in the architectures are analog to the references of metaclasses in our metamodels. Seifermann et al. [41] determines the *conformance* between two models of the same metamodel. Here, a model element in one model conforms to model elements in the other model if they can be reasonably mapped (e.g., by their name) and, among others, both have references to reasonably mapped model elements. Konersmann et al. [26] define *conformance* similar to Seifermann et al. [41] between reference models and specific models created with the same metamodel.

Reference Metamodels Sets	
Δ	System Elements
S	Security Characteristics
An	Annotations
CFG	Configurations
Pol	Security Policies
RE	Result Entries
REE	Result Entry Elements
RIV	ResolvedImplementationValues
$A = \Delta_A \cup S_A \cup An_A \cup CFG_A \cup Pol_A$	<i>Annotated Architectural Model</i>
$C = \Delta_C \cup S_C \cup An_C \cup CFG_C \cup Pol_C$	<i>Annotated Source Code</i>
$R = \Delta_R \cup S_R \cup RE \cup REE$	<i>Source Code Analysis Result</i>
$V = \Delta_V \cup S_V \cup CFG_V \cup RIV$	<i>Resolved Implementation Values Model</i>
$\Lambda = \{A, C\}$	Reference Metamodel for Input Metamodels
$\Upsilon = \{A, C, R, V\}$	Reference Metamodels
(Meta-)model elements	
$\delta \in \Delta$	System Element
$\alpha \in An$	Annotation
$s \in S$	Security Characteristic
$cfg \in CFG$	Configuration
$pol \in Pol$	Security Policy
$r \in RE$	Result Entry
$ree \in REE$	Result Entry Element
$riv \in RIV$	Resolved Implementation Value

Table 4.1: Sets and Elements in the Reference Structure

4.2 Formalization of Reference Metamodel

In this section, we formalize our reference metamodels for describing the ICs. The meta-classes and sets we allocate them in are presented in Table 4.1. The set Δ comprises the *System Elements* $\delta \in \Delta$. The set S comprises the *Security Characteristics* $s \in S$. The set An comprises the *Annotations* $\alpha \in An$. The set CFG comprises the *Configurations* $cfg \in CFG$. The set Pol comprises the *Security Policies* $pol \in Pol$. The set RE comprises the *Result Entries* $re \in RE$ and the set REE all *Result Entry Elements* ree . The set RIV comprises the *Resolved Implementation Values*.

We denote the *Annotated Architectural Model* with A , the *Annotated Source Code* with C , the *Source Code Analysis Result* with R and the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* with V . We assign the sets and their elements by a subscript of the respective input or output metamodel. Δ , S , An , CFG and Pol are used to describe the *Annotated Architectural Model* and the *Annotated Source Code*. Therefore, the set of meta-classes for, e.g., *System Elements* for the *Annotated Architectural Model*, is denoted with Δ_A and those for the *Annotated Source Code* with Δ_C . The meta-classes of these sets are denoted with δ_A or δ_C , respectively. Δ , S , CFG , RE and REE are used to describe the *Source Code Analysis Result*. Therefore, the set of

System Elements in the *Source Code Analysis Result* is denoted with Δ_R and its metaclasses with δ_R . Δ , S , CFG and RIV are used to describe the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*. Therefore, the set of *System Elements* in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* is denoted with Δ_V and its metaclasses with δ_V . The metamodels for the *Annotated Architectural Model*, *Annotated Source Code*, *Source Code Analysis Result* and *Resolved Implementation Values Model* are described by the union of the respective sets. We capture the *Annotated Architectural Model A* and the *Annotated Source Code C* in the set $\Lambda = A, C$ to denote metaclasses that exist in the input metamodel of the reference metamodels. We use the set $\Upsilon = A, C, R, V$ to denote metaclasses that exist in all reference metamodels. In the remainder of this report, we also denote the metaclasses in the specific input and output (metamodels) of the analyses with these sets if they conform to the respective metaclasses in the reference metamodels.

We denote *System Elements* with $\delta_Y \in \Delta_Y$ and *Security Characteristics* with $s_Y \in S_Y$. *Annotations* $\alpha_\Lambda \in An_\Lambda$ are allocated in the set of annotations An_Λ and are defined by referencing one *System Element* $\delta_\Lambda \in \Delta_\Lambda$ and at least one *Security Characteristic* $s_\Lambda \in S_\Lambda$. In addition, *Annotations* are referenced by *Configurations* $cfg_\Lambda \in CFG_\Lambda$. We these relations in Equation (4.2)

$$\forall \alpha_\Lambda \in An_\Lambda: \exists \delta_\Lambda \in \Delta_\Lambda, \exists s_\Lambda \in S_\Lambda, \exists cfg_\Lambda \in CFG_\Lambda: \langle \alpha_\Lambda, \delta_\Lambda \rangle \wedge \langle \alpha_\Lambda, s_\Lambda \rangle \wedge \langle cfg_\Lambda, \alpha_\Lambda \rangle \quad (4.2)$$

For brevity, we also express an annotation as a triple $\alpha_\Lambda(\delta_\Lambda, s_\Lambda, cfg_\Lambda)$ with and the relations described in eq. (4.2).

We specify a configuration $cfg_\Lambda \in CFG_\Lambda$ in the input metamodels as a metaclass providing information for a specific analysis run. This information includes arbitrary information such as numbers the analysis is run (see Heinrich et al. [20]) but also *Security Characteristics* $s_\Lambda \in S_\Lambda$, *Annotations* $\alpha_\Lambda \in An_\Lambda$, *System Elements* $\delta_\Lambda \in \Delta_\Lambda$ and a *Security Policy* $pol \in Pol$ used in the execution of the analysis as formalized in Equation (4.3).

$$cfg_\Lambda \in CFG_\Lambda: \exists \alpha_\Lambda \in An_\Lambda, \exists s_\Lambda \in S_\Lambda, \exists \delta_\Lambda \in \Delta_\Lambda, \exists ! pol_\Lambda \in Pol_\Lambda: \langle cfg_\Lambda, s_\Lambda \rangle \wedge \langle cfg_\Lambda, \delta_\Lambda \rangle \wedge \langle cfg_\Lambda, \alpha_\Lambda \rangle, \langle cfg_\Lambda, pol_\Lambda \rangle \quad (4.3)$$

The *Configuration* in the *Source Code Analysis Result R* and *Resolved Implementation Values Model V*, represents an identification of the one in the *Annotated Architectural Model A* and *Annotated Source Code C*. Therefore, we do not need the relations described in Equation (4.3) in the *Configuration* in the *Source Code Analysis Result R* and *Resolved Implementation Values Model V*.

We denote the *Source Code Analysis Result R* of a source code analysis consisting of *Result Entries* to specify counter-examples that violate the specifications. *Result Entries* are denoted by r . A *Result Entry* $r \in RE$ provides the counter-examples with *Result Entry Elements* $ree \in REE$ and a configuration $cfg \in CFG$ as shown by eq. (4.4).

$$\forall r \in R: \exists ree \in REE, \exists cfg_R \in CFG_R: \langle r, ree \rangle \wedge \langle r, cfg_R \rangle \quad (4.4)$$

Each *ree* references a *System Element* $\delta_R \in \Delta_R$ and one *Security Characteristic* $s_R \in S_R$ as shown in eq. (4.5).

$$\forall ree_R \in REE: \exists \delta_R \in \Delta_R, \exists s_R \in S_R: \langle ree, \delta_R \rangle \wedge \langle ree, s_R \rangle \quad (4.5)$$

We represent the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* as a set of *riv* $\in RIV$ representing the values of a *Security Characteristic* resulting from the implementation for a *System Element* calculated in a given *Configuration*. Therefore, a *riv* references a *Security Characteristic* $s_V \in S_V$, a *System Element* $\delta_V \in \Delta_V$ and a *Configuration* $cfg_V \in CFG_V$ as presented in Equation (4.6).

$$\forall riv \in RIV: \exists s_V \in S_V, \exists \delta_V \in \Delta_V, \exists cfg_V \in CFG_V: \langle riv, s_V \rangle \wedge \langle riv, \delta_V \rangle \wedge \langle riv, cfg_V \rangle \quad (4.6)$$

4.3 Formalization and Refinement of the Integration Conditions

In this section, we formalize the ICs in our coupling approach [35]. We will again present the IC and include the formalization. The relevance of the ICs is discussed in our coupling approach [35]. While we define the ICs in the paper about our coupling approach [35] only on the metamodel level for brevity, we will formulate them in this report also on the instance level. Aside from marking the ICs as *correspondence condition* (T) or *constraint condition* (R), we will also denote whether the IC is formulated on the metamodel level (M) or instance level (I) for improve the differentiation.

We denote all instances of metaclasses in a set of metaclasses Y with \underline{Y} .

4.3.1 Integration Conditions of the *Analyses Input Model Consistency*

For our formalization, we have to make the following assumptions: The instances of the metaclass describing the security characteristic of data in the coupling scenario s_A^{cs} is captured in the set S_A^{cs} . Let now be all values of $\underline{s_A^{cs}}$ of the metaclass s_A^{cs} be located in the set $\underline{S_A^{cs}}$. For our coupling approach to work, we also have to assume that the architectural analysis uses at least one annotation $\alpha_A^{cs} \in An_A^{cs} \subset An_A$ that annotates the security characteristic of data s_A^{cs} in the coupling scenario to system elements:

$$\begin{aligned} & (An_A^{cs} \neq \emptyset) \\ & \text{where} \\ & An_A^{cs} = \{\alpha_A \in An_A \mid \exists s_A \in S_A : \langle \alpha_A, s_A \rangle \wedge s_A = s_A^{cs}\} \end{aligned}$$

With this assumption, we can formulate the remaining ICs.

We now formulate **IC1** on the metamodel (M) and instance (model) level (I) as follows:

IC1(T)(M): A *Security Characteristic* s_C must exist in the *Annotated Source Code C* corresponding to the *Security Characteristic* of the coupling scenario s_A^{cs} in the *Annotated Architectural Model A*.

$$\begin{aligned} & S_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset \\ & \text{where} \\ & S_C^{cs} = \{s_C \in S_C \mid s_C \leftrightarrow s_A^{cs}\} \end{aligned}$$

IC1(T)(I): A value \underline{s}_C of a *Security Characteristic* S_C in the *Annotated Source Code* C must exist, corresponding to an instance \underline{s}_A^{cs} to the *Security Characteristic* of the coupling scenario s_A^{cs} in the *Annotated Architectural Model* A .

$$\underline{S}_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{S}_C^{cs} = \{\underline{s}_C \in \underline{S}_C \mid \underline{s}_C \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_A^{cs}\}$$

In the following, we define **IC2** on the metamodel level and instance level (I) as follows. As **IC2** requires correspondences between δ_C and δ_A , correspondences between cfg_C and cfg_A or between the respective instances without any dependencies between the correspondences, we can also refine this correspondence condition to two separate correspondence conditions (**IC2.1** and **IC2.2**).

IC2(T)(M): There must exist

- *System Elements* δ_C of the *Annotated Source Code* C which correspond to *System Elements* δ_A of the *Annotated Architectural Model* A that are annotated with the *Security Characteristic* s_C^{cs} of the coupling scenario by at least one *Annotation* α_C and
- *Configurations* cfg_C of the *Annotated Source Code* C which correspond to *Configurations* cfg_A in the *Annotated Architectural Model* A that uses at least one *Annotation* α_C , annotating the *Security Characteristic* s_C^{cs} in the coupling scenario.

$$\Delta_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset \wedge CFG_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_C^{cs} = \{\delta_C \in \Delta_C \mid \exists \delta_A \in \Delta_A : \exists \alpha_A^{cs} \in An_A^{cs} : \langle \alpha_A^{cs}, \delta_A \rangle \wedge \delta_C \leftrightarrow \delta_A\}$$

$$CFG_C^{cs} = \{cfg_C \in CFG_C \mid \exists cfg_A \in CFG_A : \exists \alpha_A^{cs} \in An_A^{cs} : \langle cfg_A, \alpha_A^{cs} \rangle \wedge cfg_C \leftrightarrow cfg_A\}$$

IC2.1(T)(M): There must exist *System Elements* δ_C of the *Annotated Source Code* C which correspond to *System Elements* δ_A of the *Annotated Architectural Model* A that are annotated with the *Security Characteristic* s_C^{cs} of the coupling scenario by at least one *Annotation* α_C

$$\Delta_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_C^{cs} = \{\delta_C \in \Delta_C \mid \exists \delta_A \in \Delta_A : \exists \alpha_A^{cs} \in An_A^{cs} : \langle \alpha_A^{cs}, \delta_A \rangle \wedge \delta_C \leftrightarrow \delta_A\}$$

IC2.2(T)(M): There must exist *Configurations* cfg_C of the *Annotated Source Code* C which correspond to *Configurations* cfg_A in the *Annotated Architectural Model* A that uses at least one *Annotation* α_C , annotating the *Security Characteristic* s_C^{CS} in the coupling scenario.

$$CFG_C^{CS} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$CFG_C^{CS} = \{cfg_C \in CFG_C \mid \exists cfg_A \in CFG_A: \exists \alpha_A^{CS} \in An_A^{CS}: \langle cfg_A, \alpha_A^{CS} \rangle \wedge cfg_C \leftrightarrow cfg_A\}$$

IC2(T)(I): There must exist

- instances of *System Elements* δ_C of the *Annotated Source Code* C which correspond to instances of *System Elements* δ_A in a model of the *Annotated Architectural Model* A that are annotated with a value of the *Security Characteristic* s_A^{CS} of the coupling scenario by at least one *Annotation* α_A^{CS} and
- instances of *Configurations* cfg_C of the *Annotated Source Code* C and *Configurations* cfg_A in an instance of the *Annotated Architectural Model* A that uses at least one *Annotation* α_A^{CS} , annotating the *Security Characteristic* s_A^{CS} in the coupling scenario.

$$\Delta_C^{CS} \neq \emptyset) \wedge CFG_C^{CS} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_C^{CS} = \{\delta_C \in \Delta_C \mid \exists \delta_A \in \Delta_A: \exists \alpha_A^{CS} \in An_A^{CS}: \langle \alpha_A^{CS}, \delta_A \rangle \wedge \delta_C \leftrightarrow \delta_A\}$$

$$CFG_C^{CS} = \{cfg_C \in CFG_C \mid \exists cfg_A \in CFG_A: \exists \alpha_A^{CS} \in An_A^{CS}: \langle cfg_A, \alpha_A^{CS} \rangle \wedge cfg_C \leftrightarrow cfg_A\}$$

IC2.1(T)(I): There must exist instances of a *System Elements* δ_C which correspond to instances of *System Elements* δ_A in a model of the *Annotated Architectural Model* A that are annotated with a value of the *Security Characteristic* s_A^{CS} of the coupling scenario by at least one

Annotation α_A^{CS}

$$\Delta_C^{CS} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_C^{CS} = \{\delta_C \in \Delta_C \mid \exists \delta_A \in \Delta_A: \exists \alpha_A^{CS} \in An_A^{CS}: \langle \alpha_A^{CS}, \delta_A \rangle \wedge \delta_C \leftrightarrow \delta_A\}$$

IC2.2(T)(I): There must exist instances of *Configurations* \underline{cfg}_C of the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} and *Configurations* \underline{cfg}_A in an instance of the *Annotated Architectural Model* \underline{A} that uses at least one *Annotation* $\underline{\alpha}_A^{cs}$, annotating the *Security Characteristic* \underline{s}_A^{cs} in the coupling scenario.

$$\underline{CFG}_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{CFG}_C^{cs} = \{ \underline{cfg}_C \in \underline{CFG}_C \mid \exists \underline{cfg}_A \in \underline{CFG}_A : \exists \underline{\alpha}_A^{cs} \in \underline{An}_A^{cs} : \langle \underline{cfg}_A, \underline{\alpha}_A^{cs} \rangle \wedge \underline{cfg}_C \leftrightarrow \underline{cfg}_A \}$$

We define **IC3** on the metamodel and instance level as follows:

IC3(C)(M):

There must exist an *Annotation* α_C in the *Annotated Source Code* that annotates a *Security Characteristic* $s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs}$ affected by **IC1** to a *System Element* $\delta_C^{cs} \in \Delta_C^{cs}$ affected by **IC2** and is referenced by a *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ also captured in **IC2**.

$$An_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$An_C^{cs} = \{ \alpha_C \in An_C \mid \exists \delta_C^{cs} \in \Delta_C^{cs}, \exists s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs}, \exists \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} : \langle \alpha_C, \delta_C^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle \alpha_C, s_C^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{cfg}_C^{cs}, \alpha_C \rangle \}$$

IC3(C)(I):

There must exist an *Annotation* $\underline{\alpha}_C$ in the model of the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} that annotates a value of the *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$ affected by **IC1** to an instance of a *System Element* $\underline{\delta}_C^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_C^{cs}$ affected by **IC2** and that is referenced by a instance of a *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ also captured in **IC2**.

$$\underline{An}_C^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{An}_C^{cs} = \{ \underline{\alpha}_C \in \underline{An}_C \mid \exists \underline{\delta}_C^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_C^{cs}, \exists \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}, \exists \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} : \langle \underline{\alpha}_C, \underline{\delta}_C^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{\alpha}_C, \underline{s}_C^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{cfg}_C^{cs}, \underline{\alpha}_C \rangle \}$$

We define **IC4** on the metamodel and instance level as follows:

IC4(C)(M): *Security Policies* $pol_C \in Pol_C$ of the source code analysis must use the *Security Characteristics* $s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs}$ affected by **IC1** of their *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_C \in \underline{CFG}_C$.

$$\forall pol_C \in Pol_C : \forall \underline{cfg}_C \in \underline{CFG}_C, \forall s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs} : \langle \underline{cfg}_C, pol_C \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{cfg}_C, s_C^{cs} \rangle \Rightarrow \langle pol_C, s_C^{cs} \rangle$$

IC4(C)(I): Instances of *Security Policies* \underline{pol}_C in \underline{Pol}_C of the source code analysis must use the values of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$ affected by **IC1** of their *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_C \in \underline{CFG}_C$.

$$\forall \underline{pol}_C \in \underline{Pol}_C: \forall \underline{cfg}_C \in \underline{CFG}_C, \forall \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}: \langle \underline{cfg}_C, \underline{pol}_C \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{cfg}_C, \underline{s}_C^{cs} \rangle \Rightarrow \langle \underline{pol}_C, \underline{s}_C^{cs} \rangle$$

4.3.2 Integration Conditions of the Source Code Analysis

In the following, we define **IC5** on the metamodel level (M) and instance level (I). Similar to **IC2** we can split **IC5** into two ICs as the required correspondences do not have any relation (**IC5.1** and **IC5.2**).

IC5(T)(M): There must exist *Security Characteristics* $s_R \in S_R$ and *System Elements* $\delta_R \in \Delta_R$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result* R corresponding to *Security Characteristics* $s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs}$ and *System Elements* $\delta_C^{cs} \in \Delta_C^{cs}$ of the *Annotated Source Code* C that are affected by **IC1** and **IC2** respectively.

$$\Delta_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset \wedge S_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_R^{cs} = \{\delta_R \in \Delta_R \mid \exists \delta_C^{cs} \in \Delta_C^{cs}: \delta_R \leftrightarrow \delta_C^{cs}\}$$

$$S_R^{cs} = \{s_R \in S_R \mid \exists s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs}: s_R \leftrightarrow s_C^{cs}\}$$

IC5.1(T)(M): There must exist *System Elements* $\delta_R \in \Delta_R$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result* R corresponding to *System Elements* $\delta_C^{cs} \in \Delta_C^{cs}$ of the *Annotated Source Code* C that are affected by **IC2**.

$$\Delta_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_R^{cs} = \{\delta_R \in \Delta_R \mid \exists \delta_C^{cs} \in \Delta_C^{cs}: \delta_R \leftrightarrow \delta_C^{cs}\}$$

IC5.2(T)(M): There must exist *Security Characteristics* $s_R \in S_R$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result* R corresponding to *Security Characteristics* $s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs}$ of the *Annotated Source Code* C that are affected by **IC1**.

$$S_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$S_R^{cs} = \{s_R \in S_R \mid \exists s_C^{cs} \in S_C^{cs}: s_R \leftrightarrow s_C^{cs}\}$$

IC5(T)(I): There must exist instances of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_R \in \underline{S}_R$ and instances of *System Elements* $\underline{\delta}_R \in \underline{\Delta}_R$ in the model of the *Source Code Analysis Result* \underline{R} corresponding to instances of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$ and instances of *System Elements* $\underline{\delta}_C^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_C^{cs}$ of the model of the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} that are affected by **IC1** and **IC2** respectively.

$$\underline{\Delta}_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset \wedge \underline{S}_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{\Delta}_R^{cs} = \{\underline{\delta}_R \in \underline{\Delta}_R \mid \exists \underline{\delta}_C^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_C^{cs} : \underline{\delta}_R \leftrightarrow \underline{\delta}_C^{cs}\}$$

$$\underline{S}_R^{cs} = \{\underline{s}_R \in \underline{S}_R \mid \exists \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs} : \underline{s}_R \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_C^{cs}\}$$

IC5.1(T)(I): There must exist instances of *System Elements* $\underline{\delta}_R \in \underline{\Delta}_R$ in the model of the *Source Code Analysis Result* \underline{R} corresponding to instances of *System Elements* $\underline{\delta}_C^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_C^{cs}$ of the model of the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} that are affected by **IC2**.

$$\underline{\Delta}_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{\Delta}_R^{cs} = \{\underline{\delta}_R \in \underline{\Delta}_R \mid \exists \underline{\delta}_C^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_C^{cs} : \underline{\delta}_R \leftrightarrow \underline{\delta}_C^{cs}\}$$

IC5.2(T)(I): There must exist instances of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_R \in \underline{S}_R$ in the model of the *Source Code Analysis Result* \underline{R} corresponding to instances of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$ of the model of the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} that are affected by **IC1**.

$$\underline{S}_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{S}_R^{cs} = \{\underline{s}_R \in \underline{S}_R \mid \exists \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs} : \underline{s}_R \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_C^{cs}\}$$

We define **IC6** on the metamodel and instance level as follows:

IC6(C)(M): There must exist a *Result Entry Element* $\underline{ree} \in \underline{REE}$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result* \underline{R} containing a *System Element* $\underline{\delta}_R^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_R^{cs}$ and a *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_R^{cs} \in \underline{S}_R^{cs}$, both affected by **IC5**.

$$\exists \underline{ree} \in \underline{R} : \exists \underline{\delta}_R^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_R^{cs}, \underline{s}_R^{cs} \in \underline{S}_R^{cs} : \langle \underline{ree}, \underline{\delta}_R^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{ree}, \underline{s}_R^{cs} \rangle$$

IC6(C)(I): There must exist an instance of a *Result Entry Element* $\underline{ree} \in \underline{REE}$ in the model of the *Source Code Analysis Result* \underline{R} containing an instance of a *System Element* $\underline{\delta}_R^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_R^{cs}$ and a value of a *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_R^{cs} \in \underline{S}_R^{cs}$ that are affected by **IC5**.

$$\exists \underline{ree} \in \underline{R} : \exists \underline{\delta}_R^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_R^{cs}, \exists \underline{s}_R^{cs} \in \underline{S}_R^{cs} : \langle \underline{ree}, \underline{\delta}_R^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{ree}, \underline{s}_R^{cs} \rangle$$

Similar to **IC5**, we define **IC7** on the metamodel and instance level as follows:

IC7(T)(M): It must exist *Configurations* $cfg_R \in CFG_R$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result R* corresponding to *Configurations* $cfg_C^{cs} \in CFG_C^{cs}$ of the *Annotated Source Code C* affected by **IC2**.

$$CFG_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$CFG_R^{cs} = \{cfg_R \in CFG_R \mid \exists cfg_C^{cs} \in CFG_C^{cs} : cfg_R \leftrightarrow cfg_C^{cs}\}$$

IC7(T)(I): It must exist an instance of the *Configurations* $\underline{cfg}_R \in \underline{CFG}_R$ in the model of the *Source Code Analysis Result R* corresponding to instances of *Configurations* $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ in the model of the SAM \underline{C} affected by **IC2**.

$$\underline{CFG}_R^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{CFG}_R^{cs} = \{\underline{cfg}_R \in \underline{CFG}_R \mid \exists \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} : \underline{cfg}_R \leftrightarrow \underline{cfg}_C^{cs}\}$$

4.3.3 Integration Conditions of the *Implementation Value Integration*

In the following, we define **IC8** on the metamodel and instance level. We refine **IC8** into **IC8.1**, **IC8.2** and **IC8.3**.

IC8(C)(M): All *ResolvedImplementationValues* $riv \in RIV$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model V*, have to contain *System Elements* $\delta_V \in \Delta_V$ and *Configurations* $cfg_V \in CFG_V$ must correspond to *System Elements* $\delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs}$ and *Configurations* $cfg_R^{cs} \in CFG_R^{cs}$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result R*, which are affected by **IC5** and **IC7**, respectively.

$$\forall riv \in RIV : \exists \delta_V \in \Delta_V, \exists cfg_V \in CFG_V, \exists \delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs}, \exists cfg_R^{cs} \in CFG_R^{cs} :$$

$$\langle riv, \delta_V \rangle \wedge \langle riv, cfg_V \rangle \wedge cfg_V \leftrightarrow cfg_R^{cs} \wedge \delta_V \leftrightarrow \delta_R^{cs}$$

IC8.1(T)(M): There must exist exist *System Elements* $\delta_V \in \Delta_V$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model V*, corresponding to *System Elements* $\delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs}$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result R*, which are affected by **IC5**.

$$\Delta_V^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_V^{cs} = \{\delta_V \in \Delta_V \mid \exists \delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs} : \delta_V \leftrightarrow \delta_R^{cs}\}$$

IC8.2(T)(M): There must exist exist *Configurations* $cfg_V \in CFG_V$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* V , corresponding to *Configurations* $cfg_R^{cs} \in CFG_R^{cs}$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result* R , which are affected by **IC7**.

$$CFG_V^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$CFG_V^{cs} = \{cfg_V \in CFG_V \mid \exists cfg_R^{cs} \in CFG_R^{cs} : cfg_V \leftrightarrow cfg_R^{cs}\}$$

IC8.3(C)(M): All *ResolvedImplementationValues* $riv \in RIV$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* V must reference *System Elements* $\delta_V^{cs} \in \Delta_V^{cs}$ and *Configurations* $cfg_V^{cs} \in CFG_V^{cs}$, that are affected by **IC8.1** and **IC8.2**, respectively.

$$\forall riv \in RIV : \exists \delta_V^{cs} \in \Delta_V^{cs}, \exists cfg_V^{cs} \in CFG_V^{cs} : \langle riv, \delta_V^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle riv, cfg_V^{cs} \rangle$$

IC8(C)(I): All instances of *ResolvedImplementationValues* $riv \in RIV$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* V have to contain instance of the *System Element* $\delta_V \in \Delta_V$ and the contained instance of the *Configuration* $cfg_V \in CFG_V$ must correspond to *System Elements* $\delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs}$ and *Configurations* $cfg_R^{cs} \in CFG_R^{cs}$ in the *Source Code Analysis Result* R , which are affected by **IC5** and **IC7**, respectively.

$$\forall riv \in RIV : \exists \delta_V \in \Delta_V, \exists cfg_V \in CFG_V, \exists \delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs}, \exists cfg_R^{cs} \in CFG_R^{cs} : \\ \langle riv, \delta_V \rangle \wedge \langle riv, cfg_V \rangle \wedge \underline{cfg_V} \leftrightarrow \underline{cfg_R^{cs}} \wedge \underline{\delta_V} \leftrightarrow \underline{\delta_R^{cs}}$$

IC8.1(T)(I): There must exist instances of *System Elements* $\delta_V \in \Delta_V$ in an instance of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* V , correspondto *System Elements* $\delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs}$ in an instance of the *Source Code Analysis Result* R , which are affected by **IC5**.

$$\Delta_V^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\Delta_V^{cs} = \{\delta_V \in \Delta_V \mid \exists \delta_R^{cs} \in \Delta_R^{cs} : \delta_V \leftrightarrow \delta_R^{cs}\}$$

IC8.2(T)(I): There must exist correspondences for instances of *Configurations* $cfg_V \in CFG_V$ in the instance of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* V , corresponding them with instances of *Configurations* $cfg_R^{cs} \in CFG_R^{cs}$ in an instance of the *Source Code Analysis Result* R , which are affected **IC7**.

$$\underline{CFG_V^{cs}} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{CFG_V^{cs}} = \{\underline{cfg_V} \in \underline{CFG_V} \mid \exists \underline{cfg_R^{cs}} \in \underline{CFG_R^{cs}} : \underline{cfg_V} \leftrightarrow \underline{cfg_R^{cs}}\}$$

IC8.3(C)(I): All instances of the *ResolvedImplementationValues* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$ in an instance of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} must reference an instance of the *System Elements* $\underline{\delta}_V^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_V^{CS}$ and *Configurations* $\underline{cfg}_V^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_V^{CS}$ in the instance of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} that are affected by **IC8.1** and **IC8.2**, respectively.

$$\forall \underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV} : \exists \underline{\delta}_V^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_V^{CS}, \exists \underline{cfg}_V^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_V^{CS} : \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{\delta}_V^{cs} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{cfg}_V^{cs} \rangle$$

In the following, we define **IC9**. Similar to **IC8** we refine **IC9** into **IC9.1** and **IC9.2**:

IC9(T)(M): All *ResolvedImplementationValues* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} , have to contain *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V$ corresponding to *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{CS}$ in the *Annotated Source Code* affected by **IC1**.

$$\forall \underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV} : \exists \underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V, \exists \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{CS} : \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{s}_V \rangle \wedge \underline{s}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_C^{cs}$$

IC9.1(T)(M): There must exist a *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} , corresponding to *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{CS}$ in the *Annotated Source Code* affected by **IC1**.

$$\underline{S}_V^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{S}_V^{cs} = \{ \underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V \mid \exists \underline{s}_R^{cs} \in \underline{S}_R^{CS} : \underline{s}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_R^{cs} \}$$

IC9.2(T)(M): All *ResolvedImplementationValues* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} , have to contain *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V$ affected by **IC9.1**.

$$\forall \underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV} : \exists \underline{s}_V^{cs} \in \underline{S}_V^{CS} : \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{s}_V^{cs} \rangle$$

IC9(T)(I): In all instances of *ResolvedImplementationValues* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$ in a model of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} , a correspondence for the contained value of a *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V$ must exist corresponding them to a value of a *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{CS}$ in the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} affected by **IC1**.

$$\forall \underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV} : \exists \underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V, \exists \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{CS} : \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{s}_V \rangle \wedge \underline{s}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_C^{cs}$$

IC9.1(T)(I): There must exist a correspondence for instances of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V$ in an instance of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} , corresponding them to instances of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$ in an instance of the *Annotated Source Code* affected by **IC1**.

$$\underline{S}_V^{cs} \neq \emptyset$$

where

$$\underline{S}_V^{cs} = \{ \underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V \mid \exists \underline{s}_R^{cs} \in \underline{S}_R^{cs} : \underline{s}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_R^{cs} \}$$

IC9.2(T)(I): All instances of *ResolvedImplementationValues* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$ in the model of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} , have to contain instances of *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_V^{cs} \in \underline{S}_V^{cs}$ affected by **IC9.1**.

$$\forall \underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV} : \exists \underline{s}_V^{cs} \in \underline{S}_V^{cs} : \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{s}_V^{cs} \rangle$$

We define **IC10** as follows:

IC10(C)(M): The *Security Characteristics* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$ in the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} corresponding to the *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V$ in a *Resolved Implementation Value* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} affected by **IC9** must be referenced in a *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ in the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} corresponding to the *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_V \in \underline{CFG}_V$ affected by **IC8** in the same *Resolved Implementation Value*.

$$\forall \underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV} : \exists \underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V, \exists \underline{cfg}_V \in \underline{CFG}_V, \exists \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}, \exists \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} : \\ \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{s}_V \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{cfg}_V \rangle \wedge \underline{cfg}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \wedge \underline{s}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_C^{cs} \wedge \langle \underline{cfg}_C^{cs}, \underline{s}_C^{cs} \rangle$$

IC10(C)(I): The value of a *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$ in the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} corresponding to the value of a *Security Characteristic* $\underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V$ in a *Resolved Implementation Value* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$ in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* \underline{V} affected by **IC9** must be referenced in a instance of a *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ in the model of the *Annotated Source Code* \underline{C} corresponding to an instance of a *Configuration* $\underline{cfg}_V \in \underline{CFG}_V$ affected by **IC8** in the same *Resolved Implementation Value* $\underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV}$.

$$\forall \underline{riv} \in \underline{RIV} : \exists \underline{s}_V \in \underline{S}_V, \exists \underline{cfg}_V \in \underline{CFG}_V, \exists \underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}, \exists \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} : \\ \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{s}_V \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{riv}, \underline{cfg}_V \rangle \wedge \underline{cfg}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \wedge \underline{s}_V \leftrightarrow \underline{s}_C^{cs} \wedge \langle \underline{cfg}_C^{cs}, \underline{s}_C^{cs} \rangle$$

5 Evaluation of Coverage

In this section, we provide supplementary information about the evaluation regarding the coverage of the reference metamodels and the coverage of the ICs on metamodel and model level. Section 5.1 provides a formalization of the coverage metrics of the reference metamodels and the ICs. Section 5.2 describes the conformances between our reference metamodels and the input and output metamodels of Access Analysis, the Extended Dataflow Analysis (DFA-Ext), JOANA and the extended CodeQL (CodeQL-Ext). Section 5.3 provides then details about the evaluation of the coverage, such as additional (meta)model, the creation of JUnit-Test functions to automate the evaluation and the presentation and discussion of the evaluation results for one case of our case study in our article [35].

5.1 Formalizing the Specialization of the Coverage Metrics

The metric *Coverage* proposed in our article [35] must be adapted before we can use it to evaluate the coverage of the reference metamodels for answering (Q1.1) and the coverage of the integration conditions (Q1.2 and Q1.3). In this section, we supplement our definition in the article [35] with a formalization of the conditions *COND*, the artifacts *A* to be inspected, and how *hold* determines whether the conditions hold. We denote the definitions used for the evaluation of the reference metamodels and evaluation of the integration conditions with the subscript *Ref* and *IC* respectively.

5.1.1 Coverage of Reference Metamodels

To evaluate the coverage of the reference metamodels to answer Q1.1, we construct $Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref})$ in Equation (5.1)

$$Coverage(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = \frac{\sum_{cond_{Ref} \in COND_{Ref}} hold_{Ref}(A, cond_{Ref})}{|COND_{Ref}|} \quad (5.1)$$

with

$$hold: A \times COND_{Ref} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$$

Here, A_{Ref} contains the input or output metamodel of the analysis under study, i.e., their metaclasses $a_{Ref} \in A_{Ref}$ and their references $\langle a_{Ref}, a'_{Ref} \rangle$ with $a_{Ref}, a'_{Ref} \in A_{Ref}$. For every metaclass r of the reference metamodels R , we define a condition $cond_{r,R} \in COND_{Ref}$ which

states that the input or output metamodel of an analysis contains a metaclass conforming to r . Thus, $cond_r^R$ comprises the reference metamodels and an arbitrary but fixed metaclass r . The reference metamodel for output metamodels is described only for source code analyses. Consequently, we calculate $Coverage_{Ref}$ using conditions $cond_{r,R}$ only for reference metamodel for output metamodels when inspecting source code analyses. Thus, we also only consider the output metamodels of the analysis in the evaluation artifacts A_{Ref} when inspecting source code analyses. $Coverage_{Ref}$ is calculated using $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{r,R})$. We define $hold_{ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{r,R})$ follows using the formalization of conformance in Equation (4.1):

$$hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{r,R}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \exists a_{Ref} \in A_{Ref}: conf(r, R, a_{Ref}, A_{Ref}) \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (5.2)$$

Consequently, $hold_{Ref}$ determines whether there exists a metaclass a_{Ref} in the metamodels of the analysis which *conforms* to the given metaclass of the reference metamodels captured by $cond_{r,R}$.

With $hold_{Ref}$, we define the reference metamodels to be fully covered by the input and output metamodels of an analysis if $hold_{Ref}$ evaluates to true for all conditions $cond$. In other words, each metaclass of the reference metamodels has a *conforming* metaclass in the input and output metamodels of the analysis.

With these definitions of $COND_{Ref}$, A_{Ref} and $hold_{Ref}$, the coverage allows obtaining insights into how well metamodels of analyses map to our reference metamodels. Further, our definitions here allow us to calculate $Coverage$ for existing analyses so as to determine whether our coupling approach applies to existing analyses or only to analyses tailored to our coupling. Wherever a reference metamodel cannot be applied to existing analyses, added effort must be expended to adapt the metamodels of the analysis to make the analysis usable with our coupling approach, thus contradicting a black-box coupling.

5.1.2 Coverage of Integration Conditions

For **Q1.2** and **Q1.3**, to evaluate the coverage of the ICs on the metamodel and model level, we construct the metric $Coverage_{IC}(A_{IC}, COND_{IC})$ in Equation (5.3).

$$Coverage(A_{IC}, COND_{IC}) = \frac{\sum_{cond_{IC} \in COND_{IC}} hold_{IC}(A, cond_{IC})}{|COND_{IC}|} \quad (5.3)$$

where

$$hold: A \times COND_{Ref} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$$

We formulate a condition for every IC stating that it holds on the metamodel and model level. As the ICs are already conditions themselves, we denote the conditions $cond$ with the respective IC $IC_i \in COND$. The ICs describe relations between the input and output (meta)models of the architectural and source code analyses. The ICs are also formulated

for the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*. In our evaluation, each transformation generates a correspondence model that captures the correspondences between elements in the transformations of our coupling process. Therefore, A_{IC} comprises the input and output models of the analyses, of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*, and of the correspondence models and their respective metamodels.

To define $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, ICi)$, we use the classes of ICs, i.e., *correspondence conditions* and *constraint conditions*. $hold_{IC}^{corr}(A_{IC}, ICi)$ is applied for *correspondence conditions* and $hold_{IC}^{corr}(A_{IC}, ICi)$ for *constraint conditions*. We define the illustrative function $affected(ICi, A_{IC})$ to calculate the metaclasses affected by a IC. As defined in Equation (5.4) $affected(ICi, A_{IC})$ determines all metaclasses in $a_{ICi} \in A_{IC}$ that conform to metaclasses $r_{ICi} \in R_{ICi} \subset R$ of the reference metamodel R that are captured in the definition of ICi.

$$affected(ICi, A_{IC}) = \{a_{ICi} \in A_{IC} \mid \exists r_{ICi} \in R_{ICi} \subset R: conf(r_{ICi}, R, a_{ICi}, A_{IC})\}$$

where

$$R \text{ contains reference metamodels} \tag{5.4}$$

$$R_{ICi} \subset R \text{ contains all reference metaclasses in definition of ICi}$$

In our evaluation, we perform $affected_M^{Corr}(ICi, A_{IC})$ manually based on the case and our conformances defined in Section 4.1 and also contained in our replication package [34].

With $affected_M^{Corr}(ICi, A_{IC})$ we define $hold_{IC}^{corr}$ to evaluate the correspondence conditions as described in Equation (5.5).

$$hold_{IC}^{corr}(A_{IC}, ICi) = \begin{cases} 1, & C^{ICi} \neq \emptyset \wedge \underline{C}^{ICi} \neq \emptyset \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases}$$

where

$$X, Y, \underline{X}, \underline{Y} \subset A_{IC}$$

$$CR_{X,Y}^{ICi} = \{\leftrightarrow_{x,y} \in C_{X,Y} \mid x = fst(\leftrightarrow_{x,y}) \wedge y = snd(\leftrightarrow_{x,y}) \wedge x, y \in affected(ICi, A_{IC}) \wedge \exists \underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x,y} \in \underline{C}_{X,Y}: \underline{x} = fst(\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x,y}) \wedge \underline{y} = snd(\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x,y}) \wedge isInst(\underline{x}, x) \wedge isInst(\underline{y}, y)\}$$

$$\underline{C}^{ICi} = \{\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x,y} \in \underline{C}_{X,Y} \mid \exists \leftrightarrow_{x,y} \in C^{ICi}: x = fst(\leftrightarrow_{x,y}) \wedge y = snd(\leftrightarrow_{x,y}) \wedge \underline{x} = fst(\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x,y}) \wedge \underline{y} = snd(\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x,y}) \wedge isInst(\underline{x}, x) \wedge isInst(\underline{y}, y)\}$$

$$\tag{5.5}$$

In Equation (5.5) the function $isInst$ checks whether a model element is an instance of a given metaclass. Please note that some correspondence conditions describe required correspondences for multiple metaclasses of the reference metamodels (e.g., **IC2**) to provide more concise descriptions when possible. This is why we refined the ICs in Section 4.3. For simplicity in the formalization, we assume our refined versions of the ICs, where in every IC, correspondences for *one* element of the reference metamodels is captured. For example, in contrast to **IC2** where correspondences between *System Elements and Configurations* are required, **IC2.1** and **IC2.2** require correspondences for *System Elements (IC2.1)* or *Configurations*. However, please note that the actual automated evaluation will be performed

according to the ICs in our article [35] to maintain consistency. This is possible as the refinement of the correspondence conditions was only to separate independent required correspondences. Thus, we can also assemble them back into one combined condition.

We define $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, cond_{IC})$ based on the classes of ICs, i.e., *correspondence conditions* and *constraint conditions*. We define a IC to be covered if $hold_{IC}$ returns 1 for it. Only investigating whether metaclasses conform to the ICs (e.g., by capturing correspondences) will fail to provide information about whether these metaclasses are actually used in the coupling. Thus, we will investigate whether instances of metaclasses exist that conform to the IC. This approach is valid because instances and references between instances can only exist if corresponding metaclasses and references between metaclasses, e.g., to capture correspondences, are defined.

Thus, $hold_{IC}^{corr}$ returns 1 for *correspondence conditions* if (1) for each required correspondence, *at least one* correspondence exists between instances of metaclasses affected by the IC (metamodel level) (captured in C^{ICi}) and (2) if correspondences exist between instances of those metaclasses as required by the IC (model level) (captured by \underline{C}^{ICi}). In our running example, there are correspondences between values *high*, *medium* and *low* of the metaclass *security characteristic of data* in the *Annotated Architectural Model* to the correspondingly named values in the *Annotated Source Code* of the metaclass *Level*. Therefore, $hold_{IC}^{corr}$ evaluates on the metamodel level to true because there is a correspondence between an instance of the metaclass *Level* and an instance of the metaclass *Security Characteristic of Data* (i.e., the actual target of the coupling scenario). Additionally, $hold_{IC}^{corr}$ evaluates to true on the *model* level because all values of *Level* have a correspondence to the *Annotated Architectural Model*.

We define $hold_{IC}^{const}$ in Equation (5.6).

$$hold_{IC}^{const}(A_{IC}, ICi) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } ICi \text{ defined } \forall \Rightarrow \\ & \forall a_{ICi} \in CE^{ICi}: \underline{CE}(a_{ICi})^{ICi} \neq \emptyset \wedge \\ & \forall \underline{y} \in \underline{Y}: isInst(\underline{y}, y) \wedge \underline{y} \in \underline{CE}(y)^{ICi} \\ 1, & \text{if } ICi \text{ defined } \exists \Rightarrow \\ & \exists y \in CE^{ICi}: \underline{CE}(y)^{ICi} \neq \emptyset \wedge \\ & \exists \underline{y} \in \underline{Y}: isInst(\underline{y}, y) \wedge \underline{y} \in \underline{CE}(y)^{ICi} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5.6)$$

where

$$CE^{ICi} = \{a_{ICi}^{const} \in A_{IC} \mid a_{ICi}^{const} \text{ is constrained by } ICi\}$$

$$RE^{ICi}(a_{ICi}^{const}) = \{a_{ICi}^{ref} \in A_{IC} \mid a_{ICi}^{const} \in CE_{ICi} \wedge \langle a_{ICi}^{const}, a_{ICi}^{ref} \rangle \text{ required according to } ICi\}$$

$$\underline{CE}^{ICi}(a_{ICi}^{const}) = \{a_{ICi}^{const} \in A_{IC} \mid a_{ICi}^{const} \in CE_{ICi} \wedge isInst(a_{ICi}^{const}, a_{ICi}^{const}) \wedge$$

$$(\forall a_{ICi}^{ref} \in RE_{ICi}(a_{ICi}^{const}): \exists \underline{a}_{ICi}^{ref} \in \underline{A}_{IC}: isInst(\underline{a}_{ICi}^{ref}, a_{ICi}^{ref}) \wedge \langle \underline{a}_{ICi}^{const}, \underline{a}_{ICi}^{ref} \rangle \wedge$$

$$\wedge (\exists \underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x, a_{ICi}^{corr}} \in \underline{CR}^{IC}: \underline{a}_{ICi}^{ref} = snd(\underline{\leftrightarrow}_{x, y}))\}$$

In $hold_{IC}^{const}$, as described in Equation (5.6), we determine the metaclasses constrained by the condition based on the conformance to the metaclass of the reference metamodel captured in the condition (CE_{ICi}). In addition, we determine the referenced metaclasses for a single constrained metaclass that have to exist according to the constraint condition ($RE(a_{ICi}^{const})_{ICi}$). With this information, we can determine whether an instance of a constrained metaclass conforms to the condition (formally captured here in $RE(a_{ICi}^{const})_{ICi}$). For calculating this, we assume a set \underline{CR}^{ICi} capturing all correspondences conforming to the correspondence conditions required by ICi .

With this, $hold_{IC}^{const}$ returns 1 for a *constraint condition* if (1) one instance of at least one or all metaclasses affected by the IC exists that references instances of metaclasses as described by the IC (metamodel level) and (first part of Equation (5.6) (2) at least one or all instances of those metaclasses (depending on the condition) reference instances of metaclasses as described by the condition. Thus, if $hold_{IC}^{const}$ evaluates to true for both parts, it returns 1 and 0 otherwise. In our running example, the information flow annotation annotates the *Level high* to the *Parameter userData* (IC2) in the buy service and to the *Parameter userData* in the buy method corresponding to the *security characteristic of data high* (IC1). This information flow annotation annotates an instance of the metaclass *Level* captured in IC1 to an instance of the metaclass *Parameter* captured in IC2. Additionally, since a provision of the information flow annotation is defined in the source code, the annotation is captured in an implicit configuration. With the instances of *Level* and *Parameter* annotated by these annotations having a correspondence to the *Annotated Architectural Model*, $hold_{IC}(E, IC3)$ returns 1.

With $hold_{IC}^{corr}$ and $hold_{IC}^{const}$, we provide two functions with slightly different approaches for the evaluation. In addition, we have to embed both functions in the metric $Coverage_{IC}$. Thus, we define $hold_{IC}$ in Equation (5.7) as a function selecting the appropriate function based on whether the IC is a correspondence condition or constraint condition. This selection is performed in our evaluation manually as we are aware how whether the IC is an correspondence condition or integration condition.

$$hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, ICi) = \begin{cases} hold_{IC}^{corr}(A_{IC}, ICi) & \text{if } ICi \text{ is correspondence condition} \\ hold_{IC}^{const}(A_{IC}, ICi) & \text{if } ICi \text{ is constraint condition} \end{cases} \quad (5.7)$$

$Coverage_{IC}$ evaluates if all, some or no ICs hold on the metamodel and model level. Thus, the definitions of $COND_{IC}$, A_{IC} and $hold_{IC}$ allow obtaining insights into whether the ICs are *necessary*. If $hold_{IC}$ evaluates to 0 for one IC, then the condition is not necessary. One consequence is that a *coupling expert* who attempts to enforce a IC which is actually unnecessary for the coupling will likely be hindered by the unnecessary conditions.

5.2 Coverage of the Reference Metamodels

Here, We provide our mappings of the metaclasses of the input and output metamodels of the analyses in the evaluation of our coupling approach [35], i.e., Access Analysis, DFA-Ext, CodeQL-Ext and *JOANA* to the reference metamodels to make the results of the evaluation replicable. Therefore, in this section, we present the mappings of the elements of the input metamodels and output metamodels of the case study analyses to the elements of the reference structures. We describe the mappings of the reference metamodels to the Access Analysis [28], the DFA-Ext, the extended CodeQL and *JOANA* in Sections 5.2.1 to 5.2.4 respectively. Listing all system elements for the input models of analyses would not be feasible for evaluating the coupling approach. We, therefore, detail the mappings for *System Elements* only if a specification of security characteristics for them is possible. *JOANA* and CodeQL provide no EMF metamodel for their input or output. This is why we created them as described in Section 3.6.2 and Section 3.6.1. We describe the mappings based on the EMF metamodels and not regarding the exposed syntax of the analyses to provide a uniform basis for applying the ICs later in this paper. For the configuration of an analysis only by its metaclasses, we use the term *Implicit* for the configuration. If an analysis uses at least one metaclass enabling the identification for an analysis execution, we classify this element as *Configuration*. Still, it may be possible that the configuration still needs additional input, e.g., the location of the Java source code as in *JOANA*. For security policies defined by the analysis or in the tooling, i.e., not definable by an analysis user, we use the term *Integrated*. We provide all mappings also in the replication package [34].

5.2.1 Conformance between Reference Metamodel and Input Metamodel of Access Analysis

In this section, we describe the conformances of the input metamodels and the input metamodel of the Access Analysis [28] to the metaclasses of the reference metamodels. We provide no conformances for the reference metamodels for the output metamodels or *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodels, as they only address source code analyses in our coupling approach [35].

The conformances of the elements of the input metamodel of the Access Analysis to the reference metamodels is presented in Table 5.1. For a full description of the elements in the Access Analysis metamodel, please refer to the Access Analysis Paper [28]. The access analysis uses elements of the PCM and annotates them with security characteristics. PCM elements like *Parameters*, the *Call* or *Return* of a *OperationSignature*, the *ResourceContainers* or *Linking Resources* are all classified as *System Elements* as they are buildingblock of the system. Therefore, we define $hold(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because there are elements of the PCM, conforming to *System Element*. The Access Analysis uses self-definable *DataSets* to characterize data for the security analysis conforming to the description of *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because there are elements of the Access Analysis input metamodel, conforming to *Security Characteristic*. The annotation *Information Flow (Annotation)* assigns *DataSets* to

Reference Metamodel Metaclass	Analysis Input Metamodel Metaclass
Security Characteristic	DataSet
Security Characteristic	Location
Security Characteristic	Tamper Protection
Security Characteristic	Connection Type
Security Characteristic	SharingType
Annotation	Information Flow
Annotation	LocationAndTamperProtection
Annotation	Encryption
Annotation	FurtherPhysicalConnections
Annotation	Sharing
System Element	Interface
System Element	Operation Signature
System Element	Parameter
System Element	Call
System Element	Return
System Element	Resource Container
Configuration	Implicit
Security Policy	Integrated

Table 5.1: Conformances for input metamodels to the input metamodel of Access Analysis to the reference metamodel for input metamodels

Parameters (System Element), *Call (System Element)* and *Return (System Element)*. It is also possible to annotate *Interfaces (System Element)* all of the prior system elements. The annotations *Sharing(Annotation)* and *FurtherPhysicalConnections(Annotation)* annotate *SharingType* and *ConnectionType* respectively to *ResourceContainers(System Element)* to define whether resources are used in a shared environment or whether the resource container may have connections that can be used by an *Adversary*. The annotation *LocationAndTamperProtection (Annotation)* annotates *Locations (Security Characteristic)* or *TamperProtection* to either a *ResourceContainer (System Element)* or *LinkingResource (System Element)* to define, their locations and whether mechanisms are used to avoid tampering by an *Adversary*. The annotation *Encryption (Annotation)* defines whether data sent over a *LinkingResource(System Element)* is encrypted. *Information Flow*, *Sharing*, *LocationAndTamperProtection*, and *Encryption* references a *System Element* and a *Security Characteristic*, which is why we determine them to be conformant to the metaclass *Annotation* of the reference metamodels. Therefore, we define $hold(A_{Ref}, Annotation)$ returning *true* because there are elements of the Access Analysis input metamodel, conforming to *Annotation*. The Prolog rules of the analysis tooling described by Kramer et al. [28] define when a vulnerability is reported. They use, among others, *DataSets* and *Locations* to determine a vulnerability, classifying the rules as *integrated Security Policy*. Therefore, we define $hold(A_{Ref}, SecurityPolicy)$ returning *true* because the Prolog rules contain the necessary relations described in the reference metamodels. The *Repository Model*, the *Confidentiality Model*, the *Allocation Model*, the *Adversary Model*, the *Resource Environment Model* and the *System Model* are all used as input to configure the

Reference Metamodel Metaclass	Analysis Input Metamodel Metaclass
System Element	Parameter
System Element	AssemblyContext
System Element	ResourceContainer
Security Characteristic	Literal
Annotation	AssemblyAssignee
Annotation	ResourceAssignee
Annotation	UsageAssignee
Annotation	ParameterAnnotation
Configuration	Implicit
Security Policy	Integrated

Table 5.2: Mappings of the reference metamodel for input metamodels to the input metamodel of Access Analysis

analysis. They contain all *System Element*, *Annotation* and *Security Characteristic*. In addition, the *Security Policy* is always the same as it is *implicitly* captured. This is why we define the *Configuration* to be *implicit*. Therefore, we define $hold(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because the input files of the AccessAnalysis contain the necessary relations described in the reference metamodels.

We found conformance between the input of the Access Analysis for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for input metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{Ref})$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodels for the Access Analysis ($Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = 1$).

5.2.2 Conformances between Reference Metamodel and Input Metamodel of Extended Dataflow Analysis

In this section, we describe the conformance of the input metamodel of the DFA-Ext to the reference metamodel for input metamodels. We provide no conformances for the reference metamodels for the output metamodels or *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodels, as they only address source code analyses in our coupling approach [35]. The conformances are listed in Table 5.2. In our evaluation, we use the current implementation and models of the DFA discussed by Boltz et al. [7].

The DFA-Ext is a framework that allows the definition of custom *Characteristics* describing security-relevant characterizations of elements in the PCM to analyze data flow vulnerabilities. In the PCM exist, among others, the metaclass *Parameter*, *AssemblyContext* and *ResourceContainer*, which are building blocks of the system. Therefore, we classify them as *System Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because the *Parameter*, *AssemblyContext* and *ResourceContainer* conform to *System Element*. While the *Characteristics* are annotated, the underlying metaclass *Literal* describes every available value. As described in Chapter 3, we define either literals for *Roles*, such as *TravelAgency*,

User or Airline for the TravelPlanner [24], *Confidentiality Levels*, i.e., high and low for JPMail used by Tuma et al. [47] or by Seifermann et al. [41]. This is why we characterize *Literals* as *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because *Literal* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. In the DFA, the annotations *AssemblyAssignee* and *ResourceAssignee* are used to annotate *Literals (Security Characteristic)* to *AssemblyContext(System Element)* or *ResourceContainer(System Element)*. We add to these annotations the *ParameterAnnotation* in the DFA-Ext (c.f., Section 3.6.3), which annotates *Literals (Security Characteristic)* to *Parameter(System Element)*. *AssemblyAssignee*, *ResourceAssignee* and *ParameterAnnotation* all reference a *Security Characteristic* and a *System Element*, making them conformant to *Annotation*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Annotation)$ returning *true* because *AssemblyAssignee*, *ResourceAssignee* and *ParameterAnnotation* conform to *Annotation*. In the current state of the DFA tooling, the analysis determines when a vulnerability is reported based on constraints that must be compiled with the analysis framework for their evaluation. These constraints use relations between *Literals* to determine whether a vulnerability exists. Therefore, we classify the *Security Policy* as *Integrated*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityPolicy)$ returning *true* because the implemented constraints contain the necessary relations described in the reference metamodels. The DFA-Ext configures the analysis by the *System Model*, *UsageProfile Model*, the *DataDictionary Model*, *Repository Model*, *NodeCharacteristics Model* and the *ParameterAnnotations Model* without a dedicated metaclass to identify an execution of the analysis. While the current state of the tooling, the *Security Policy* is *Integrated* in the analysis tooling, there exists a version of the DFA that defines the *Security Policy* in a separate model, which is also used as input. Therefore, we define the *Configuration* as *Implicit*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because the input files of the DFA-Ext contain the necessary relations described in the reference metamodels.

We found conformance between the input of the Access Analysis for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for input metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond)$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodels for the DFA-Ext, i.e., ($Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = 1$).

5.2.3 Conformance between Reference Metamodel and Metamodels of JOANA

In this section, we elaborate the conformance of the input metamodel, output metamodel and *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel of *JOANA* to the reference metamodels.

Conformances for the Input Metamodel The conformances of the metaclasses in the input metamodel of *JOANA* to the metaclasses of the reference metamodel for input metamodels regarding the created metamodel described in Section 3.6.2 is presented in Table 5.3. *JOANA* uses the metaclasses *Method*, *Field* and *Parameter* from the Java metamodel. These metaclasses provide building blocks to describe the implementation of the system. Therefore, we classify *Methods*, *Fields* and *Parameters* as *System Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because the *Methods*, *Fields* and *Parameters*

Reference Metamodel Element	Metamodel Element
System Element	Method
System Element	Parameter
System Element	Field
Security Characteristic	Level
Annotation	Source
Annotation	Sink
Security Policy	Lattice
Configuration	EntryPoint

Table 5.3: Conformances for the input metamodel of *JOANA* to the reference metamodel for input metamodels

conform to *System Element*. *JOANA* uses *Level* to describe information flow-related characteristics of data, e.g., in *Fields* or *Parameters*. Therefore, we classify *Level* as *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because *Level* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. The metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* describe annotations that reference either a *Field* (*System Element*) or a *Parameter* (*System Element*) to specify them as a source or sink in an information flow and references a *Level* (*Security Characteristic*) to define the expected characteristics of data confined in them. Therefore, *Source* and *Sink* reference a *System Element* and a *Security Characteristic*, making them conform to the *Annotation*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Annotation)$ returning *true* because *Source* and *Sink* conform to *Annotation*. *JOANA* provides the *Lattice* metaclass to describe allowed information flows in the system. For this purpose, a *Lattice* contains one or more instances of the *MayFlow* metaclass. This metaclass references two instances of *Level* (*Security Characteristic*). Therefore, *Lattice* also reaches *Level* (*Security Characteristic*) over the contained *MayFlow* instances. This results in conformance to the *Security Policy* metaclass of the reference metamodel. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityPolicy)$ returning *true* because *Lattice* conforms to *Security Policy*. *JOANA* uses *EntryPoints* to specify the method used as the start for creating the program representation for a single analysis execution. An *EntryPoint* is identified by a unique *Tag*. The *EntryPoint* also contains the applicable security *Level* (*Security Characteristic*) in the analysis run and a *Lattice* (*Security Policy*). The specification of the expected behavior regarding information flow is performed by the annotations *Sources* (*Annotation*) and *Sinks* (*Annotation*) *JOANA* requires, aside from the *EntryPoint*, also the Java source code to run an analysis. The tuple of *EntryPoint* and *JavaRoot* contains references to *System Element*, *Security Characteristic*, *Annotation* and *Security Policy*, making this tuple conforming to *Configuration* while *EntryPoint* is the element making an analysis execution identifiable. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because *EntryPoint* and *JavaRoot* together conform to *Configuration*.

We found conformance between the input metamodels of the *JOANA* for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for input metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Cond)$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodel for input metamodels for the *JOANA* ($Coverage_{Ref}(E, COND) = 1$).

Reference Metamodel Metaclass	Analysis Output Metamodel Metaclass
System Element	Field_SCAR
System Element	Parameter_SCAR
Security Characteristic	Level_SCAR
Result Entry	Flow
Result Entry Element	Source
Result Entry Element	Sink
Configuration	EntryPoint_SCAR

Table 5.4: Conformances for the output metamodel of *JOANA* to the reference metamodel for output metamodels

Conformances for the Output Metamodel The conformance of the metaclasses of the output metamodel of the extended CodeQL to the metaclasses of the reference metamodels for output metamodels are provided in Table 5.4. The *Field_SCAR* and *Parameter_SCAR* both represent implementation elements of the Java source code. Therefore, we classify them as *System Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because the *Parameters_SCAR* and *Fields_SCAR* conform to *System Element*. *Level_SCAR* identifies the characteristic of data in the input metamodel, which led to the violation. Therefore, we classify it as *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because *Level_SCAR* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. The metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* reference a *Field_SCAR* (*System Element*) or *Parameter_SCAR* (*System Element*) and a *SecurityLevel_SCAR* (*System Element*) as part of an illegal flow. *Source* and *Sink* reference a *System Element* and a *Security Characteristic* as part of a counter-example. This makes *Source* and *Sink* conforming to *Result Entry Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, ResultEntryElement)$ returning *true* because *Source* and *Sink* conform to *Security Characteristic*. *EntryPoint_SCAR* identifies an *EntryPoint* in the input metamodel, which represents a *Configuration*. This is why we classify *EntryPoint_SCAR* in the output metamodel of *JOANA* also as *Configuration*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because *EntryPoint_SCAR* conforms to *Result Entry Element*. The illegal flows are represented by an *Flow* that references a *EntryPoint_SCAR* (*Configuration*), a *Source* (*Result Entry Element*) and a *Sink* (*Result Entry Element*) of an illegal flow. Because *Flow* represents a single counter-example and references *Configuration* and one or more *Result Entry Element*, it conforms to *Result Entry*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, ResultEntry)$ returning *true* because *Flow* conforms to *Result Entry*.

We found conformance between the output metamodel of the *JOANA* for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for output metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Cond)$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodel for output metamodels for *JOANA* ($Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = 1$).

Conformances for the Resulting Values Metamodel Table 5.5 describes the conformances between the metaclasses of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel of the *JOANA* and the metaclasses of the reference metamodel for the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*

Reference Metamodel Metaclass	Resolved Implementation Values Metamodel Metaclass
System Element	Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValue
Security Characteristic	Level_ResolvedImplementationValues
Configuration	EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues
<i>Resolved Implementation Value</i>	ResolvedImplementationValue

Table 5.5: Conformances for the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* of *JOANA* to the reference metamodel for *Resolved Implementation Values Model*

metamodel. The *Resolved Implementation Values Model* of *JOANA* comprises the *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* metaclass identifying a *Parameter* (*System Element*) in the input metamodel of *JOANA*. Therefore, we classify *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* as *System Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because the *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* conforms to *System Element*. *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* metaclass identifies a *Level* (*Security Characteristic*) in the input metamodel of *JOANA*. Therefore, we classify *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* as *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValue* identifies an *EntryPoint* (*Configuration*) in the input metamodel of *JOANA*. Therefore, we classify *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValue* as *Configuration*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValue* conforms to *Configuration*. The *ResolvedImplementationValue* references a *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* (*System Element*), *SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues* (*Security Characteristic*) and *RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue* (*Configuration*). Therefore, *ResolvedImplementationValue* references a *System Element*, *Security Characteristic* and *Configuration*. This makes *ResolvedImplementationValue* conforming to the *Resolved Implementation Value*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, ResolvedImplementationValue)$ returning *true* because *ResolvedImplementationValue* conforms to *Resolved Implementation Value*.

We found conformance between the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel of *JOANA* for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{Ref})$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodel for the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel for *JOANA* ($Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = 1$).

5.2.4 Conformances between Reference Metamodel and Metamodels of CodeQL

In this section, we elaborate the mappings between the reference metamodels and the input metamodel, output metamodel and Resolved Implementation Value metamodel of *JOANA*.

Reference Metamodel Metaclass	Analysis Input Metamodel Metaclass
System Element	Parameter
System Element	Field
Security Characteristic	SecurityLevel
Annotation	SecurityLevelAnnotation
Security Policy	AllowedFlows
Configuration	(Query, JavaRoot)

Table 5.6: Conformances for the input metamodel of CodeQL-Ext to the reference metamodel for input metamodels

Conformances for the Input Metamodel The conformances of the metaclasses of the input metamodel of CodeQL-Ext to the metaclasses of the reference metamodel for the input metamodels, are presented in Table 5.6.

Our CodeQL-Ext uses a Java metamodel comprising, among others, method *Parameters* and *Fields*. These metaclasses are building blocks of Java source code. Therefore, we define method *Parameters* and *Fields* as *System Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because the *Parameters* and *Fields* conform to *System Element*. The *SecurityLevel* describes the characterization of data in *Parameters* and *Fields*. This is why we define *SecurityLevel* as *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because *SecurityLevel* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. *SecurityLevelAnnotations* define the *SecurityLevel* (*Security Characteristic*) for either *Parameters* (*System Element*) or *Fields* (*System Element*). Therefore, *SecurityLevelAnnotations* references a *Security Characteristic* and a *System Element*, making it conform to *Annotation*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Annotation)$ returning *true* because *SecurityLevelAnnotations* conforms to *Annotation*. We classify *AllowedFlows* as *Security Policy* because it references the *SecurityLevel* (*Security Characteristic*) to describe when a flow is not allowed, i.e., when a vulnerability is reported. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityPolicy)$ returning *true* because *AllowedFlows* conforms to *Security Policy*. In our CodeQL-Ext metamodel, a *Query* defines all information for an security characteristic of data-based analysis with CodeQL, i.e., we generate a CodeQL query file for each of these elements. The *Query* uses an *id* to be identifiable. The *Query* defines the applicable values of *SecurityLevel* (*Security Characteristic*) in the analysis. In addition, the *Query* contains the applied *SecurityLevelAnnotations* (*Annotation*). In addition to the previously mentioned elements, the *Query* defines a *AllowedFlows* (*Security Policy*). While CodeQL-Ext also requires the Java Source Code as input, *Query* allows for identification when multiple queries are executed on this source code. Therefore, we classify the combination of *Query* and *JavaRoot* as *Configuration*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because *Query* and *JavaRoot* together conform to *Configuration*.

We found conformance between the input of CodeQL-Ext for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for input metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{Ref})$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodel for input metamodels for the CodeQL-Ext ($Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = 1$).

Reference Metamodel Metaclass	Analysis Output Metamodel Metaclass
Result Entry	Result
Result Entry Element	ResultEntryElement
Configuration	RuleId
System Element	Parameter_SCAR
System Element	Field_SCAR
Security Characteristic	SecurityLevel_SCAR

Table 5.7: Conformances for the output metamodel of CodeQL-Ext to the reference metamodel for output metamodels

Conformances for the Output Metamodel The output metamodel of the extended CodeQL has a similar structure as the *JOANA* output metamodel defined in Section 3.6.1. The conformance of the metaclasses of the output metamodel of the extended CodeQL to the metaclasses of the reference metamodels for output metamodels are provided in Table 5.7. The *Field_SCAR* and *Parameter_SCAR* both represent implementation elements of the Java source code. Therefore, we classify them as *System Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because the *Parameters_SCAR* and *Fields_SCAR* conform to *System Element*. *SecurityLevel_SCAR* identifies the characteristic of data in the input metamodel, which led to the violation. Therefore, we classify it as *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because *SecurityLevel_SCAR* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. An *ResultEntryElement* references a *Field_SCAR* (*System Element*) or *Parameter_SCAR* (*System Element*) and a *SecurityLevel_SCAR* (*System Element*) as part of an illegal flow. Therefore, we classify the *ResultEntryElement* as *Result Entry Element* of the reference metamodel. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, ResultEntryElement)$ returning *true* because *ResultEntryElement* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. *RuleId* identifies a *Query* in the input metamodel, which represents a configuration. This is why we classify *RuleId* as *Configuration*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because *RuleId* conforms to *Result Entry Element*. The illegal flows are represented by an *Result* that references a *RuleId* (*Configuration*), and two *ResultEntryElements* (*Result Entry Element*) that represent the sources and sink of the illegal flow. Therefore, we classify *Result* as *Result Entry*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, ResultEntry)$ returning *true* because *Result* conforms to *Result Entry*.

We found conformance between the output metamodel of CodeQL-Ext for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for output metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{Ref})$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodel for output metamodels for the CodeQL-Ext ($Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = 1$).

Conformances for the Resulting Values Metamodel Table 5.8 describes the conformances between the metaclasses of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel of CodeQL-Ext and the metaclasses of the reference metamodel for the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel. The *Resolved Implementation Values Model* of CodeQL-Ext comprises the *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* metaclass identifying a *Parameter* in the input metamodel of CodeQL-Ext. Therefore, we classify *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues*

Reference Metamodel Metaclass	Resolved Implementation Values Metamodel Metaclass
<i>Resolved Implementation Value</i>	ResolvedImplementationValue
Configuration	RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue
Security Characteristic	SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues
System Element	Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues

Table 5.8: Conformances for the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* of CodeQL-Ext to the reference metamodel for *Resolved Implementation Values Model*

as *System Element*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SystemElement)$ returning *true* because the *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* conforms to *System Element*. *SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues* metaclass identifies a *SecurityLevel* in the input metamodel of CodeQL-Ext. Therefore, we classify *SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues* as *Security Characteristic*. Therefore, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, SecurityCharacteristic)$ returning *true* because *SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues* conforms to *Security Characteristic*. *RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue* identifies a *Query* in the input metamodel of CodeQL-Ext. Therefore, we classify *RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue* as *Configuration*. Consequently, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, Configuration)$ returning *true* because *RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue* conforms to *Configuration*. For CodeQL-Ext, the *ResolvedImplementationValue* references a *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues*(*System Element*), *SecurityLevel_ResolvedImplementationValues* (*Security Characteristic*) and *RuleId_ResolvedImplementationValue* (*Configuration*). Therefore, *ResolvedImplementationValue* references a *System Element*, *Security Characteristic* and *Configuration*. This makes *ResolvedImplementationValue* conforming to the *Resolved Implementation Value*. Consequently, we define $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, ResolvedImplementationValue)$ returning *true* because *ResolvedImplementationValue* conforms to *Resolved Implementation Value*.

We found conformance between the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel of CodeQL-Ext for every metaclass of the reference metamodel for *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodels, i.e., every $hold_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, cond_{Ref})$ returns *true*. Therefore, we have a full *Coverage* of the reference metamodel for the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel for the CodeQL-Ext ($Coverage_{Ref}(A_{Ref}, COND_{Ref}) = 1$).

5.3 Coverage of Integration Conditions

In evaluating our coupling approach [35], we inspect the *Coverage* of the ICs in successfully created couplings to determine whether the ICs are necessary. We perform a set of automated test cases which inspect whether the trace condition and constraint condition hold for the respective models. We create these tests based on the formalization of our ICs, presented in Section 4.3. To evaluate the coverage of the ICs, we use correspondence models, which enable the resolution between elements of two or more models. However, *Configuration* with several input models (*implicit Configuration*) or an identifying element, e.g., an *EntryPoint* of *JOANA*, and additional input makes creating correspondences and automated calculations

Figure 5.1: The metamodel for the representation of Access Analysis information flow annotations

difficult. Similarly, using stereotypes for annotating PCM elements by the AccessAnalysis introduced challenges in creating automated tests. Therefore, we introduce metamodels to support the automated evaluation of the coverage of ICs in Section 5.3.1. With these metamodels, we describe correspondence (meta)models in detail in Section 5.3.2. With the supporting (meta)model, correspondence models and the formalization of the ICs, we create the automated tests. The design of these tests is described in Section 5.3.3. Finally, we exemplarily describe the results based on this automation for the case comprising the Access Analysis, *JOANA* and *JPMail* in Section 5.3.4.

5.3.1 Coverage Evaluation Supporting Models

When evaluating the coverage of the ICs, we must identify the (meta)model elements targeted by each IC. However, we face two challenges in our case studies representing (meta)model elements in correspondences: 1) there is no unified representation of configurations in all case studies referencing all required other metaclasses of the reference metamodels, making their capturing in correspondences difficult 2) the access analysis uses a profile mechanism for representing the relevant information flow related annotations, making them also difficult to capture in correspondence models.

We address these challenges by providing additional EMF metamodels, models, and transformations and integrate them into the coupling and the coverage evaluation. We provide one metamodel to capture configurations. In addition, we provide a metamodel for capturing the *Information Flow* annotation in the Access Analysis and a transformation transforming the described annotations for one system into a model of this metamodel.

5.3.1.1 Access Analysis Annotations Metamodel

We define a metamodel for representing the *Information Flow* annotations of the Access Analysis. This metamodel is presented in Figure 5.1. This metamodel consists of a root metaclass *Annotations* containing all annotations. The abstract *Information Flow* metaclass presents a common superclass for all remaining *Information Flow* annotations. The metaclass *Information Flow* references one or more *DataSets* to represent the annotated *Security Characteristics*. The metaclass *Annotations* is defined to reference one or more *Information Flow* elements and a single *OperationSignature*. The three *Information Flow* subclasses reference separate *System Elements*. The *Information Flow Call* and *Information Flow Return* metaclasses define whether the *Call* or *Return* of the given *OperationSignature* is annotated. The *Information Flow Parameter* metaclass references a parameter of the *OperationSignature* to represent its annotation.

We define a transformation reading every *Information Flow* stereotype in a *Repository* model. In the Access Analysis, this stereotype references an *OperationSignature* and one or more *ParameterAndDataPairs*. Each *ParameterAndDataPair* references one or more *DataSet* and provides one or more *Strings*. The allowed *Strings* are *call*, *return* or the name of a parameter. For each *Information Flow* stereotype in the *Repository* model, the transformation extracts the referenced *OperationSignature*. Then, the transformation inspects each *ParameterAndDataPair*. For each *call*, *return* or *parameter name* provided as *Strings* in the *ParameterAndDataPairs*, we merge the respective *DataSets*. For each *call*, the transformation creates an *Information Flow Call* instance referencing the *Operation Signature* and the respective *DataSets*. For each *return*, the transformation creates an *Information Flow Return* instance referencing the *Operation Signature* and the respective *DataSets*. For each *Parameter* represented as *String* containing its name, the transformation resolves the corresponding instance of *Parameter* of the instance of the *Operation Signature*. The transformation then creates a *Information Flow Parameter* instance referencing the *Operation Signature*, the *Parameter* and the respective *DataSets*. The transformation then creates a file with the same name of the *Repository* model in the same folder but with the *accessanalysisannotations* file ending.

We execute this transformation for the JPMail and TravelPlanner *Repository* Model for the Access Analysis in our case study after applying the respective coupling with JOANA and CodeQL (Extended).

5.3.1.2 Configurations Metamodel

The *Configurations* metamodel consists of the four metaclasses *Configurations*, *Configuration*, *FullyImplicitConfiguration*, *HybridConfiguration* and *SingleElementConfiguration*. The *Configurations* metaclass captures all available configurations for a single system. The abstract *Configuration* metaclass describes a common superclass for all remaining configuration elements. The *FullyImplicitConfiguration* metaclass describes a *Configuration*, which only consists of input models of an analysis. Therefore, the *FullyImplicitConfiguration* metaclass references one or more *EObjects* to target the root elements of each (meta)model to be

used in a configuration. In our evaluation, the *FullyImplicitConfiguration* of the Access Analysis references the root elements of the *Repository Model* or *Deployment Model* (System Elements), *Confidentiality4CBSE Model* (Security Characteristics) and the *Annotations Model* described in Section 5.3.1.1. We create an instance of a *Configuration* in each coupling while referencing the *Annotations* element manually, as these are only used for the automated coverage evaluation. For the DFA-Ext, the *FullyImplicitConfiguration* references the root elements of the *System Model*, the *Repository Model*, *Deployment Model*, *Usage Model* (System Models), the *DataDictionary* (*Security Characteristics*), the *NodeCharacteristics Model* and the *ParameterAnnotations Model* (Annotations).

The *SingleElementConfiguration* references a *Configuration* element containing all described elements in the reference metamodels. We do not have such a configuration in our case study.

The *HybridConfiguration* references a *Main Configuration Element* used for identifying a configuration. In our case study, these are *Query* of *CodeQL* and *EntryPoint* of *JOANA*. The *HybridConfiguration* references one or more *EObjects* called *AdditionalInput*. Besides the *Query* and *EntryPoint*, *CodeQL* and *JOANA* require the source code as input. This is why we reference the *JavaRoot* of the respective case.

5.3.2 Correspondence Metamodels

For the coupling approach, we must enable the technical resolution between the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* and *Annotated Architectural Model* in the coupling process. This resolution can be performed by using a unique identifier, such as a class's fully qualified path, or by using specific metamodels that capture correspondences between metaclasses, so-called correspondence (meta)models (see Section 2.1). However, in an instance of the correspondence metamodel, the same model elements can be contained in different correspondences. We will discuss such correspondences later in this section. We, therefore, use correspondence (meta)models to support the automated evaluation of the *Coverage of Integration Conditions*. The correspondences are described on the metamodel level and are instantiated when performing transformations in the coupling process. Talcott et al. [45] describe the *Source Code Analysis Result* as an abstraction of the *Annotated Source Code*. In our coupling approach, we require the *Source Code Analysis Result* to contain counter-examples [35]. As described in Section 5.2.3, we created the *Source Code Analysis Result* to contain identifications of the elements of the *Annotated Source Code* to reflect the information in the actual representation rather than using references. If we would use references from the *Source Code Analysis Result* to the *Annotated Source Code*, e.g., in *JOANA* to *Parameters*, *EntryPoints* or *Levels*, the correspondence models would be mostly trivial, i.e., both sides of a correspondence contain the same element.

For the evaluation, we provide correspondence (meta)models between the input (meta)models of each analysis tuple, i.e., Access Analysis and CodeQL, Access Analysis and JOANA, DFA-Ext and CodeQL, and DFA-Ext and JOANA. The correspondences between the *Annotated Source Code* and the *Source Code Analysis Result* metamodels of the source code analyses in

the *Source Code Analysis* step and between the metamodels for the *Source Code Analysis Result*, the *Annotated Source Code* and the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* in the *Implementation Value Resolution* step have to be provided only once for each analysis as they are not specific for the coupling with an architectural analysis.

In this section, we will exemplarily detail the correspondence (meta)models for the coupling of the Access Analysis [28] and *JOANA*. The other correspondence metamodels and their instances created in the evaluation are structured similarly and can be found in our replication package [34].

5.3.2.1 Correspondence Metamodel for PCM and Java

The Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext both use the PCM as ADL while CodeQL and *JOANA* both analyze Java source code. Instead of defining the correspondences between the system elements for every combination of analyses, we define a correspondence metamodel for PCM and the Java metamodel separately. The correspondences are listed in Table 5.9. This approach is reasonable as providing correspondences for the system elements and correspondences for elements for analyzing a quality property, such as information flow security, increases the modularity of the metamodels as proposed by Heinrich et al. [20].

The correspondences between the PCM and our Java metamodel are created analog to the mapping between the PCM and Java used by Kramer et al. [27]. Here, a *BasicComponent* or a *CompositeDataType* corresponds to a *Class* in Java as captured in the *BasicComponent2Class* or *CompositeDataType2Class* correspondences, respectively. *OperationProvidedRole* connects a *OperationSignature* to a *RepositoryComponent* through the *OperationInterface*. This defines that the *RepositoryComponent* provides the service captured by the *OperationSignature*. We, therefore, correspond a *OperationProvidedRole* and a *OperationSignature* to a *Method* of a *Class* to which the *RepositoryComponent* corresponds. For corresponding the parameters in the services, we correspond the *OperationProvidedRole*, *OperationSignature* and contained *Parameter* to a *Parameter* in a *Method* in a *Class* in our Java metamodel. Containing only a *Method* or *Parameter* of our Java metamodel is possible because these elements are uniquely identifiable. In the PCM, however, we have to identify the *Parameter* and *OperationSignature* provided by a *RepositoryComponent* through the *OperationProvidedRole*. We cannot provide any correspondence for *Fields* in Java because the PCM does not contain a semantically corresponding element for them.

5.3.2.2 Correspondences for the Access Analysis and JOANA

We now detail the correspondence metamodels for the example case of the Access Analysis and *JOANA*. The other correspondence models are created similarly and can be found in our replication package [34].

Correspondence Metaclass	PCM Metaclasses	Java Metaclasses
BasicComponent2Class	BasicComponent	Class
CompositeDataType2Class	CompositeDataType	Class
ProvidedOperationSignature2Method	OperationProvidedRole, OperationSignature	Method
PCMParameter2JavaParameter	OperationProvidedRole, Parameter	Parameter

Table 5.9: Correspondences between Elements of the Palladio Component Model and the Java Metamodel

Correspondence Metaclass	Access Analysis Metaclasses	JOANA Metaclasses
ConfigurationCorrespondence	FullyImplicitConfiguration	HybridConfiguration
DataSetLevelCorrespondence	DataSet	Level

Table 5.10: Correspondences between Elements of the Access Analysis Confidentiality Specifications and *JOANA*.

Correspondences for the Input Metamodels of the Access Analysis and *JOANA* We capture the correspondences between the input metamodels of the Access Analysis and *JOANA* as listed in Table 5.10. The correspondences for the *System Elementare* already defined in the correspondence metamodel for the PCM and *JOANA* explained previously. We, therefore, require correspondences for the *Configuration* and the *Security Characteristics*. In our correspondence models, we use the supporting *Configuration* metaclasses described in Section 5.3.1.2 to create the correspondences for *Configurations*. The Access Analysis uses its input models as configurations. The input models required for information flow-related specifications are the *Repository* model of the PCM and the *ConfidentialitySpecification* model.

The *Repository* model contains the *System Elements* and the *Information Flow* stereotypes. The *ConfidentialitySpecification* model contains the *Security Characteristics* that are annotated. The root elements of these metamodels are the *Repository* and the *ConfidentialitySpecification*, respectively. This is why we use a *FullyImplicitConfiguration* as metaclass to represent the configuration (see Section 5.3.1.2). In addition, we supply the *Annotations* model to evaluate the coverage of the ICs to this configuration. *JOANA* uses *EntryPoints* for identification of a configuration (see Section 3.6.2). However, running *JOANA* also requires the Java model to be analyzed, resulting in a *HybridConfiguration* with an *EntryPoint* as *MainConfigurationElement* and the Java model as *AdditionalInput*. We, therefore, define a *ConfigurationCorrespondence* to provide correspondences between the *FullyImplicitConfiguration* of the Access Analysis and the *HybridConfiguration* of *JOANA*. The security characteristic in the coupling scenario of the Access Analysis and *JOANA* is the *DataSet* annotated by the *Information Flow* stereotype. We correspond the *DataSet* to *Levels* in *JOANA* as *Adversaries* in the Access Analysis may only access information in certain data sets. Therefore, we define a *DataSetLevelCorrespondence* between *DataSet* and *Level*. Potentially, we could also create correspondences between the *StereotypeApplication* or our introduced *Information Flow* metaclasses (see Section 5.3.1.1) capturing information flows in the Access Analysis and the *Sources* and *Sinks* of *JOANA*. However, we do not require this information due to the structures and assumptions stated in our paper about the coupling of architectural analyses and source code analyses using information flow information [35].

5.3.2.3 Correspondences for the Annotated Source Code and Source Code Analysis Result of *JOANA*

The correspondences between the *Annotated Source Code* and *Source Code Analysis Result* of *JOANA* are presented in Table 5.11. For representing the correspondences between the

Correspondence Element	JOANA Input Metamodel Metaclasses	JOANA Output Metamodel Metaclasses
EntryPointCorrespondence	HybridConfiguration	EntryPoint_SCAR
LevelCorrespondence	Level	Level_SCAR
ParameterCorrespondence	Parameter	Parameter_SCAR
FieldCorrespondence	Field	Field_SCAR

Table 5.11: Correspondences between Elements of the Input Metamodel of *JOANA* and its Output Metamodel

configurations, we create the *EntryPointCorrespondence* metaclass. *EntryPointCorrespondence* corresponds the *HybridConfiguration* metaclass for the input metamodel of *JOANA* to the *EntryPoint_SCAR* metaclass in the *Source Code Analysis Result*. The *LevelCorrespondence* corresponds a *Level* metaclass in the *Annotated Source Code* of *JOANA* to a *Level_SCAR* metaclass in the *Source Code Analysis Result* metamodel. The *ParameterCorrespondence* corresponds a *Parameter* metaclass of the Java metamodel to a *Parameter_SCAR* metaclass in the *Source Code Analysis Result* metamodel. The *FieldCorrespondence* corresponds a *Field* metaclass of the Java metamodel to a *Field_SCAR* metaclass in the *Source Code Analysis Result* metamodel.

5.3.2.4 Correspondences for the Annotated Source Code, Source Code Analysis Result and Resolved Implementation Values Model of *JOANA*

The ICs describe that the security characteristic of data in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* has to exist in the *Annotated Source Code*. The *System Elements* and *Configurations* must be contained in a correspondence to the *Source Code Analysis Result*. We, therefore, provide correspondences between the input metamodel and output metamodel of *JOANA* and the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* as shown in Table 5.12.

The *EntryPointCorrespondence_ResolvedImplementationValues* corresponds the *EntryPoint_SCAR* metaclass from the output metamodel of *JOANA* with the *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* metaclass of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* metamodel. The *ParameterCorrespondence_ResolvedImplementationValues* corresponds the *Parameter_SCAR* from the output metamodel of *JOANA* with the *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* metaclass of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*. In contrast to the prior correspondences, the *LevelCorrespondence* corresponds a *Level* from the *Annotated Source Code* metamodel of *JOANA* with the *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* to ensure corresponding values of *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* to those existing in the *Annotated Source Code*.

5.3.3 Creating the Automated Coverage Tests

We automated our coverage evaluation [35] by designing automated tests representing the calculation of $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC_i)$. These tests do not test the implementation of the coupling but rather test whether the correspondences formulated in a *correspondence conditions* or the constraints formulated in a *constraint condition* hold, i.e., whether the required references exist). For this purpose, the test functions inspect the input and output (meta)models of the analyses and the correspondence models created in the coupling process.

To design the test functions, we apply correspondence (meta)models and our formalization of the ICs in Section 4.3. We evaluate each IC for a successfully established coupling. Determining $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC_i)$ is automated by a unit test for the Java language. The selection whether $hold_{IC}^{corr}$ or $hold_{IC}^{const}$ is applied is done by us manually as we are aware of whether

Correspondence Element	JOANA Metaclass	JOANA Resolved Implementation Values Model Metaclass
EntryPointCorrespondence_ResolvedImplementationValues	EntryPoint_SCAR	EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues
ParameterCorrespondence_ResolvedImplementationValues	Parameter_SCAR	Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues
LevelCorrespondence_ResolvedImplementationValues	Level	Level_ResolvedImplementationValues

Table 5.12: Correspondences between Elements of the Palladio Component Model and the Java Metamodel

the tested condition is a constraint condition or correspondence condition. As already mentioned in Section 5.1, we create the unit tests conforming to the ICs described in our article [35] rather than using the refined versions of the ICs presented. The reason for this is that we want to maintain consistency between the description in the article and our evaluation. However, the unit tests in our replication package [34] show the same structures in the original conditions and the refined conditions.

We design for each IC one test that determines whether a IC holds on the metamodel and one test to decide whether or not it holds on the model level. In these tests, we evaluate the ICs by examining the contents of the input and output models and correspondence models as defined in the evaluation of our coupling approach [35]. These tests mostly use functionality independent of the metamodels to calculate $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, ICi)$ and replace the metamodels and models in the coupling. In some tests, adapting the test to the specific metamodels was necessary for technical reasons. We will discuss these cases explicitly in the definition of the test functionality.

We use the EMF for representing our (meta)models. We use the following contents of EMF (meta)models in creating our test functionality: Metaclasses (*EClass*), instances of these classes (*EObjects*), and references for which we consider *Crossreferences* and *Containments*. Every functionality in our automated tests is described based on these contents.

As presented in Section 4.3, we use a set-theoretic approach to describe the ICs, for which we have to provide functionality independent of the specific (meta)models of the analyses in the coupling. In our set-theoretic formalization, we define the metamodels as sets of their metaclasses and models as sets of instances of these metaclasses.

In our ICs, we also define subsets of metaclasses or instances for a particular purpose, e.g., a set capturing all system elements $delta_A^{cs} \in \Delta_A^{cs}$ which are annotated by the Security Characteristic of the coupling scenario s_A^{cs} . For all sets in our ICs, we provide functions calculating them. The functions to provide the metaclasses or instances in the sets are named according to the formalized description of the reference metamodels and their metaclasses, e.g., with *delta* (δ) for system elements, *s* for *Security Characteristics* or *cfg* for *Configurations*. The corresponding model is denoted with the name of the subscript in the formalization, e.g., *A* for the architectural input model or *R* for the *Source Code Analysis Result*. The name of the function also contains either *Metamodel* or *Model* to denote whether the calculated set contains the metaclasses or the instances. We calculate these sets by providing functionality based on *EClasses* and *EObjects*. Later in this section, we present examples of calculating the different sets in the ICs. All calculations are provided in the replication package [34] in the class *IntegrationConditionSetCalculator.java*.

We do not provide a mechanism to assign metaclasses of the reference metamodels to metaclasses of the input and output (meta)models of the analyses. However, for calculating the sets described in Section 4.3, this information is necessary for identifying the relevant metaclasses, especially in the *Annotated Architectural Model* and the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*. This is why we define single metaclasses or sets of metaclasses of the input and output metamodels mapping to metaclasses of the reference metamodels relevant for

the coupling. For the Access Analysis, the set Δ_A^{cs} contains the *EClass Parameter*, s_A^{cs} contains the *EClass DataSet* and CFG_A^{cs} contains *FullyImplicitConfiguration*.

For calculating sets capturing elements in a correspondence, we provide functions in the *CorrespondenceResolutionUtil.java* to obtain corresponding elements. The *getCorrespondingElements_Metamodel* function searches metaclasses (*EClass*) corresponding to the *EClass* given in the *targetMetaclass* parameter based on correspondences in the provided root element of a correspondence model provided in the *correspondences* parameter. The *getCorrespondingElements_Model* function searches all *EObjects* corresponding to the *EObject* provided in the *targetInstance* parameter from correspondences in the provided root element of a correspondence model provided in the *correspondences* parameter. There is also a *getCorrespondingElements_Model_Multi* that uses a set of *EObjects* identifying an element to search for corresponding *EObjects* from correspondences in the provided root element of a correspondence model supplied in the *correspondences* parameter.

All functions are created based on the following assumptions: (1) the root element of the correspondences only contains correspondences, and (2) every correspondence contains two references to instances of metaclasses identifying elements in the different models. Either this identification refers to a single instance of a metaclass directly in one target model or an instance of a metaclass identifying some element by referencing multiple other metaclasses. An example of a metaclass referencing other metaclasses for identification is presented by the *PCMParameter2JavaParameter* correspondence where the PCM parameter is identified by referencing a *OperationProvidedRole*, a *OperationSignature* and a *Parameter*. The *getCorrespondingElements_Metamodel* function calculates corresponding *EClasses* based on the assumption that the metaclasses correspond if correspondences between their objects exist.

For determining the (transitive) *reachability* described for our reference metamodel [35], we provide the functions *collectAllReachableEClasses* and *collectAllReachableEObjects*, each using an *EClass* or respectively an *EObject* as input. *collectAllReachableEClasses* calculates for an *EClass* all transitive reachable other *EClasses* by inspecting each *Crossreference* or *Containment* relation iteratively. Again, their cross-referenced or contained elements are collected for each cross-referenced or contained *EClass*. We provide an analog function for *EObjects* determining every *reachable EObject* from it.

Based on these functions and the (meta)models, we calculate the sets in the formalization of the ICs (see Section 4.3 as described in the following). Every relevant element and set contains the *cs* (coupling scenario) denotation. The functions are named in the following scheme *calculate_X_cs_Y_Z*. *X* denotes the sets of metaclasses of the reference metamodels, i.e., *An* (*Annotations*), *Delta* (*System Elements*), *S* (*Security Characteristics*) or *CFG* (*Configuration*). *Y* in this naming scheme denotes the respective (meta)model in the coupling, i.e., *Annotated Architectural Model (A)*, *Annotated Source Code (C)*, *Source Code Analysis Result (R)* or *Resolved Implementation Values Model (V)*. *Z* in this naming scheme denotes whether the set contains metaclasses (*Metamodel*) or instances (*Model*).

In the following, we describe the design of the test functions for *correspondence conditions* and *constraint conditions*

5.3.3.1 Creating Tests for Correspondence Conditions

Correspondence conditions induce correspondences between metaclasses or their instances of the input model and the output model of a process step. The corresponding metaclasses or their instances in the output (meta)model are then assigned to a new set. In the **IC1** on the metamodel level, for instance, the metaclasses of *Security Characteristics* (s_C) in the *Annotated Source Code* (output metamodel) are assigned to S_C^{cs} when they correspond to s_A^{cs} in the *Annotated Architectural Model* (input (meta)model). The only metaclass of all *Security Characteristics* (S_C) in *JOANA* corresponding to *DataSet (Security Characteristic)* of the coupling scenario s_A^{cs} is *Level* ($s_C \in S_C$). Thus, we must provide a set S_C^{cs} containing *Level*.

For this purpose, most formalizations of correspondence conditions contain iterations over elements in certain sets in the output (meta)model (\forall/\exists) and iterations over elements in certain sets in the input (\forall/\exists) and conditions about correspondences between these elements or necessary references. If the conditions hold, the elements are assigned to certain sets. We realize these conditions in the Java tests for the input metamodel and output metamodel level as follows. For the metamodels, each function requires the following input: (a) the set of metaclasses in the input metamodel affected by the IC. (b) The root element of the correspondence model where the relevant correspondences can be found for the process step. For the *correspondence conditions* captured for the *Implementation Value Resolution*, we also require the sets of metaclasses of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* of relevance because we have to make sure that only these metaclasses are captured (see Section 4.3).

With this input, we perform the following steps to calculate the sets of *EClasses* of the *correspondence conditions* on the metamodel level:

1. (Optional) If the metaclasses of the input metamodel are constrained, filter the metaclasses for which the constraint holds
2. Iterate over all remaining metaclasses of the input metamodel and fetch all corresponding metaclasses (*getCorrespondingElements_Metamodel*)
3. Collect all obtained metaclasses in a new set of the type *EClass*
4. Return the newly created set

The newly created set is empty if there is no correspondence for the metaclass instances.

On the instance level, we calculate the set based on all required sets of the relevant prior ICs. Therefore, we use the following input in the respective functions:

(a) The set of model elements of the input model affected by the target IC. (b) The set of metaclasses from the output metamodel affected by the target IC. (c) The root of the output model that is relevant for calculating the set of instances, e.g., when calculating S_R^{cs} for the *Source Code Analysis Result* of *JOANA*, we require the root of the *Source Code Analysis Result* model. (d) The root of the correspondence model where the relevant correspondences can be found for the process step, e.g., when calculating S_R^{cs} , we have to inspect the correspondences in the *ScarCorrespondence* model of for *JOANA*. For the *correspondence conditions* captured

for the *Implementation Value Resolution*, we also require the sets of metaclasses of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* of relevance because we have to make sure that only these metaclasses are captured (see Section 4.3).

With this input, we perform the following steps to calculate the sets of *EObjects* of the *correspondence conditions* on the model level:

1. Calculate for all metaclasses of the output metamodel affected by the target IC, i.e., input (b), the instance from the root obtained in input (c).
2. Calculate for all the instances of step (1) the corresponding instances in the input model by inspecting the correspondences in the correspondence model provided captured in (d).
3. Create a set with those instances calculated in step (1), corresponding to the elements in the input model provided in (a).
4. Return the newly created set

If the root representing the output of the process step contains no instances of the inspected metaclasses in (b) or none of these instances corresponds to those in the input model, the newly created set is empty.

We can now define the Java functionality for *hold(A, cond)* based on these sets. We create for every IC two tests inspecting whether the condition holds on the metamodel and model level. Every *correspondence condition* for the *Analyses Input Model Consistency* and *Source Code Analysis*, i.e., **IC1**, **IC2**, **IC5** and **IC7**, that the correspondences exist for at least one metaclass or its instance respectively. For these ICs, we calculate the resulting set behind the implication symbol (\Rightarrow) in Section 4.3, i.e., we collect metaclasses or their instances in the respective sets with the functionality described before. We replace the existence with the condition that the resulting set in the IC (set behind the implication symbol (\Rightarrow)) must not be empty. With this approach, checking whether at least one correspondence exists can be realized by calculating the sets of the output metaclasses or their instances specified by the ICs and then checking whether these sets are not empty. To evaluate IC for the *Analyses Input Model Consistency* and *Source Code Analysis* on the metamodel level, we perform the following steps:

1. The test function obtains all sets required for the function's input to calculate the resulting sets of metaclasses in the IC.
2. The sets with corresponding metaclasses resulting from the IC are calculated by executing the function with the sets obtained in (1.).
3. The Java Unit Test uses an assertion to check whether the condition that the sets of (2.) are not empty

On the model level, this procedure is performed with the functions for calculating the sets of the instances (*EObjects*) of the respective metaclasses. Therefore, the Java Unit Test succeeds when the IC holds, i.e., there exists a corresponding metaclass or, respectively, their instances to the *Annotated Architectural Model* and fails otherwise.

The test design for the *correspondence conditions* for the *Integration* differs, i.e., **IC8** and **IC9**, because these ICs require that all metaclasses or instance of the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* correspond to the other (meta)models rather than needing only one correspondence. We perform the following steps for evaluating $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, ICi)$ for **IC8** and **IC9**:

1. We first define the sets of metaclasses affected by **IC8** and **IC9**, i.e., Δ_V^{cs} , CFG_V^{cs} and S_V^{cs} . For a case comprising *JOANA*, for instance, we define Δ_V^{cs} for **IC8** to contain *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* and CFG_V^{cs} to contain *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues*. For **IC9** we define S_V^{cs} to contain *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues*.
2. The sets of metaclasses in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model* corresponding to other metaclasses of the *Annotated Source Code* or *Source Code Analysis Result* as described by **IC8** and **IC9** are calculated.
3. For every *Resolved Implementation Value*, its reachable instances are calculated. For all reachable instances, elements of either **IC8** or **IC9** defined in (1.) are searched and their metaclasses are captured in the process. For **IC8**, there must exist reachable instances of *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* and an instance of the metaclass *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues*. For **IC9**, reachable instances of *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* must exist.
4. If in (3.) the described instances are not found and no metaclass captured, $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, ICi)$ does not hold because the condition does not hold for all instances.
5. If all described instances are found in (3.), it is checked whether their metaclasses are contained in the sets calculated in (2.). If not all metaclasses are contained in the sets calculated in (2.), then not all metaclasses in all *Resolved Implementation Value* have a correspondence as described in **IC8** or **IC9**, respectively.

On the model level, this procedure is performed with the functions for calculating the sets of the instances (*EObjects*) of the respective metaclasses. In addition, step (5.) is performed based on the instances rather than metaclasses. Therefore, the Java Unit Test succeeds when the IC holds, i.e., there exists a corresponding metaclass or, respectively, their instances for all *Resolved Implementation Value* to the *Annotated Architectural Model* and fails otherwise.

5.3.3.2 Creating Tests for Constraint Conditions

Calculating the *constraint condition* cannot be performed in such a uniform process as described for *correspondence conditions* in Section 5.3.3.2. Each *constraint condition* on the metamodel level requires references from metaclasses mapping to elements of the reference metamodels to other metaclasses from the sets defined in the *constraint conditions*. We formalized the required references and correspondences between the metaclasses. In every Java Unit test, we evaluate whether the references exist by calculating the respective metaclasses and the respective sets of metaclasses from the *correspondence conditions*.

Integration Condition 3 For **IC3**, we manually provide the metaclasses of annotations in the *Annotated Source Code* An_C . In *JOANA* these are *Source* and *Sink*. The test function then calculates S_C^{cs} , CFG_C^{cs} and Δ_C^{cs} . The test function calculates all metaclasses in An_C that reach metaclasses of S_C^{cs} and Δ_C^{cs} by the function *calculate_An_cs_C_Metamodel*. If a metaclass of an annotation reaches a metaclass in S_C^{cs} and Δ_C^{cs} , the test function stores this metaclass in a set An_C^{cs} . The test function removes all metaclasses in An_C^{cs} that are not reached by a metaclass in CFG_C^{cs} and returns the remaining set. **IC3** requires only one metaclass of an annotation that reaches metaclasses in the sets S_C^{cs} , CFG_C^{cs} and Δ_C^{cs} . Therefore, the test function checks whether this set is empty. If the set is empty, the test fails because there is no annotation conforming to our *constraint condition*, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC3)$ returns *false* on the metamodel level. Otherwise, the test succeeds, and $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC3)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level. For evaluating the model level, the test function calculates the sets of instances $\underline{S_C^{cs}}$, $\underline{CFG_C^{cs}}$ and $\underline{\Delta_C^{cs}}$. Then, all instances of the metaclasses in An_C^{cs} are calculated. Based on these sets, the test function calculates the set $\underline{An_C^{cs}}$ that contains instances of An_C^{cs} that reach instances in the sets $\underline{S_C^{cs}}$ and $\underline{\Delta_C^{cs}}$. Then the test function removes all instances from $\underline{An_C^{cs}}$ that are not reached by an instance $\underline{CFG_C^{cs}}$ and returns the remaining set. We only require one annotation $\underline{\alpha_C^{cs}}$ according to **IC3** that reaches instances of the sets $\underline{S_C^{cs}}$, $\underline{CFG_C^{cs}}$ and $\underline{\Delta_C^{cs}}$. Therefore, the test function examines whether $\underline{An_C^{cs}}$ is empty. If $\underline{An_C^{cs}}$ is empty, the test function fails as there is not one annotation annotating an instance of a *Security Characteristic* in $\underline{S_C^{cs}}$ to an *System Element* in $\underline{\Delta_C^{cs}}$ and that is used in a *Configuration* $\underline{CFG_C^{cs}}$, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC3)$ returns *false* on the model level. Otherwise, the test succeeds and $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC3)$ returns *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 4 For **IC4**, we manually provide the metaclasses Pol_C identified as policy in the input metamodel of the *Annotated Source Code*, i.e., *Lattice* for *JOANA*. Due to our generalized structure of the *Configurations*, we cannot consider the *EClasses* directly. Therefore, we use the instances, extracting all metaclasses *EClass* and using the reference of the *EObjects* to reconstruct the references of the *EClass*. This is possible as an *EObject* can only have a reference to another *EObject* if their *EClasses* describe this reference to the fitting other *EClass*. Therefore, the test function iterates over all instances (*EObjects*) and extracts their metaclass *EClass*. We also formulate all constraints on the *EClass* level. With the marked metaclasses for Pol_C , the test function then iterates over all CFG_C^{cs} and all S_C^{cs} so that only security policies in configurations that describe Security Characteristics corresponding to those of the coupling scenario are tested. If the metaclass of the correspondence $cfg_C^{cs} \in CFG_C^{cs}$ references a metaclass of the security characteristics in S_C^{cs} , then the test function inspects whether also the security policy in this configuration references this metaclass of the security characteristic. If there is a metaclass of the security characteristic in S_C^{cs} that is not referenced by the respective policy, then $hold_{IF}(E, IC4)$ returns *false* and *true* otherwise.

The same process is performed for all instances of the *Security Policies*, *Configurations* and *Security Characteristics*. Therefore, the test function uses a similar implementation but uses the instances (*EObjects*) instead of *EClasses*. The test function first iterates over all instances of the metaclasses in Pol_C to determine whether they are reachable by the *Configuration* in

$cfg_C^{cs} \in CFG_C^{cs}$. If the instance of the security policy $pol_C \in Pol_C$ is reachable by cfg_C^{cs} , the test function iterates over all instances captured in S_C^{cs} . If these instances are reachable by cfg_C^{cs} , the test function verifies if they are also reachable by pol_C . The test function fails if there is one instance in S_C^{cs} that is reachable by cfg_C^{cs} but not by pol_C , i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC4)$ returns *false*. Otherwise the test function succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC4)$ returns *true*.

Integration Condition 6 For the evaluation of **IC6**, the test function performs the following steps: On the metamodel level, the test function first extracts all instances of *Result Entry Elements*. For this extraction, we provide the respective metaclasses manually as they are not otherwise contained in correspondences or similar. For the *Source Code Analysis Result* model of *JOANA*, the metaclasses are *Source* and *Sink*. If there exists no instances, the test fails, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC6)$ returns *false*. The test function then calculates the sets Δ_R^{cs} and S_R^{cs} . The metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* references technically the generic *SystemElement* metaclass. However, in Δ_R^{cs} , only the metaclasses *Parameter_SCAR* and *Field_SCAR* (subclasses of this metaclass) are contained. Therefore, checking the condition purely on the metamodel level would result in wrong statements due to technical reasons. Therefore, the test function extracts for each instance of *Source* or *Sink* all reachable instances and retrieves their metaclasses. The test function then checks whether the Δ_R^{cs} comprises one of the reachable metaclasses. The same procedure is also performed for S_R^{cs} . If these checks return true, the test succeeds as this IC only requires the existence of such a combination of elements, meaning that $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC6)$ returns *true*. If no such instance exists, the test fails, meaning $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC6)$ returns *false*. In our case study, there exist *Sources* and *Sinks* referencing the metaclasses *Level_SCAR* and *Parameter_SCAR* corresponding to *Level* and *Parameter* in the *Annotated Source Code* respectively. Therefore, the test succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC6)$ returns *true* for the metamodel level. Otherwise, the test fails, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC6)$ returns *false* for the metamodel level.

On the instance level, a similar implementation is performed. However, instead of comparing the *EClasses* of the elements reachable by the ICs, the instances are compared. Similarly, if a instance of the *ResultEntryElements*, i.e., *Source* and *Sink* for *JOANA*, reaches instances of the sets Δ_R^{cs} and S_R^{cs} , the test succeeds. This success means that $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC6)$ returns *true* on the model level. If there exists no instance of *ResultEntryElements* or there exists no *ResultEntryElement* reaching instances of the sets Δ_R^{cs} and S_R^{cs} , the test fails, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC6)$ returns *false* on the model level.

Integration Condition 10 For evaluating **IC10**, the test function performs the following steps: The test function first calculates S_V and CFG_V . Then, the test function iterates over every instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue*. We have to manually define these elements, as *ResolvedImplementationValue* cannot be identified in another way. On the metamodel level, the test function calculates for each instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue* whether it reaches instances of the metaclasses in S_V and CFG_V , respectively. If an instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue* does not reach instances of the metaclasses in S_V and CFG_V , the test fails, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC10)$ returns *false*. For the metaclasses in S_V the test function calculates the corresponding metaclasses from S_C^{cs} . The test function uses the

existing correspondences from the instances of the metaclasses from S_V to the instances in S_C^{cs} (see Integration Condition 9). However, as the metaclass *HybridConfiguration* only references the metaclass *EObject*, we cannot resolve the types reachable by *EntryPoint*, which is only given on the instance level. Therefore, the test function calculates for the instances of \underline{CFG}_V and their corresponding instances in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} . For the instance in \underline{CFG}_V , there are no direct correspondences to \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} formulated in the ICs and comprised in the correspondence models. Therefore, the test function calculates for every instance in \underline{CFG}_V^{cs} the corresponding instances in \underline{CFG}_R^{cs} in the *Source Code Analysis Result*. For the calculated instances in \underline{CFG}_R^{cs} , the corresponding instances in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs} are calculated. For each of these calculated instances of the configuration $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ the test function parses the instance to the *HybridConfiguration* and retrieves the specific instance of *MainConfigurationElement*, e.g., *EntryPoint* in *JOANA*. The test function then retrieves the metaclass of this instance. With this metaclass, we retrieved a corresponding metaclass \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} for \underline{cfg}_V with which the test function can determine whether it reaches a metaclass s_C^{cs} corresponding to metaclass s_V^{cs} in the *Resolved Implementation Value*. Technically, as we recheck this on the metaclass level for each instance, the configuration may only reach an instance of the metaclass if the metaclasses in the configuration also reach such an element. If the instance of the configuration $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ does not reach an instance of the metaclass captured in S_C^{cs} corresponding to the metaclass in S_V^{cs} , the test fails, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC10)$ returns *false*. Otherwise, the test succeeds because the conditions hold for every *Resolved Implementation Value*, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC10)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

The test function performs a similar procedure on the model level but considers the instances rather than the metaclasses. Therefore, the test function first calculates for each instance of the S_V^{cs} the corresponding instance $\underline{s}_C^{cs} \in \underline{S}_C^{cs}$. It then inspects whether the configuration $\underline{cfg}_C^{cs} \in \underline{CFG}_C^{cs}$ reaches the calculated instance \underline{s}_C^{cs} . If the instance of the configuration \underline{cfg}_C^{cs} does not reach \underline{s}_C^{cs} , the test fails, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC10)$ returns *false*. Otherwise, the test succeeds because the conditions hold for every *Resolved Implementation Value*, i.e., $hold_{IC}(A_{IC}, IC10)$ returns *true* on the model level.

5.3.4 Evaluation Results for the Case AccessAnalysis, JOANA and JPMail

We now present the results of our Java Unit Tests for the case comprising the coupling of the Access Analysis and *JOANA* and their application on *JPMail*. Please refer to our replication package [34] to replicate the results of the other cases.

Integration Condition 1 We apply our test function for **IC1** on the metamodel and model level. For evaluating **IC1** on the metamodel level, the test function first calculates the set S_C^{cs} . S_C^{cs} contains the metaclass *Level* of *JOANA* as it corresponds to *DataSet* of the Access Analysis. The test function succeeds because S_C^{cs} is not empty, indicating that $hold_{IC}(E, TC1)$ evaluates to *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, the test function calculates all instances of the metaclasses of S_C^{cs} . This results in the set S_C^{cs} to contain the *Levels High* and *Low*. The test function succeeds because S_C^{cs} is not empty, indicating that $hold_{IC}(E, TC1)$ evaluates to *true* on the metamodel level.

Integration Condition 2 We apply our test function for **IC2** on the metamodel and model level. For evaluating **IC2** on the metamodel level, the test function first calculates the set Δ_C^{cs} and CFG_C^{cs} by using the provided sets Δ_A^{cs} and CFG_A^{cs} respectively. Δ_C^{cs} contains the metaclass *Parameter* in a *Method* of a *Class* in the Java metamodel corresponding to a metaclass *Parameter* of a *OperationSignature* in a *OperationProvidedRole* in the PCM. CFG_C^{cs} contains the metaclass *HybridConfiguration*, containing the *MainConfigurationElement EntryPoint*, corresponding to the metaclass *FullyImplicitConfiguration* of the Access Analysis. The test function succeeds because Δ_C^{cs} and CFG_A^{cs} are not empty, indicating that $hold_{IC}(E, TC1)$ evaluates to *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, the test function calculates all instances of the metaclasses of Δ_C^{cs} and CFG_C^{cs} corresponding to instances in Δ_A^{cs} and CFG_A^{cs} respectively. This results for Δ_C^{cs} containing, among others, the parameters *body* and *header* in the java methods *dispatchMail*. These parameters correspond to the parameters *body* and *headers* in the *OperationSignature dispatchMail*, which are annotated by instances in the An_C^{cs} . We also calculate all instances of *Configurations* CFG_C^{cs} in the *Annotated Source Code* that correspond to an instance of the configuration CFG_A^{cs} that are referenced by instances of *InformationFlow* in An_A^{cs} . CFG_C^{cs} contains for the Access Analysis and JPMail, e.g., the *HybridConfiguration* referencing an instance of *EntryPoint* with the *Tag* defined as 1. The test function succeeds because Δ_C^{cs} and CFG_A^{cs} are not empty, indicating that $hold_{IC}(E, TC1)$ evaluates to *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 3 We apply our test function for **IC3** on the metamodel and model level. For the Access Analysis and *JOANA* for JPMail, the set An_C^{cs} contains the metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* as both annotate *Level* from S_C^{cs} (see Integration Condition 1) to, among others, method *Parameters* from Δ_C^{cs} (see Integration Condition 2). In addition, the metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* are also reachable by an *EntryPoint* in the *HybridConfiguration* from CFG_C^{cs} (see Integration Conditions 2). Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC3)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, there exist instances of *Source* or *Sink*, annotating instances *High* and *Low* of the metaclass *Level* (see Integration Conditions 2) to, for instance, the parameters *body* and *header* in the Java methods *dispatchMail* of the classes *POP3* or *SMTP*. These annotations are reachable in a *HybridConfiguration* containing an *EntryPoint*, e.g., the one with the *Tag* 1. Therefore, the test function for the model level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC3)$ returns *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 4 We apply our test function for **IC4** on the metamodel and model level. On the metamodel level, the *Lattice* is the only *SecurityPolicy* in *JOANA*. Every *HybridConfiguration* of *JOANA* contains an *EntryPoint*. *EntryPoint* contains the *Lattice*. The set S_C^{cs} contains the metaclass *Level* (see Integration Condition 1). Each *EntryPoint* contains

instances of the metaclass *Level*. Every *Lattice* contains instances of *AllowedFlow*, which contain instances of the metaclass *Level*. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC4)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, every *HybridConfiguration* contains an instance of *EntryPoint* containing the instances *High* and *Low* of the metaclass *Level* (see Integration Condition 1). Every instance of a *Lattice* contains an instance of *AllowedFlow* referencing the instances *High* and *Low* of the metaclass *Level* to define that only *Low* classified data may flow to *High* classified data. In result, every instance of *Security Policy*, i.e., *Lattice*, uses all instances of S_C^{cs} . Therefore, the test function for the model level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC4)$ returns *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 5 We apply our test function for **IC5** on the metamodel and model level. The set Δ_R^{cs} contains the metaclass *Parameter_SCAR* because it is captured in a correspondence with the metaclass *Parameter*, contained in the set Δ_C^{cs} (see Integration Condition 3). Similarly, the set S_R^{cs} contains the metaclass *Level_SCAR* because it is captured in a correspondence with the metaclass *Level* contained in the set S_C^{cs} (see Integration Condition 1). In result, the sets Δ_R^{cs} and S_R^{cs} are not empty. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC5)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, Δ_R^{cs} contains, among others, the instances of the metaclass *Parameter_SCAR* identifying the *body* and *header* of the java methods *dispatchMail* in the classes *POP3* or *SMTP*, which correspond to to the instances *body* and *header* of the Java methods *dispatchMail* of the metaclass *Parameter* in the *Annotated Source Code*. The instances *body* and *header* of the Java methods *dispatchMail* of the metaclass *Parameter* are both contained in Δ_C^{cs} (see Integration Condition 3). Similarly, the set S_R^{cs} contains the instances *High* and *Low* of the metaclass *Level_SCAR*, which correspond to the instances *High* and *Low* of the metaclass *Level* in the *Annotated Source Code* respectively. The instances *High* and *Low* of the metaclass *Level* in the *Annotated Source Code* are both contained in the set S_C^{cs} . Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC5)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

Integration Condition 6 We apply our test function for **IC6** on the metamodel and model level. On the metamodel level the set Δ_R^{cs} contains the metaclass *Parameter_SCAR* and S_R^{cs} contains the metaclass *Level_SCAR* (see Integration Condition 5). We define the metaclasses *Source* and *Sink* in the *Source Code Analysis Result* of *JOANA* as *Result Entry Elements* *ree*. *Source* and *Sink* both reference either *Parameter_SCAR* or *Field_SCAR*. In addition, they both reference *Level_SCAR*. In our *Source Code Analysis Result* model, our test function finds instances of *Source* and *Sink* that reference instances of the metaclasses *Parameter_SCAR* and *Level_SCAR*. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC6)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, the set S_R^{cs} contains the instances *High* and *Low* of the metaclass *Level_SCAR*. Additionally, the set Δ_C^{cs} contains, among others, the instances of the metaclass *Parameter_SCAR* identifying the *body* and *header* of the java methods *dispatchMail* in the

classes *POP3* or *SMTP*. There exists, among others, a *Sink* in the *Source Code Analysis Result*, defining the instance $\underline{s}_R^{cs} \in \underline{S}_R^{cs}$ *Low* of the metaclass *Level_SCAR* for the instance $\underline{\delta}_R^{cs} \in \underline{\Delta}_C^{cs}$ *body* of the metaclass *Parameter_SCAR*, in the Java methods *dispatchMail* of the classes *POP3*. **IC6** only the existence of one such a *Result Entry Element*. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $\text{hold}_{IC}(E, IC6)$ returns *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 7 We apply our test function for **IC7** on the metamodel and model level. On the metamodel level, the test function calculates the set CFG_R^{cs} containing the metaclass *EntryPoint_SCAR* because there exist correspondences to instances of the metaclass *HybridConfiguration*, which are included in CFG_C^{cs} (see Integration Condition 3). As a result, the CFG_R^{cs} is not empty. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $\text{hold}_{IC}(E, IC7)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, the test function calculates CFG_R^{cs} which contains 17 instances of *EntryPoint_SCAR* which correspond to a *HybridConfiguration* in CFG_C^{cs} . In result, the CFG_R^{cs} is not empty. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $\text{hold}_{IC}(E, IC7)$ returns *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 8 We apply our test function for **IC8** on the metamodel and model level. On the metamodel level, the test function calculates the set CFG_V^{cs} containing the metaclass *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* and the set Δ_V^{cs} containing the metaclass *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues*. Each instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue* reaches an instance with a metaclass of the set CFG_V^{cs} and an instance with a metaclass of the set Δ_V^{cs} . The test function calculates corresponding metaclasses in the *Source Code Analysis Result* for these metaclasses. For the metaclass *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues*, the test function found correspondences to the metaclass *Parameter_SCAR*. For the metaclass *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues*, the test function found correspondences to the metaclass *EntryPoint_SCAR*. These correspondences have been found for every instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue*. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $\text{hold}_{IC}(E, IC8)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, the test function again calculates the set CFG_V^{cs} containing the metaclass *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* and the set Δ_V^{cs} containing the metaclass *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues*. Each instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue* reaches an instance with a metaclass of the set CFG_V^{cs} and an instance with a metaclass of the set Δ_V^{cs} . For the instances of these metaclasses, the test function then calculates corresponding instances in the *Source Code Analysis Result*. One example of an instance of *ResolvedImplementationValues* reaches an instance of *Parameter_ResolvedImplementationValues* that identifies the parameter *body* of the *dispatchMail* method in the class *POP3*. The test function calculates the corresponding *Parameter_SCAR* in the *Source Code Analysis Result* model (see Integration Condition 5). The same instance of *ResolvedImplementationValues* reaches an instance of *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* identifying the *EntryPoint* with the *Tag 1*. The test function calculates the corresponding *EntryPoint_SCAR* in the *Source Code Analysis Result* model, also identifying the *EntryPoint* with the *Tag 1*. The test function was able to find reachable instances contained in the sets CFG_V^{cs} and Δ_V^{cs} for each instance of

ResolvedImplementationValues. In addition, for all reachable instances of the metaclasses in the sets CFG_V^{cs} and Δ_V^{cs} from the instances of *ResolvedImplementationValue*, a corresponding instance could be found in CFG_R^{cs} and Δ_V^{cs} . Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC8)$ returns *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 9 We apply our test function for **IC9** on the metamodel and model level. The test function calculates the set S_V^{cs} containing the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* on the metamodel level. Each instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue* reaches an instance with a metaclass of the set S_V^{cs} . For these metaclasses, the test function then calculates corresponding metaclasses in the *Annotated Source Code*, i.e., the *JOANA* (meta)model. For the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues*, the test function found correspondences to the metaclass *Level* in the *JOANA* (meta)model. Because these correspondences have been found for every instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue*, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC9)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, the test function again calculates the set S_V^{cs} containing the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues*. Each instance of *ResolvedImplementationValue* reaches an instance *high* of the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues*, contained in the set S_V^{cs} . For this instance, the test function calculates corresponding instances in the *Annotated Source Code*. The instance *high* in each *ResolvedImplementationValue* corresponds to all instances of the metaclass *Level* in every *EntryPoint* in the *Annotated Source Code*. The test function found reachable instances of metaclasses in the set S_V^{cs} for each instance of the metaclass *ResolvedImplementationValues*. In addition, for all reachable instances of the metaclasses in the sets S_V^{cs} , i.e., *high* from the instance of *ResolvedImplementationValues*, a corresponding instance could be found contained in S_V^{cs} . Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC9)$ returns *true* on the model level.

Integration Condition 10 We apply our test function for **IC10** on the metamodel and model level. On the metamodel level, the test function inspects every instance of the metaclass *ResolvedImplementationValue* and calculates the reachable instances of the metaclasses captured in S_V^{cs} and CFG_V^{cs} . S_V^{cs} contains the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* (see Integration Condition 9) while CFG_V^{cs} contains the metaclass *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* (see Integration Condition 8). The test function then calculates corresponding instances in the *Annotated Source Code*. For the instance *high* of the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* in the *Resolved Implementation Values Model*, the test function calculates the corresponding metaclass *Level*. For the instances of the metaclasses *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues*, the test function calculates the corresponding instances in the *Annotated Source Code*. For the *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* identifying the *EntryPoint* with the *Tag* 1, for instance, the test function calculates the corresponding instance of the metaclass *EntryPoint_SCAR*. From this instance, the test function then calculates the *HybridConfiguration* containing the instance of *EntryPoint* with the *Tag* 1. The test function inspects whether the metaclasses of all reachable instances in this instance of *HybridConfiguration* contains the metaclass *Level* as this is the one corresponding to the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* in the *Resolved Implementation Values*

Model. The test function finds an instance with the metaclass *Level*, e.g., the *Level high* in the *EntryPoint* with the *Tag 1*, and therefore succeeds for this *Resolved Implementation Value*. The same result is obtained for every instance of *Resolved Implementation Value*. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC10)$ returns *true* on the metamodel level.

On the model level, the test function inspects every instance of the metaclass *ResolvedImplementationValue* and calculates the reachable instances of the metaclasses captured in S_V^{cs} and CFG_V^{cs} . S_V^{cs} contains the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* (see Integration Condition 9) while CFG_V^{cs} contains the metaclass *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* (see Integration Condition 8). An instance of *Resolved Implementation Values* reaches, for example, the instances *high* of the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* and the instance of *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* identifying the *EntryPoint* with *Tag 1*. In our example, the test function calculates, for instance, for the instance *high* of the metaclass *Level_ResolvedImplementationValues* the corresponding instances *high* of the metaclass *Levels* for every *EntryPoint*. The test function then calculates the for the instance of *EntryPoint_ResolvedImplementationValues* the *HybridConfiguration* containing the *EntryPoint* with *Tag 1*. The test function detects that one of the calculated corresponding instances of *Level*, i.e., *high*, is reachable by the instance of *HybridConfiguration*. The test function calculates this relation for every instance of the metaclass *ResolvedImplementationValue*. Therefore, the test function for the metamodel level succeeds, i.e., $hold_{IC}(E, IC10)$ returns *true* on the model level.

6 Evaluating Accuracy

In this section, we present the injected information flows in Section 6.1. In addition, we present the results of the coupling of the Access Analysis and JOANA for all systems in Section 6.2 as an illustrative example. All detected information flows, the expected vulnerabilities and the found vulnerabilities are captured, amongst other information, in our replication package [34].

6.1 Insertion of Information Flows

To evaluate the increase in accuracy, we modify the implementation to insert information flows that result in values of security characteristics, which are not consistent with the architectural specifications. For introducing the information flows, we use three equivalence classes **EC1** to **EC3** that influence the coupling and the result in the architectural analysis as explained in our coupling approach [35]. *EC1: values of security characteristics of data flowing to an implementation element* classifies the information flows based on whether *same* or *different* values flow to a single sink *SystemElement* element. *EC2: effect on architectural result* classifies the injected information flows by whether they have an *effect* or *no effect* on the architectural analysis result after the coupling. *EC3: visibility of sources of an information flow* classifies the injected information flow by its comprised *System Elements*, i.e., whether the sources of the information flow is *visible* and *hidden* in the architectural analysis.

We introduce flows so that every category of every equivalence class is covered at least once in at least one case. However, not every equivalence class has to be present in every case. With the introduced information flows, we intend to demonstrate the capabilities and pitfalls of coupling static security analyses. As described in Section 3.1, we extend the case study systems, if necessary, by additional implementation and architectural elements to inject these flows.

6.1.1 TravelPlanner

For the TravelPlanner case study, we introduce the following information flows. The flows are represented accumulated for the target system element, as this allows to capture the *multiple* class more concisely. In the Access Analysis, each adversary may see data of specified Security characteristics of data. The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability if an adversary reaches a required or provided interface of a component with data assigned that he/she may not see. This is not the case in the DFA-Ext.

1. We introduce one information flow to the *Parameter ccd_decl* of the *bookFlightOffer Method* in the *Airline* class from the credit card details in the *hidden Field ccd* of the *CreditCardCenter* class (EC3). This flow leaks the *same* (EC1) security characteristic of data *User* from the *ccd* to *ccd_decl* which is classified as *Airline*. This flow is designed to show an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter ccd_decl* of the *bookFlightOffer OperationSignature* in the *OperationProvidedRole* of the *Airline* Component through the coupling as the *ccd User* flows to a system element which is visible to the *Airline*. The introduced information flow tests the coupling's capability to use information flows from system elements not represented in the architectural model. This flow is adapted from Katkalov et al. [23] and Seifermann et al. [41], which both circumvent a declassification of the credit card details in their evaluation. We represent this violation in the implementation by directly using the *hidden Field ccd* and directly passing its content to *bookFlightOffer* of *Airline* without using the *Method declassifyCCD* to perform a proper declassification, i.e., encryption.
2. We introduce two information flows to the *Parameter entry* of the *Method log* in the *AirlineLogger* class which is classified with the Security characteristic of data *Airline* and *Support*. The first flow originates from the *hidden Field ccd* (EC3) in the *CreditCardCenter* classified with the Security characteristic of data *User* as in the first information flow. The second flow originates from the *Parameter discount* (EC3) of the *Method getFlightOffers* of the *Airline* class, which is classified with the Security characteristics of data *Airline* and *TravelAgency* as they are designed to be received by them. Therefore, both flows contribute *different* security characteristics of data (EC1) to the sink system element. Both flows introduce an effect from *ccd* has an *effect* (EC2) for the *OperationProvidedRole* for the *Parameter entry* of the *OperationSignature log* in the *AirlineLogger* component, as the *entry* parameter is only meant to receive data classified as *Support* or *Airline*. We also expect an *effect* for the *OperationRequiredRole* for the *Parameter entry* of the *OperationSignature log* in the *Airline* component in the Access Analysis. For these flows, we do introduce a call to *log* and pass *discount* and *ccd* in the methods *getFlightOffers* and *bookFlightOffer* respectively.
3. Based on the prior introduced flows, the *AirlineLogger* passes all flows the *Parameter entry* of the *storeLog Method* of the *LoggingDB*. This results in *different* security characteristics of data (EC1) from the *hidden Field ccd* (EC3) and *visible Parameter discount* (EC3) to the *Parameter entry*. We expect an *effect* (EC2) for the *OperationProvidedRole* for the *Parameter entry* of the *OperationSignature storeLog* in the *LoggingDB* component. We also expect an *effect* (EC2) for the *OperationRequiredRole* for the *Parameter entry* of the *OperationSignature storeLog* in the *AirlineLogger* component in the Access Analysis.
4. We add an information flow from the *hidden Field passengerdetails* of the *TravelPlanner* (EC3) to the *Parameter passengerDetails* of the *Method bookFlightOffer* in the *Airline*. The *hidden Field passengerDetails* is classified with the Security characteristic of data *User* while the content of the *Parameter* of *bookFlightOffer* is classified with the Security characteristics of data *Airline* and *User*, contributing the *same* (EC1) security characteristic of data. Therefore, the *passengerDetails* should be declassified,

which is not performed. This flow, therefore, also has an *effect* as *passengerDetails* in *bookFlightOffer* is accessible by the *Airline*. For this flow, we have to introduce the *hidden Field passengerdetails* in the *TravelPlanner*.

5. We add a information flow from the *hidden Field passengerDetails* (EC3) of the *TravelPlanner* to a *Parameter details* of the *Method addToFlight* in the *FlightStoring*. This introduces a flow with the same values of security characteristics of data (EC1) as only the *passengerDetails* classified as *User* to the *Parameter passengerDetails* classified with *Airline*. However, this flow must show *no effect* (EC2) in the DFA-Ext. The Access Analysis must show *no effect* (EC2) regarding the provided interface in *FlightStoring*, but must show an *effect* (EC2) in the required interface of the *Airline* class.

In the Access Analysis, each adversary may see data of specified Security characteristics of data. The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability if an adversary reaches a required or provided interface of a component with data assigned that he/she may not see. Due to the injected information flows, we expect the Access Analysis to detect *seven* vulnerabilities and the DFA-Ext to detect *four* vulnerabilities in the *TravelPlanner* after we apply our coupling approach. Due to the injected information flows of the category *no effect*, we expect the integration of *one* value of security characteristic, which should not be reported by the Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext.

6.1.2 JPMail

In the JPMail system, we introduce an information flow in the system by removing the encryption of the *header* and *body* of an email, which is already used in the evaluation of the approach from Seifermann et al. [41] on the architectural level. We use the specification of Tuma et al. [47] and Seifermann et al. [41] of *Attack Zones* for the classification of our introduced flows. The specification states that POP3 and SMTP are located in those *Attack Zones* and that no data with the Security characteristics of data *high* should flow in these zones. Therefore, there is only one path through the system, which leads to the following six not allowed information flows between the parameters *header* and *body* in the *sendEmail Method* of the *MailSendingFacade* class to the parameters *header* and *body* of the *dispatch Method* in the classes POP3, SMTP, and *MailReceivingFacade* class:

1. We introduce a flow from the *visible parameter header* in the *sendEmail* of the *Interface MailSending* of the *MailSendingFacade* class (EC3) with the security characteristic of data *high* to the *parameter header* of the *dispatchMail Method* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* in the class *SMTP* with security characteristic of data *low*. Because there is only one path through the system, this flow is leaking the *same* security characteristic of data value to the *Parameter header* in the *dispatchMail Method* (EC1). This flow has an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter header* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationProvidedRole* of the *SMTP Component* as the *SMTP* is accessible by an attacker.

2. We introduce a flow from the *visible parameter body* in the *sendEmail* of the *Interface MailSending* of the *MailSendingFacade* class (EC3) with the security characteristic of data *high* to the *parameter body* of the *dispatchMail Method* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* in the class *SMTP* with security characteristic of data *low*. Because there is only one path through the system, this flow is leaking the *same* security characteristic of data value to the *Parameter body* in the *dispatchMail Method* (EC1). This flow has an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter body* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationProvidedRole* of the *SMTP Component* as the *SMTP* is accessible by an attacker.
3. We introduce a flow from the *visible parameter header* in the *sendEmail* of the *Interface MailSending* of the *MailSendingFacade* class (EC3) with the security characteristic of data *high* to the *parameter header* of the *dispatchMail Method* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* in the class *POP3* with security characteristic of data *low*. Because there is only one path through the system, this flow is leaking the *same* security characteristic of data value to the *Parameter header* in the *dispatchMail Method* (EC1). This flow has an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter header* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationProvidedRole* of the *POP3 Component* as the *POP3* is accessible by an attacker. This flow also has an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter header* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationRequiredRole* of the *SMTP Component* as the *SMTP* is accessible by an attacker and communicates with *POP3 Component*.
4. We introduce a flow from the *visible parameter body* in the *sendEmail* of the *Interface MailSending* of the *MailSendingFacade* class (EC3) with the security characteristic of data *high* to the *parameter body* of the *dispatchMail Method* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* in the class *POP3* with security characteristic of data *low*. Because there is only one path through the system, this flow is leaking the *same* security characteristic of data value to the *Parameter body* in the *dispatchMail Method* (EC1). This flow has an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter body* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationProvidedRole* of the *POP3 Component* as the *POP3* is accessible by an attacker. This flow also has an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter body* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationRequiredRole* of the *SMTP Component* as the *SMTP* is accessible by an attacker and communicates with *POP3 Component*.
5. We introduce a flow from the *visible parameter header* in the *sendEmail* of the *Interface MailSending* of the *MailSendingFacade* class (EC3) with the security characteristic of data *high* to the *parameter header* of the *dispatchMail Method* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* in the class *MailReceivingFacade* with security characteristic of data *low*. Because there is only one path through the system, this flow is leaking the *same* security characteristic of data value to the *Parameter header* in the *dispatchMail Method* (EC1). This flow has an *effect* (EC2) for the *Parameter header* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationRequiredRole* of the *POP Component* as the *SMTP* is accessible by an attacker and communicates with *MailReceivingFacade Component*.
6. We introduce a flow from the *visible parameter body* in the *sendEmail* of the *Interface MailSending* of the *MailSendingFacade* class (EC3) with the security characteristic of

data *high* to the *parameter body* of the *dispatchMail Method* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* in the class *MailReceivingFacade* with security characteristic of data *low*. Because there is only one path through the system, this flow is leaking the *same* security characteristic of data value to the *Parameter body* in the *dispatchMail Method (EC1)*. This flow has an *effect (EC2)* for the *Parameter body* of the *dispatchMail OperationSignature* in the *OperationRequiredRole* of the *POP Component* as the *SMTP* is accessible by an attacker and communicates with *MailReceivingFacade Component*.

Due to the injected information flows, we expect the Access Analysis to detect *eight* vulnerabilities and the DFA-Ext to detect *four* vulnerabilities in JPMail after we apply our coupling approach.

6.1.3 CoCoMe

In the JPMail system, we introduce an information flow by removing the declassification of the card numbers. Removing declassification mechanisms to create the ground truth for evaluation is an often used practice in related work, such as [41, 23, 47]. We use the specification of Greiner and Herda [18] for the classification of the introduced flows. The specification states that the *number of the payment card* provided by the *Customer* must only be printed declassified, i.e., the last four digits. We extend this scenario by stating that the *Cashier* must also not be allowed to see this information. We inject an information flow violating this by omitting the declassification in the *Component Billing*.

This omitted declassifications leads to the following two not allowed information flows:

1. With the omitted declassification, we introduce an information flow from the *visible Parameter number (EC3)* of the *Method readCardNumber* of the *Class CardReader* with the values of security characteristics of data *Customer* and *Bank* to the *Parameter number* of the *Method readCardNumber* of the *Class CashDesk* which is specified with the values of security characteristic of data *Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager*. There is only one flow to the *Parameter number* of the *Method readCardNumber* of the *Class CashDesk* which is specified with the values of security characteristic of data *Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager*. Consequently, this flows leaks the *same* security characteristic of data values (**EC1**). This flow has an *effect (EC2)* on the *Parameter number* of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* from the *OperationInterface ReaderIf* provided by the *Component CashDesk* as now the full number of the payment card specified, which should only be accessible by the *Customer* and *Bank*, are now also accessible for the *Cashier*. More explicitly, the leaked information is specified with the values *Customer* and *Bank* (*Parameter number* of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface ReaderIf* provided by the *Component CardReader*), while the *Parameter number* of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* of the *Component CashDesk* which is specified with the values of security characteristic of data *Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager*.

2. With the omitted declassification, we also introduce an information flow from the *visible* *Parameter number* of the *Method readCardNumber* of the *Class CardReader* (EC3) with the values of security characteristics of data *Customer* and *Bank* to the *Parameter cardNumber* of the *Method printPaymentCard* of the *Class Printer* which is specified with the values of security characteristic of data *Bank*, *ByStander*, *Cashier*, *Customer* and *StoreManager*. This flow arises because the *CashDesk* passes the now non-declassified version of the number of the payment card to this method. There is only one transitive flow to the *Parameter cardNumber* of the *Method printPaymentCard* of the *Class Printer* (specified with the values of security characteristic of data *Bank*, *ByStander*, *Cashier*, *Customer* and *StoreManager*). Consequently, this flows leaks the *same* security characteristic of data values (EC1). This flow has an *effect* on the *Parameter cardNumber* of the *OperationSignature printPaymentCard* of the *Component Printer* as now the full number of the payment card specified, which should only be access by the *Customer* and *Bank*, are now accessible also for the *ByStander* and the *Cashier*.

Due to the injected information flows, we expect the Access Analysis to detect *three* vulnerabilities and the DFA-Ext to detect *two* vulnerabilities in CoCoMe after we apply our coupling approach. The difference between both analyses arises because the DFA-Ext does not consider *Operation Required Roles*, while the Access Analysis does so. In consequence, the Access Analysis and DFA-Ext must identify vulnerabilities for the *OperationProvidedRoles* involving the *Parameter cardNumber* of the *OperationSignature printPaymentCard* of the *Component Printer* and the *Parameter number* of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* of the *Component CashDesk*. However, the Access Analysis also reports a vulnerability for the *OperationRequiredRole* involving the *Parameter cardNumber* of the *OperationSignature printPaymentCard* in the *OperationInterface PrinterIf* required by the *CashDesk*, i.e., which is now also visible for the *Cashier*.

6.1.4 Eclipse Secure Storage

In Eclipse Secure Storage, we inject an information flow by removing an existing encryption of the *password*. This *password* is encrypted with an internal password which is created from the *challengeResponse* comprising the questions to restore the *master password* and the answers a ser has to provide. Removing declassification mechanisms such as encryption to create the ground truth for evaluation is an often used practice in related work, such as [41, 23, 47].

1. In Eclipse Secure Storage, we inject a single information flow from the *visible* (EC3) parameter *challengeResponse* of the service *setUpRecovery* provided by the *Password-Management* component, classified with the value of security characteristic of data *high*. This injections has already been investigated by Tuma et al. [48]. As illustrated in Listing 3.2, we remove the encryption of the password derived from the answers in *challengeResponse* to provide, instead, the password directly to the service *internalPut* of the *SecurePreferences* component by the parameter *value* classified as *low*. Since

we are the ones who introduce the encryption, we do not remove it when storing the question. Consequently, the result is unusable in our evaluation, because we already know that retaining the encryption will cause a vulnerability.. Since we inject just a single flow, it leaks the *same* security characteristic of data (EC1), specifically, from the *high* classified *challengeResponse* of the service *setupRecovery* to the *low* classified *value* of the service *internalPut*. This injected flow has an *effect* (EC2) because we model the *Component SecurityPreferences* and its services to be accessible by an *Attacker*.

Due to the injected information flows, we expect the Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext to detect *one* vulnerability in Eclipse Secure Storage after we apply our coupling approach.

Not considered Information Flow. When investigating the Eclipse Secure Storage implementation, we found an implicit information flow from the *Parameter challengeResponse* of the *Method setupRecovery* to the parameter *pathName* of the *Method nodeExists* from the *Class SecurePreferences*. We also found this issue with *JOANA*. However, this information flow cannot be found from CodeQL-Ext because it only investigates data flows in contrast to implicit information flows. While we acknowledge the existence of this vulnerability and the existence shows that selecting analyses in the coupling is important, we do not count the vulnerabilities in the coupling arising from this implicit flow. We do this because we did not explicitly introduce this implicit flow and because it cannot be found with CodeQL-Ext.

6.2 Results of the Accuracy Evaluation for Access Analysis and JOANA

This section describes the evaluation results in investigating the accuracy of the coupling of Access Analysis and JOANA. We injected information flows according to section 6.1. In every case, the recall r is 1, i.e., we found every expected outcome. However, in several cases with *JOANA*, a precision $p < 1$ has been found, i.e., when the coupling reported false positive vulnerabilities f_p . We discuss these false positives isolated in Section 6.2.2. This is why we first discuss the true positive results and their interpretation of the cases involving the Access Analysis and *JOANA* for all systems, i.e., *TravelPlanner*, *JPMail*, *CoCoMe* and *Eclipse Secure Storage*. Then, we discuss the false positives explicitly later in this section. We provide all results in our replication package [34].

6.2.1 Illustration of the True Positive Results

In this section, we discuss the true positive results of our evaluation of accuracy regarding the coupling of Access Analysis and *JOANA* for all systems.

6.2.1.1 Access Analysis, JOANA and TravelPlanner

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter ccd_decl* of the *OperationSignature bookFlightOffer* in the *Interface AirlineBooking* from the *Component AirlineBooking* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (1.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned only the *DataSet User* instead of *Airline* and *User* as before. However, this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Airline*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Airline*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

The Access Analysis reports two vulnerabilities after the coupling for the injected information flow (2.) in Section 6.1. The *DataSets* assigned to *Parameter entry* of the *OperationSignature log* in the *Interface AirlineLogging* after the coupling is *User* compared to *Airline* and *Support* without the coupling. The first vulnerability is reported for the *Component Airline* due to its *OperationRequiredRole* to *AirlineLogging* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Airline*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Airline*. The second vulnerability is reported for the *Component AirlineLogger* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* to *AirlineLogging* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Airline*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Airline*. Both vulnerabilities are *expected* because both results are of the *effect* category, counting as two true positives t_p .

The Access Analysis reports two vulnerabilities after the coupling for the injected information flow (3.) in Section 6.1. The *DataSets* assigned to *Parameter entry* of the *OperationSignature storeLog* in the *Interface LogStorage* after the coupling is *Airline*, *User* and *TravelAgency* compared to *Support* without the coupling. The first vulnerability is reported for the *Component AirlineLogger* due to its *OperationRequiredRole* to *LogStoring* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Support*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Support*. The second vulnerability is reported for the *Component LoggingDB* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* to *AirlineLogging* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Support*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Support*. Both vulnerabilities are *expected* because both results are of the *effect* category, counting as two true positives t_p .

The Access Analysis reports one vulnerability after the coupling for the injected information flow (4.) in Section 6.1. The *DataSets* assigned to *Parameter passengerDetails* of the *OperationSignature bookFlightOffer* in the *Interface AirlineBooking* after the coupling is *User* compared to *Airline* and *User* without the coupling. The vulnerability is reported for the *Component Airline* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* to *AirlineBooking* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Airline*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Airline*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

Despite the injected information flow (5.) in Section 6.1, the Access Analysis reports no vulnerability for the *Parameter details* of the *OperationSignature addToFlight* in the *Interface*

FlightStoring for the *OperationProvidedRole* of the component *FlightStorage*, despite its assigned *DataSet User* after the coupling compared to *Airline* before. No vulnerability is reported because no *Adversary* can access the location on which the *FlightStorage* with the *OperationProvidedRole* is deployed. No report of a vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *no effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p . In contrast, the Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for *Parameter details* of the *OperationSignature addToFlight* in the *Interface FlightStoring* for the *OperationRequiredRole* of the component *Airline* after the coupling due to the injected information flow (5.) in Section 6.1. Again, the assigned *DataSet* is *User* after the coupling compared to *Airline* before. The vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Airline*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Airline*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

We did not design an information flow to the *Parameter flightId* of the *OperationSignature addToFlights* in the *Interface FlightStoring* for which *Airline* has an *OperationRequiredRole*. Still, JOANA reported information flows to this *Parameter*, which results due to our coupling in the annotated *DataSets User* and *Support* compared to *Airline* before. The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Airline*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Airline*. As we did not *expect* this vulnerability in our study design, we count it as a false positive f_p .

6.2.1.2 Access Analysis, JOANA and JPMail

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter header* of the *OperationSignature dispatchMail* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* from the *Component SMTP* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (1.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned only the *DataSet high* instead of *low* as before. However, this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker* due to the allocation of *SMTP* in the *Location AttackZone*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter body* of the *OperationSignature dispatchMail* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* from the *Component SMTP* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (2.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned only the *DataSet high* instead of *low* as before. However, this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker* due to the allocation of *SMTP* in the *Location AttackZone*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

The Access Analysis reports two vulnerabilities after the coupling for the injected information flow (3.) in Section 6.1. The *DataSets* assigned to *Parameter header* of the *OperationSignature dispatchMail* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* after the coupling are *high* compared to *low* without the coupling. The first vulnerability is reported for the *Component*

SMTP due to its *OperationRequiredRole* to *EMailDispatchment* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. The second vulnerability is reported for the *Component POP3* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* to *EMailDispatchment* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. Both vulnerabilities are *expected* because both results are of the *effect* category, counting as two true positives t_p

The Access Analysis reports two vulnerabilities after the coupling for the injected information flow (4.) in Section 6.1. The *DataSets* assigned to *Parameter body* of the *OperationSignature dispatchMail* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* after the coupling are *high* compared to *low* without the coupling. The first vulnerability is reported for the *Component SMTP* due to its *OperationRequiredRole* to *EMailDispatchment* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. The second vulnerability is reported for the *Component POP3* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* to *EMailDispatchment* because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. Both vulnerabilities are *expected* because both results are of the *effect* category, counting as two true positives t_p

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter header* of the *OperationSignature dispatchMail* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* from the *Component POP3* due to its *OperationRequiredRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (5.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned only the *DataSet high* instead of *low* as before. However, this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker* due to the allocation of *POP3* in the *Location AttackZone*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p . There is no report for the component *MailReceivingFacade* as it is not located in the *AttackZone*.

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter body* of the *OperationSignature dispatchMail* in the *Interface EMailDispatchment* from the *Component POP3* due to its *OperationRequiredRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (6.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned only the *DataSet high* instead of *low* as before. However, this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker* due to the allocation of *POP3* in the *Location AttackZone*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *low*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p . There is no report for the component *MailReceivingFacade* as it is not located in the *AttackZone*.

6.2.1.3 Access Analysis, JOANA and CoCoMe

The Access Analysis reports all three expected information flows after the coupling with *JOANA* when applied on *CoCoME*. The Access Analysis reports the following three true positive vulnerabilities.

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter number* of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface CardReaderIf* provided by the *Component CashDesk* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (1.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned the *DataSets Bank* and *Customer* in contrast to *Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager* from before the coupling. However, the *Parameter number* is accessible by the *Adversary Cashier* due to the allocation of the *Component CashDesk* on the *ResourceContainer OutputDevice* in the *Location CashDesk*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Cashier*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter cardNumber* of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface PrinterIf* provided by the *Component Printer* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (2.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned the *DataSets Bank* and *Customer* in contrast to *Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager* from before the coupling. However, the *Parameter cardNumber* is accessible by the *Adversary ByStander* due to the allocation of the *Component Printer* on the *ResourceContainer OutputDevice* in the *Location Queue*. The *Adversary ByStander* may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *ByStander*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter cardNumber* of the *OperationSignature readCardNumber* in the *OperationInterface PrinterIf* required by the *Component CashDesk* due to its *OperationRequiredRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (2.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned the *DataSets Bank* and *Customer* in contrast to *Bank, ByStander, Cashier, Customer* and *StoreManager* from before the coupling. However, the *Parameter cardNumber* is accessible by the *Adversary Cashier* due to the allocation of the *Component CashDesk* on the *ResourceContainer CashDeskPC* in the *Location CashDesk*. The *Adversary Cashier* may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *ByStander*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

6.2.1.4 Access Analysis, JOANA and EclipseSecureStorage

The Access Analysis reports the expected vulnerability after the coupling with JOANA when applied on EclipseSecureStorage.

The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter value* of the *OperationSignature internalPut* in the *OperationInterface ISecurePreferencesMain* provided by the *Component SecurePreferences* due to its *OperationProvidedRole* after the coupling for the injected information flow (1.) in Section 6.1. This vulnerability is reported because this *Parameter* has now been assigned the *DataSets High* in contrast to *Low* from before the coupling. This vulnerability is reported because the *Parameter value* is accessible by the *Adversary Attacker* due to the allocation of the *Component SecurePreferences* on the *ResourceContainer*

DataBase in the *Location Attack*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSet low*. This vulnerability is *expected* because the result is of the *effect* category, counting as a true positive t_p .

6.2.2 Discussion of False Positives

We now discuss the false positive results in our evaluation. These false positives arise in the following cases: (1) Access Analysis, *JOANA* and *TravelPlanner* (2) Access Analysis, *JOANA* and *Eclipse Secure Storage* (3) *DFA-Ext*, *JOANA* and *Eclipse Secure Storage*.

The false positives in cases (2) and (3) are the same. Consequently, we report them together in the following.

Access Analysis, *JOANA* and *TravelPlanner* In the *TravelPlanner*, the Access Analysis reports a vulnerability for the *Parameter flightId* of the *OperationSignature addToFlights* in the *Interface FlightStoring* for which *Airline* has an *OperationRequiredRole*. We did not design an information flow to the *Parameter flightId* of the *OperationSignature addToFlights* in the *Interface FlightStoring*. This flow occurs because *JOANA* reports information flows to the *Parameter flightId* of the *Method addToFlight* in the *AirlineStorage* class. However, we did not design such a flow. Still, *JOANA* reported information flows to this *Parameter*, which results from our coupling in the annotated *DataSets User* and *Support* compared to *Airline* before. The Access Analysis reports a vulnerability because this *Parameter* is accessible by the *Adversary Airline*, which may only access data annotated with *DataSets* including *Airline*.

This vulnerability is reported in the Access Analysis but not in the *DFA-Ext*. This is because the change of the values of the *Security Characteristic* affects the *OperationProvidedRole* and the *OperationRequiredRole*. The Access Analysis reports the vulnerability due to the *OperationRequiredRole*, which is not considered by the *DFA-Ext*.

Still, *JOANA* reports for both couplings the same information flows and both couplings process them similarly. *CodeQL* does not report any such flow. However, *CodeQL* only considers direct information flows (data flows) but not indirect flows (information flow through control flows). As we do not have another information flow analysis available analyzing direct and indirect flow, we cannot verify whether the flows to *Parameter flightId* of the *OperationSignature addToFlights* in the *Interface FlightStoring* are correct or incorrect. If they are correct, we did not consider them in the source code correctly. If the flows are incorrect, our assumption about the accuracy of the source code analyses [35] is wrong. In any case, as we did not *expect* this vulnerability in our study design, we count it as a false positive f_p .

Access Analysis or DFA-Ext, JOANA and Eclipse Secure Storage In the Eclipse Secure Storage, both the Access Analysis and the DFA-Ext report two vulnerabilities in the coupling with JOANA: The first false positive occurs because JOANA reports an (unexpected) information flow from the *Parameter challengeResponse* of the *OperationSignature setupRecovery* in the *Class PasswordManagement* to the *Parameter key* in the *Method internalPut* of the *Class SecurePreferences*. Our coupling changes the value of the security characteristic of data representing confidentiality levels for both, Access Analysis and DFA-Ext from *low* to *high* for the *Parameter key* in the *OperationSignature internalPut* of the *OperationInterface ISecurePreferences*, which is provided by the *Component SecurePreferences* by a *OperationProvidedRole*. This vulnerability is reported because the *Component SecurePreferences* is allocated on the *Resource Container DataBase*, which is accessible by an attacker who may only know data annotated with the value *low*. As we did not expect this outcome, we count this result as one false positive f_p for the cases of Access Analysis and DFA-Ext being coupled with JOANA and applied in EclipseSecureStorage. We investigated this unexpected information flow further. We see no reason for this information flow as *challengeResponse* does not interact with the *Parameter key* except that it is used in the same *Method internalPut*. We assume that JOANA over-approximated in this case by flagging all parameters in the same *Method*. However, we cannot fully confirm or reject this assumption due to the lack of other information flow analyses investigating implicit information flows. A similar unexpected information flow is also reported in the case Access Analysis, JOANA and TravelPlanner, where the *Parameter flightId* was flagged in addition to the expected *Parameter details*.

The second false positive occurs because JOANA reports an (unexpected) information flow from the *Parameter challengeResponse* of the *Method setupRecovery* in the *Class PasswordManagement* to the *Parameter pathName* in the *Method node* of the *Class SecurePreferences*. Our coupling changes the value of the security characteristic of data representing confidentiality levels for both, Access Analysis and DFA-Ext from *low* to *high* for the *Parameter pathName* in the *OperationSignature node* of the *OperationInterface ISecurePreferences*, which is provided by the *Component SecurePreferences* by a *OperationProvidedRole*. This vulnerability is reported because the *Component SecurePreferences* is allocated on the *Resource Container DataBase*, which is accessible by an attacker who may only know data annotated with the value *low*. As we did not expect this outcome, we count this result as one false positive f_p for the cases of Access Analysis and DFA-Ext being coupled with JOANA and applied in EclipseSecureStorage. We investigated this unexpected information flow further. However, we see no indications of how this flow exists because the *Method node* is only called with constants in the *Method setupRecovery*. Consequently, also here we see no reason for this information flow as *challengeResponse* does not interact with the *Parameter pathName* except.

In both cases, we cannot confirm or reject whether JOANA shows overapproximative behavior. Still, another probable scenario is that we do not identify all existing implicit information flows in EclipseSecureStorage, leading to our unexpected results. However, in the context of our case study, this outcome illustrates a possible scenario where the coupling expert is not an expert in the domain of the source code analysis. In consequence, even for the coupling expert, it is hard to predict the outcome of a coupling when selecting a specific analysis.

We want to highlight one more report of the architectural analysis in the coupling. *JOANA* reports an information flow from the *Parameter challengeResponse* of the *Method setupRecovery* in the *Class PasswordManagement* to the *Parameter key* in the *Method remove* of the *Class SecurePreferences*. This flow exists because the *Method setupRecovery* determines whether *challengeResponse* is null and, if so, the content fitting to the constant parameter *key*, i.e., the answers are removed in *SecurePreferences*. Due to the null-check, *JOANA* detects an implicit information flow to the *Parameter key*. This is why our coupling changes the values of the security characteristic of data annotated to the *Parameter key* of the *OperationSignature remove* in the *OperationInterface ISecurePreferencesMain*, which is provided by the *Component SecurePreferences* by an *OperationProvidedRole* from the value *low* to *high*. This implicit information flow already exists in the implementation used by Tuma et al. [48]. This results in a vulnerability reported by Access Analysis and DFA-Ext because *SecurePreferences* is allocated on the *ResourceContainer DataBase*, which can be accessed by an attacker.

We were aware of this vulnerability beforehand in our inspection of the implementation. We did not fix this vulnerability beforehand, in contrast to the encryption of the questions (see Section 3.4), because this null-check comprised more than a single statement which could have the potential to remove other unexpected information flows. In addition, this flow could only be found with *JOANA* and not with CodeQL-Ext because it results from an implicit information flow. As we could not influence this information flow and would have a biased report in favor of one Analysis (*JOANA* would knowingly report a Vulnerability or CodeQL-Ext would not detect one), which we know beforehand. This would already influence our evaluation results. Consequently, we want to highlight this existing flow and its consequences without considering it in the evaluation results.

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